

D3.1 Report on the developed methods and indicators framework

JUSTNature | Work Package 3, Task 3.1

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ABBREVIATION LIST

Term	Description
CE	Circular Economy
CiPeL	City Practice Lab
CUM	Circular Urban Metabolism
DiD	Difference in Differences
DPSIR	Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response
ES	Ecosystem services
ESVD	Ecosystem Services Valuation Database
EJ	Ecological Justice
FFH	Flora Fauna Habitat
GA	Grant Agreement
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
MCDA	Multicriteria Decision Analysis
LSW	Local Stakeholder Workshop
NbS	Nature-based Solutions
PM	Particulate Matter
RACER	Relevant, Acceptable, Credible, Easy, Robust
RCT	Randomized Control trial
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Accepted,
UHI	Urban Heat Island
UM	Urban Metabolism
UTCI	Urban Thermal Comfort Index

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present deliverable reports on the results of Task 3.1 Evolving indicator framework to an integrated life-cycle approach.

Nature-based solutions (NbS) bear an undeniable potential towards supporting a just transition to sustainable, circular urban environments and there appears a need for a comprehensive NbS evaluation that will effectively monitor and evaluate the performance and impact of NbS interventions, as well as the progress toward Circular Urban Metabolism (CUM) and urban sustainability while assuring that the outcomes will equally affect all human and non-human groups.

JUSTNature proposes the development of an Ecological Justice – Circularity indicator framework for Low-carbon | High air quality NbS that is defined as a **system of indicators to holistically monitor and evaluate the performance and impacts of Low Carbon| High air quality NbS** interventions at neighborhood/city scale, **synthesizing previously identified NbS indicators** while **combining the principles of (i) sustainability, (ii) circularity, and (iii) justice**

The development of the Ecological Justice – Circularity indicator framework was based on a set of criteria that characterize it in relation to its potential to measure progress towards CUM, ecological justice and the sustainable development goals. Stemming from the concept definition of the framework, the criteria for the three principles are called **concept criteria**.

Moreover, a set of criteria is defined for the indicators that compose the framework. The set of criteria for the indicators includes **technical criteria** that characterize the indicators regarding their computation methodology, data requirements, and ease of use. In addition, the indicators are also assessed for their potential to measure progress towards CUM, EJ and the sustainable development goals (concept criteria for the indicators). For each of the indicator criteria, scores were given as follows:

- Technical criteria: 0=no; 1=partially/difficult; 2=yes
- Concept criteria:
 - CUM relevance: 0=no; 1 yes, indirectly; 2=yes, directly
 - Ecological justice criterion: 0=no; 1=has the potential; 2=yes
 - SDG relevance: this is an on/off criterion, 0=no; 2=yes

Eventually, in transitioning from the indicator criteria to the framework criteria, two groups of criteria were formed for characterizing the framework as well: technical and concept. Each of the framework criteria expresses qualities of the framework and they receive a score, resulting from the scores of the indicators that comprise the framework. Effectively, the framework's score for each of the criteria/qualities results from inclusion of relevant indicators.

Framework criteria		Explanation
TECHNICAL	Credibility	The framework is composed of credible indicators with transparent methodology and unambiguous interpretation
	Applicability	The application of the framework is based on applicable indicators. The required data are easily accessible at no/low cost.
	Ability to track temporal changes	The framework is composed of indicators that track changes and determine the degree to which goals are achieved over time.
CONCEPT	CUM Validity	The Framework includes indicators relevant to CUM aspects
	Relevance to sustainable development	The Framework includes indicators relevant to specific SDGs
	Ecological Justice	The Framework includes indicators that can measure ecological justice

The indicators that comprise the framework bring their attributes into the framework and ultimately, the framework is characterized by the set of indicators that comprise it. The attributes of the indicators are expressed through the scores that the indicators have received for each of the indicator criteria. The scores are used as inputs for calculating the qualities of the framework. Therefore, different compositions of indicators form frameworks with different qualities.

The creation of the indicator framework entails an iterative step-by-step approach. This stepwise process has been followed by the JUSTNature CiPeLs leading to a tailored evaluation framework for each CiPeL. Eventually, frameworks with varying indicator compositions and results in their qualities have been created. The created frameworks per CiPeL are not directly comparable since they were designed to evaluate different NbS, derived from different needs and their primary purpose is to assist the CiPeLs in aligning with the specific objectives of the proposed interventions.

Within, as well as beyond JUSTNature, the cities can use the evaluation of the framework for checking alignment with their objectives and targets and ensuring that they have in hand a credible and applicable indicator framework that can measure and provide insights on critical areas of ecological injustices, transition to circularity and sustainable urban development. In that sense, the developed ecological justice – circularity indicator frameworks are not static, but rather flexible and their qualities will change by adding or removing indicators with changing plans and objectives.

Underpinning the logic of NbS is the promise of a double dividend. One part of this dividend is the cost-saving secured by harnessing ecosystem services to meet needs that would otherwise require an engineered solution. The other part comprises the myriad co-benefits that the ecosystem provides. Notwithstanding this promise, the implementation of NbS necessarily requires a change in the status quo, which brings its own attendant costs. Impact evaluations are especially important because they attempt to infer a causal

relationship between an intervention and a (set of) outcome indicator(s) and ascribe the changes to the NbS itself. A holistic impact assessment almost certainly requires consideration of multiple indicators using a mix of methodological approaches. Methodological approaches, including ones that are appropriate for the data sparse environments that often characterize NbS interventions, are available and a common feature of each approach is the identification of control site(s) that serve as a comparison with the site of the NbS. This feature is often required for inferring causality, but it raises the question of how to ensure that such sites are sufficiently “comparable.”

To select suitable sites, the monitoring team needs to ensure for all areas of performance that (1) all sites follow parallel trends, (2) timing of data collection takes into account the impact onset, (3) sites are distant enough to avoid spillover effects, but close enough to maximize latent similarity, (4) effective dosage and how it scales is considered when comparing sites of different sizes, (5) and the role of the sites in larger relevant systems are similar. To support this process, the document offers a process and the key variables to assess comparability, an algorithm to quantitatively synthesize these variables in a single comparability metric, using publicly available data, an overview of existing NbS databases to find benchmark sites, and a machine-learning method to generate synthetic control sites in the absence of a real control.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Aims and objectives

The present deliverable reports on the results of Task 3.1 Evolving indicator framework to an integrated life-cycle approach.

The main aim of this task was the development of an NbS indicator framework for the evaluation of the Low-carbon | High air quality NbS functions and services. The framework was envisioned to be built upon existing NbS indicators while integrating a circularity perspective. NbS implementation is linked to realization of circularity in cities, but currently NbS assessments lack this perspective (Atanasova et al., 2021). T3.1 set out to integrate the circularity perspective into the development of the indicator framework building on the concepts of urban metabolism and circular economy.

NbS evaluation frameworks have been established from previous NbS projects with the first comprehensive framework introduced by the ECLIPSE project (Raymond et al., 2017). Building upon the ECLIPSE and integrating the collective experience of H2020 funded projects, the European Commission published a handbook for guiding monitoring and evaluation of NbS (European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2021). The handbook identifies 12 societal challenges that NbS can serve as mitigation means, and proposes indicators suited to measure the impact of NbS in each challenge.

JUSTNature, specifically focusses on the implementation of NbS as a means for transitioning to low-carbon cities. Such transition should be achieved respecting the principle of ecological justice, benefiting both human and non-human urban populations. With this in mind, already in Deliverable 2.1 Conceptual & action framework on Low carbon | High air quality NbS potentials, considerations for evolving the existing NbS indicators towards capturing the ecological space (in-)justices are discussed. This can be achieved not least by integration of disaggregated data on social variables and spatial analysis into the indicator calculation (Gantioler et al., 2023). Therefore, one of the objectives for the development of the framework was to propose adjustments to the existing NbS indicators for integrating the justice perspective.

Along with the development of an indicator framework (and the reason for its development) comes the NbS performance and impact evaluation. Although performance indicators are straightforward in their interpretation, a credible impact evaluation presupposes understanding causality. Essentially this entails the selection of a suitable methodology for the evaluation task at hand. The second aim of task 3.1, was to investigate the methodological obstacles for inferring causality and propose a methodology for identifying control sites and assessing comparability.

2.1.1 Link with other project activities

The work of Task 3.1 for the development of the indicator framework that is reported herein built upon previous work of [Task 2.1](#) and [Task 2.2](#). Specifically, commencement of Task 3.1 followed completion of Task 2.1. The two tasks are aligned by integrating the [6 areas of injustices that](#) were defined in Task 2.1, in the development of the indicator framework by distributing NbS indicators into the 6 thematic areas. In addition, the baskets of indicators that were formed in Deliverable [2.1](#) (Gantioler et al., 2023), were also integrated in the indicator framework of Task 3.1. The indicators needed for the formulation of the [socio-ecological profiles](#) as part of Task 2.2, are also part of the indicator framework.

Following-up the completion of their activities, Task 3.1 and Task 2.2 are planning a common approach for communicating to the city partners the connection of the tools that have been produced through the two tasks and how these can be used for strategic decision making. This is planned to take place in October 2023 during the collaborative workshop and the details will be reported as part of the associated report under [Task 4.2](#). Task 3.1 has also used input from [Task 4.2](#); the results of the local stakeholder workshops 1 and 2 (T4.2) guided the selection of indicators for creating a tailored indicator framework in each city according to its challenges and NbS interventions.

Task 3.1 indirectly links with [WP5 activities](#) for the implementation of the NbS since the evaluation framework can be considered indispensable to any NbS implementation. A direct link exists between T3.1 and [Task 6.2](#) where selected indicators will be visualized through the [digital twins](#). Furthermore, alignment with the [co-governance indicator framework](#) that is developed in [WP7](#) has been examined and is continuously cross-checked. The two tasks converge in their approach to form state-of-the-art lists of indicators from which the city partners are asked to select based on relevance.

Within WP3, Task 3.1 feeds into [Task 3.2](#) and [Task 3.3](#), the first by indicating monitoring requirements for measuring sensor-based indicators and the second builds upon Task 3.1 for developing the decision support tools for NbS long-term planning and operation.

Finally, the proposed framework has been added in the [Innovations Registry](#) of [WP8](#) and a scientific publication based on the work reported herein is planned in support of the project's dissemination ([WP9](#)).

2.2 Deliverable outline

The present section ([Section 2](#)) serves as introduction to the aims and objectives of T3.1 and places the task among other JUSTNature activities that feed into it or are fed by it. The remainder of the report is structured as follows:

[Section 3](#) sets the background of the main concepts that underpin the proposed framework of indicators. The chapter introduces the concepts of urban metabolism and circularity as well as the sustainable approach to urban metabolism which, embodying the perspective of

circularity, can become circular urban metabolism and support the transition to sustainable urban environments. Moreover, in this chapter, the nexus between the urban metabolism patterns and socio-ecological justice in cities is highlighted, along with the role that NbS play in achieving circular urban metabolism. The section closes with the definition and proposal for an Ecological Justice – Circularity indicator framework for Low-carbon | High air quality NbS, that combines the principles of (i) sustainability, (ii) circularity, and (iii) justice.

Section 4 moves forward to present the process that was followed for developing the Ecological Justice – Circularity indicator framework for Low-carbon | High air quality NbS. Being primarily an NbS evaluation framework, it is structured using as basis state of the art NbS indicators. These indicators, and consequently the framework, were evaluated (scored) according to criteria that derived from the literature. In this section the rational for selection of criteria, and the calculations that link the indicator scores to the framework scores, are explained. Finally, although not being part of the task 3.1 description, while performing the indicator scoring, the development of a tool that visualizes the indicator criteria and associated scores was investigated. Information about this tool is provided in the final part of this section.

Section 5 focuses on the tailored indicator frameworks that have been developed for the City Practice Labs (CiPeL). The section starts with the explanation of the process that was followed for developing the tailored indicator frameworks. Next, the characterization of the frameworks, based on the framework criteria that were defined in section 4, is presented along with a discussion that reflects on the differences among the various frameworks.

Section 6 addresses the topic of NbS impact assessments, the methodological obstacles that arise when trying to ascribe causal effects and the methodological approaches that can be considered for quantifying the changes in indicators. The section goes on to discuss implementation of the various methodological approaches with necessary adjustments per justice area in order to achieve benchmarking and selection of control sites that can serve as comparison with the intervention site. A methodology for assessing comparability and identifying control sites is eventually proposed. The section closes with a review of existing databases and a discussion of data-driven approaches to impact assessment.

Section 7 concludes the deliverable highlighting the main outcomes of the reported work.

3 CONCEPT DEFINITION OF THE EVOLVING INDICATOR FRAMEWORK

3.1 Background on main concepts

3.1.1 The sustainable transformation pursuit

Within an intensified urbanization process, cities are confronted with a multitude of urban societal challenges that pose severe environmental consequences and compromise the overall quality of life (Liang, Wang, & Li, 2019). As cities expand, their energy demand increases to cover the needs for transport, industrial and commercial activities, buildings and infrastructure, water distribution, and food production. Due to the increase of the required amounts of energy and resources, cities are becoming more and more dependent on surrounding ecosystems, pressuring the planet's natural resources. Moreover, the urban sprawl and increasing demand of resources creates within cities various socioeconomic problems, such as increasing inequalities, poverty, and social exclusion (United Nations Population Fund - UNFPA, 2016).

In addition to being major consumers of resources, cities are also producers of waste and pollutants, being responsible for the emission of 60–80% of global greenhouse gas emissions. Asian cities are the biggest carbon emitters, but when comparing emissions per capita, cities in developed countries present higher emissions than in developing countries (Wei, Wu, & Chen, 2021). This observation relates to global inequalities of who pollutes and who bears the burden (Chancel, 2022; Hubacek et al., 2017). More so, such inequalities within countries and cities are associated with ranging socio-economic status (Büchs & Schnepf, 2013).

Cities are currently home to 55% of the human population and they are expected to accommodate about 70% of the world's population by 2050. In high-income countries the urban population already reaches 80%, and for middle-income countries the percentage ranges from 50% to 80% (Ritchie & Roser, 2018). The increasing population in conjunction with environmental and socioeconomic problems makes the urban systems multidimensional and very complex. In the face of the increasing complexity of the urban systems, urban planning and management require a more inclusive and sustainable approach to confront all challenges efficiently and simultaneously and comply with the residents' needs (Sodiq et al., 2019).

New holistic approaches are needed that integrate efficient monitoring and management of production and consumption, minimize waste production and energy losses, increase resilience, and promote social equity. Cities must become focal players in driving sustainable transformation while maintaining economic growth and population well-being. This is clearly highlighted in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (UN, 2015). Especially, tackling the climate change and achieving optimal resource consumption are critical within urban environments (Krellenberg, Bergsträßer, Bykova, Kress, & Tyndall, 2019; Sanchez Rodriguez, Ürge-Vorsatz, & Barau, 2018). This is emphasized by the dedication of two SDGs.

SDG 11 aims to “make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable,” and SDG 12 aims to “ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns”.

Even in the face of the myriad environmental and social challenges, cities can be part of the solution in overcoming them. Economically, cities punch well above their weight, accounting for more than 80% of global GDP (World Bank, 2023). They are focal points of the human ingenuity that arises from agglomeration effects. When people and firms can readily share knowledge, infrastructure, and culture, the resulting benefits are numerous, including higher productivity, lower transportation costs, greater efficiency of resource use, as well as the social cohesion that comes from exposure to new ideas. The high density of cities – their defining feature but also the source of many of the environmental stressors cited above – makes them ideal settings for the introduction of nature-based solutions. This is particularly the case when not only designed as a transformative action to tackle several challenges simultaneously but when reframing human-nature relationships by focusing on the regenerative potential for healthy and just urban landscapes (Welden, Chausson, & Melanidis, 2021).

3.1.2 Urban metabolism and circular economy as tools to promote sustainable development

In the effort to develop sustainable cities and communities, the study of urban metabolism (UM) is particularly relevant (Céspedes Restrepo & Morales-Pinzón, 2018; Ulgiati & Zucaro, 2019). Urban metabolism can be defined as “the sum of the technical and socio-economic processes that occur in cities, resulting in growth, production of energy, and elimination of waste” (Christopher Kennedy, Cuddihy, & Engel-Yan, 2007). The introduction of urban metabolism can be traced back to Karl Marx’s work “Capital”, who used the term “metabolism” to create a connection between economy and ecology. Wolman in 1965 was the first to quantify urban metabolism components based on information for production and consumption when studying inflows and outflows of a hypothetical US city of one million inhabitants (Wolman, 1965). Research on urban metabolism continued in the following decades. Some indicative cases for cities around the world are New York (Kane & Erickson, 2007), Los Angeles (Ngo & Pataki, 2008), Paris (Barles, 2009), Lisbon (Niza, Rosado, & Ferrdo, 2009), Beijing (Y. Zhang, Yang, Liu, & Yu, 2011), Bogota (Alfonso Piña & Pardo Martínez, 2014), Cape Town (Hoekman & von Blottnitz, 2017). Comparative studies were conducted among global megacities (S. Chen et al., 2020; Han et al., 2018; C. A. Kennedy et al., 2015), Swedish cities (Rosado, Kalmykova, & Patrício, 2017), Chinese cities (Wang, Li, Liu, & Zhang, 2020), Latin American cities (Guibrinet, Sanzana Calvet, & Castán Broto, 2017), French cities (Bahers, Barles, & Durand, 2019), Spanish cities (González-García & Dias, 2019), and Danish cities (Lanau, Mao, & Liu, 2021).

The notion of urban metabolism is loosely based on an analogy with the metabolism of organisms, and cities are treated as organisms with the equivalent of metabolic processes

that exchange materials and energy with their surrounding environment to function and grow, and in turn produce waste that must be efficiently managed (C. Kennedy, Pincetl, & Bunje, 2011). In practice, analyzing urban metabolism involves quantification of the interactions (flows) of energy, water, nutrients, materials, and wastes in an urban region (X. Zhang & Li, 2018). Although in many UM studies cities mimic giant organisms with an exchange of resources analogous to natural organisms, the complexity of urban environments and the fact that cities are home to a multitude of organisms, humans, animals, and vegetation supports the notion of the cities as ecosystems that should be analyzed as such (Golubiewski, 2012).

Understanding and quantifying the natural and human availability of resources and their circulation within the urban system can provide valuable insights into the system's sustainability and the environmental impacts caused by cities. UM can address the complex dynamics of contemporary urban areas while considering the social processes that shape them and the population growth factor (John, Luederitz, Lang, & von Wehrden, 2019; Maranghi et al., 2020). In that sense, UM analysis can support urban planners and designers to create effective policies to tackle environmental challenges and the socio-economic problems related to them. Building upon those advancements, researchers have started to use the urban metabolism concept to identify sustainable urban solutions and evaluate the impacts of implementing sustainable urban policies (Chrysoulakis et al., 2013; Davoudi & Sturzaker, 2017), assist the transition to smart cities (Bibri & Krogstie, 2020) and effectively manage urban energy systems (Rosales Carreón & Worrell, 2018) as well as support ecosystem services (Elliot, Almenar, Niza, Proença, & Rugani, 2019; Perrotti & Stremke, 2020).

The metabolism of most contemporary urban areas is predominantly linear, characterized by input of natural resources and outputs of waste and emissions. It is consequently studied and expressed by the traditional linear extract-produce-use-dispose models (Cui, Wang, & Feng, 2019; C. Kennedy et al., 2011). Integrating circularity in urban metabolism could drive the transition from linear to circular urban metabolism and address social and environmental challenges in urban areas (D'Amico, Arbolino, Shi, Yigitcanlar, & Ioppolo, 2022; Tan, Arbabi, Densley Tingley, Brockway, & Mayfield, 2021). Using this approach, the city can be treated as an ecosystem in which the circularity of natural ecosystems should be restored (Feiferytė-Skirienė & Stasiškienė, 2021), for example by means of nature-based solutions.

Closely linked to circularity in urban metabolism is the Circular Economy model (CE), which is currently acknowledged as a promising pathway to achieve sustainable urban development (C. W. Chen, 2021; Corona, Shen, Reike, Rosales Carreón, & Worrell, 2019; European Commission, 2020). The CE model promotes sustainability through the reduction and recirculation of natural resources. It promises to reduce primary resource use, waste, and emissions by introducing closed material cycles that assist in retaining the value of products and materials in the economy for as long as possible (Haas, Krausmann, Wiedenhofer, Lauk, & Mayer, 2020). The economic model that CE represents aims to

overcome the traditional take-make-dispose linear pattern of production and consumption of goods and services by following closed loops in which waste is minimized and more resources could be reused and recycled. Circularity is used to transform the linear economy and ultimately lead to the creation of green jobs and stimulate economic growth while mitigating pressures on the environment (Korhonen, Honkasalo, & Seppälä, 2018; Webster, 2017).

Despite the increasing interest in the CE and the fact that its theoretical foundations are not new, CE is considered an umbrella concept incorporating different meanings and therefore is interpreted differently by different stakeholders depending on their needs and goals (Hartley, van Santen, & Kirchherr, 2020; Kirchherr, Reike, & Hekkert, 2017; Mayer et al., 2019). The analysis of 114 CE-related definitions by Kirchherr *et al.*, (2017) provides quantitative evidence of the CE heterogeneity of definitions and supports the presumption that it could mean different things to different actors. In addition, different CE principles have been proposed in the literature, including the widely used R-principles. There is a range of so-called R-principles, starting with 3Rs (reduce, reuse recycle) through 5Rs (...rethink, refuse) to 10Rs (...recover, recycling, repurpose, remanufacture, refurbish, repair), or other principles associated to some extent with the R-frameworks. Different authors assign different attributes and meanings in their conceptualizations of these principles (Papageorgiou et al., 2021). But, although this spectrum of CE principles is interpreted and implemented differently by various actors, using policies based on CE could aid modern cities to reform conventional waste and by-product utilization and recycling. The CE approach extends traditional recycling and promotes product, component, and material reuse, remanufacturing, refurbishment, repair, cascading, and upgrading (Korhonen et al., 2018). The CE model is currently considered a suitable path to increase the sustainability of the economic system (Elia, Gnoni, & Tornese, 2017).

Furthermore, the inclusion of CE practices in urban planning can function as a “toolbox” for achieving a sizeable number of SD targets (Saidani, Yannou, Leroy, Cluzel, & Kendall, 2019). The transition towards a more circular economy can contribute to several sustainable development goals (SDGs), most prominently to SDG 12, sustainable production and consumption patterns (European Commission, 2015). Despite practical issues in its functionality, integrating CE in UM can assist in addressing several urban sustainability issues, and drive the transition from linear to circular urban metabolism (L. Dong, Liu, & Bian, 2021). Recognizing this potential, local authorities and urban planners are using the CE principles in developing policies and strategies to move toward a more circular urban development model (Rehman, Reda, Paiho, & Hasan, 2019; Vanhuyse, Haddaway, & Henrysson, 2021).

3.1.3 Circular urban metabolism

Both CE and UM recognize and emphasize the need to include circularity in the pursuit of sustainable development in the cities, but neither approach is sufficient and effective enough when applied separately. UM understanding and application in a circular perspective is fundamental to developing sustainable cities and communities based on material and energy flow analysis within the city and the surrounding areas. But for a circular metabolism approach to achieve sustainability within the urban space, it must be supported by an economic system that favors new business models, technological innovation, and effective land use (D'amico, Arbolino, Shi, Yigitcanlar, & Ioppolo, 2021). UM and CE can therefore benefit from each other. Both concepts can be adopted simultaneously and will mutually complement one another.

A concept that marries the two approaches, combining the R circularity principles with the UM vision of the sustainable urban ecosystem, is the **circular urban metabolism (CUM)**. The idea for a circular urban metabolism was first introduced by Herbert Girardet who suggested that cities need to adopt circular metabolic processes, where outputs of the system are also inputs to it (Girardet, 2000). Essentially, CUM can be considered as analogous to the cradle-to-cradle approach of life cycle analysis transferred to the study of urban metabolic processes (Broto, Allen, & Rapoport, 2012). Under the CUM approach, UM can be used to describe efficiently material, waste and energy flows and the integration of CE principles can provide the rules for efficient changes towards circularity (Cui, 2022). By bringing the CUM concept into urban planning, policymakers and designers can rethink and redesign urban flows in a circular way, including the reduction, reuse, and recovery of resources (Lucertini & Musco, 2020).

The application of CUM can be crucial in understanding the interactions and dependencies between the cities and the hinterlands, and in this way setting the ground to design resilient and sustainable energy and material flows. A comprehensive CUM design can be a valuable tool to improve the resource use pattern (Wang, Zhang, Zhang, Fu, & Zhang, 2021) and initiate substantial transformations in design, production, consumption, use, waste, and reuse practices. Complex processes within urban systems could be simplified to promote the vision of sustainable cities (Sánchez Levoso et al., 2020). From that perspective, CUM offers a better way to explore and develop cyclical and restorative models for the city (Cui, 2022).

In recent years, CUM has been increasingly gaining recognition as a methodology to mitigate resource depletion and minimize waste generation. But like the CE concept, more exploration is required along with actual application on urban systems, and activation of NbS in particular. CUM has been formulated by merging the basic principles of circularity and UM, and as a result, the created concept embodies many of the associated limitations and weaknesses. The CUM concept is still in its infancy and requires further analysis and development at its core (Cui, 2022).

But despite difficulties in field application and existing research gaps, CUM has the potential to unite separate scientific fields under a broader umbrella towards the desired goal to provide urban areas with alternatives to change their production and consumption modes. The transition to circularity can aid cities strengthen their infrastructure (Gravagnuolo, Angrisano, & Girard, 2019), including their green infrastructure (Perrotti & Stremke, 2020). Therefore, by incorporating the CUM principles in urban planning and design cities can become more resilient (Kalmykova, Sadagopan, & Rosado, 2018). From this point of view, CUM suggests a better way to explore cyclical and restorative models. In total, CUM has the potential to strengthen relations between the urban core and neighboring regions, redefine land and infrastructure use, and update urban policies to respond to the challenges of climate change (Lucertini & Musco, 2020; van Broekhoven & Vernay, 2018).

3.1.4 Nexus between (circular) urban metabolism and socioecological justice

Primarily, urban metabolism refers to the flow of materials, energy, and resources within a city, encompassing processes such as resource extraction, consumption, waste generation, and emissions. In addition, the literature discusses far-reaching aspects and expressions of urban metabolism, relating to power relations and their expression in urban flows, as well as expansion of the concept to include political ecology insights and the social, economic, technological transformations that take place in urban environments (Broto et al., 2012; C. Kennedy et al., 2011; Pincetl, Bunje, & Holmes, 2012). Simultaneously, ecological justice focuses on the fair distribution of environmental resources and benefits, and the prevention of disproportionate environmental ills among different social, human and non-human population groups. However, the distribution of environmental resources and benefits is only the tip of the iceberg, being an expression of underlying processes relating to dimensions of recognition and procedural justice (Zuniga-Teran, Gerlak, Elder, & Tam, 2021).

The intersection of urban metabolism and ecological justice reveals a nexus between the functioning of urban systems, the resulting ecological conditions, and the equitable distribution of benefits and burdens among diverse communities – human and non-human – as well as between the power relations and decision-making processes that lead to manifestation of certain urban metabolism patterns and associated ecological space injustices. This nexus, although notable, is rarely addressed in the existing literature on sustainable urban metabolism (John et al., 2019). It is however a significant one, especially when considering the power imbalances between human and non-human populations in cities. The intersection of sustainable (circular) urban metabolism and ecological justice reframes the human–nature relationship into a mutually supportive and beneficial one, as opposed to viewing the city primarily as a human ecosystem benefiting from nature (Broto et al., 2012; Welden et al., 2021).

Six perspectives from which urban metabolism can be studied, namely 1. *the city as an ecosystem*, 2. *material and energy flows within the city*, 3. *economic–material relations*

within the city, 4. economic drivers of rural–urban relationships, 5. the reproduction of urban inequality, and 6. re-signifying the city through new visions of socioecological relationships, have been introduced by (Broto et al., 2012). The authors highlight that urban metabolism flows and distributional justice are the result of governance models, socio-economic and political drivers. They thus emphasize the importance of collaboration among diverse fields, such as urban planning, ecology, sociology, and engineering, to comprehensively address the challenges posed by urbanization. This interdisciplinary approach is essential for understanding how urban systems function holistically and how their functioning intersects with societal equity and ecological justice concerns.

The practical applications of studying urban metabolism for urban planning and design are discussed by (C. Kennedy et al., 2011). Integration of urban metabolism considerations in urban planning is essential to ensure that the dynamics of material and energy flows are not only efficient but also justly distributed. By analyzing inflow, consumption, and outflow of resources within a city, urban planners and designers obtain a comprehensive view of urban resource utilization, waste generation, and energy consumption, and can consequently identify areas of inefficiency and environmental impact, which are crucial for promoting both sustainability and ecological justice. This analysis requires a suite of indicators that cover social, health and economic impacts. Among the most indicators those for energy, water, material, and waste flows, as well as quality of life (spatial, biophysical, economic, management of and access to utilities), all of which are recognized to influence certain flows and define the urban metabolism (Chris Kennedy, Stewart, Ibrahim, Facchini, & Mele, 2014).

Similarly, Pincetl *et al.* (2012) propose an expanded urban metabolism approach that recognizes that energy consumption patterns in cities are intertwined with social, economic, and technological factors. Effectively, this approach requires a scale adaptation of the urban metabolism study from the whole city scale that uses aggregated data to zoom into specific localities, thus more clearly identifying “*who-is using-what-flows-where-to do-what*”. Here, the aspect of time, evaluating and addressing temporal injustices, could be added. By identifying the causes of disparities, urban planners can design targeted interventions that address both environmental and social challenges. When considering planning of NbS interventions from the aspect of ecological justice, this approach has already been adopted in JUSTNature with the development of the socio-ecological profiles maps (Zambelli et al., 2022).

Consequently, there is a need for a holistic view of urban systems that merges urban metabolism studies with justice considerations (John et al., 2019). This will be achieved not least by bringing into the urban metabolism assessment social, health and economic aspects, demographic data and understanding of the actors and policies influencing the metabolism of societies (Broto et al., 2012; John et al., 2019; C. Kennedy et al., 2011; Pincetl et al., 2012). By integrating urban metabolism assessment and socioecological justice perspectives, the intricate interactions between urban processes, social dynamics, and

environmental quality can be unveiled and more easily understood. With this knowledge, urban planners can create sustainable and inclusive urban environments where the benefits and costs of urban development are shared equitably among all residents. Naturally, this sustainable and inclusive urban planning can entail the planning and implementation of nature-based solutions.

3.1.5 NbS role in (circular) urban metabolism

Nature-based solutions are at the forefront of urban sustainability discourse due to their manifold potential in tackling urban challenges. By nature, NbS bear cyclical functions, thus supporting circularity in cities and consequently balancing their metabolism. This can be achieved on multiple levels, from green building materials to green building systems and green building sites (Pearlmutter et al., 2020).

In transitioning from linear urban metabolism where materials and energy accumulate in urban environments (C. Kennedy et al., 2011), to circular urban metabolism where materials and energy flow in closed loops, NbS can be viewed as an indispensable tool (Atanasova et al., 2021). Nature-based solutions model nature-inspired lessons to city planning and design and by introducing NbS in the urban environments the cycles of nature and natural ecosystems are brought into the city. These functions of the NbS relate to two ways of addressing urban metabolism in the cities, as brought forward by Broto *et al.* (2012), namely “*the city as an ecosystem*” and “*material and energy flows in the city*”.

The first, although challenging due to the complicated nature of urban ecosystems, is treating natural ecosystem functions as an example of urban planning. The second is accounting for material and energy flows using the material flow analysis approach, drawing from the industrial ecology example (Broto et al., 2012). Material flow analysis enables the quantification of nutrients, waste, and pollutants that flow within the urban system, either absorbed by it or stocked within it. Such quantification allows the detection of input sources, outflow streams, and potential sinks for consequent planning of closing the loops and balancing the metabolism. Implementing NbS interventions such as improving soil permeability, with potential to regulate water and carbon cycles (Y. Zhang, 2013) can efficiently support the transition to a closed-loop urban system.

As found by (Babí Almenar et al., 2021) among 374 case studies that addressed urban challenges and NbS ecosystem services, representing 3 continents (Europe, America, and Asia), four climate types, and three gross national income classes, the challenge of “*green and circular economy*” was the only challenge to be mentioned in at least 50% of the cases. This observation highlights the prominence of the circular economy challenge, and by extension of circular processes overall, across a multitude of urban environments. The “*green and circular economy*” challenge along with other frequently reported challenges of “*water management*”, “*material and solid waste management*”, that also relate to circularity of urban flows, can be tackled through the ecosystem services offered by the implementation of NbS.

The NbS contribution to circularity in cities is enhanced by their multi-functionality, tackling multiple challenges and offering multiple ecosystem services simultaneously (Calheiros & Stefanakis, 2021; Somarakis, Stagakis, & Chrysoulakis, 2019). As a result, NbS contribute to closing loops in water management, offering food from edible green walls and edible green roofs, balancing energy demand, closing nutrient loops, and supporting biodiversity in cities (Atanasova et al., 2021; Calheiros & Stefanakis, 2021; Pearlmutter et al., 2020; Tsatsou, Frantzeskaki, & Malamis, 2023). In view of the transition to low-carbon and high air quality cities, NbS close the loops by capturing CO₂ (Keith et al., 2021) and particulate matter (PM) (Diener & Mudu, 2021), although the sequestration potential varies depending on vegetation type and size, as well as other site-specific factors (Diener & Mudu, 2021; Grzędzicka, 2019).

The multiple benefits of NbS expand on challenges of social justice and cohesion, health and well-being, participatory planning and governance, knowledge and social capacity building for sustainable urban transformation, and place regeneration (European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2021). Addressing these challenges requires studying urban metabolism from the viewpoint of *“reproduction of urban inequality”* and *“resignifying the city through new visions of socioecological relationships”* (Broto et al., 2012).

It is needed to plan, implement, and evaluate NbS interventions from a socioecological justice perspective, addressing all three principles of procedural, recognition and distributional justice (Biernacka, Kronenberg, & Łaszkiwicz, 2020; Dumitru, Frantzeskaki, & Collier, 2020; Pineda-Pinto, Frantzeskaki, & Nygaard, 2022; Zuniga-Teran et al., 2021). This approach is essential for equitably tackling urban challenges. Likewise, bringing the ecological justice perspective in the NbS planning and implementation converges with the proposals for an expanded urban metabolism concept integrated with justice considerations, eventually contributing to the design of sustainable and inclusive cities.

3.2 Definition of the Ecological Justice – Circularity indicator framework for Low-carbon | High air quality NbS

The previous sections have highlighted a few noteworthy links among the urban sustainability pursuit, the circular urban metabolism concept, the ecological justice, and the role of NbS (Figure 1). These can be summarized as follows:

1. Aiming for circularity in urban processes opens a pathway to sustainable urban development and sustainability, not least by reducing the cities' dependence on imported resources, mitigating the environmental impact of accumulating waste and pollution, and ensuring longevity and livability of the urban systems.
2. Simultaneously there exists a profound nexus between urban metabolism and ecological justice, where urban metabolism flows are formed from similar power relations that influence recognition, procedural and distributional justice in cities. The

urban metabolism assessment can contribute to revealing injustices and the design of circular urban metabolism can in turn alleviate injustices.

3. Designing for circular urban metabolism, NbS can contribute first by modelling and inspiring circular flows as well as by bringing circular flows in cities. Besides, NbS are widely accepted for their manifold potential in addressing urban societal challenges.
4. Already underlined in the Deliverable 2.1, ecological justice in cities can be accomplished through just planning and implementation of NbS infrastructure, governed by procedural and recognition justice and resulting in fair distribution of ecological goods. Necessarily, the NbS evaluation framework would need to evolve by integrating the justice perspective in the analysis, effectively capturing and revealing socio-ecological injustices in distribution of NbS impacts and benefits.

Figure 1: Links among sustainable development, circular urban metabolism, ecological justice and NbS

NbS bear an undeniable potential towards supporting a just transition to sustainable, circular urban environments (Figure 1). Despite the clear links that can be tracked in literature between NbS implementation and realization of circularity in cities, current EU plans and initiatives overlook this connection. More generally, assessments of NbS typically lack the circularity perspective (Atanasova et al., 2021).

Consequently, there appears a need for a comprehensive NbS evaluation framework that shall help decision-makers design and implement NbS at the city level and then effectively monitor and evaluate the performance and impact of NbS interventions, as well as the progress toward CUM and urban sustainability while assuring that the outcomes will equally affect all human and non-human groups. The use of this framework should provide useful information on how a city is performing in different areas, facilitate transparency, and support investments in the green economy.

JUSTNature proposes the development of an Ecological Justice – Circularity indicator framework for Low-carbon | High air quality NbS that will provide NbS performance evaluation and simultaneous assessment of just transition to sustainable and resilient cities.

Therefore, within JUSTNature, the framework of indicators is defined as a **system of indicators to holistically monitor and evaluate the performance and impacts of Low Carbon| High air quality NbS** interventions at neighborhood/city scale, **synthesizing previously identified NbS indicators** while **combining the principles of (i) sustainability, (ii) circularity, and (iii) justice.**

To this end, state-of-the-art indicators for NbS evaluation have been collected and assigned to the 6 thematic areas of justice, as defined in JUSTNature. Subsequently, a set of criteria has been applied to the indicators for assessing their potential to measure ecological justice as well as progress relevant to CUM and SDGs. The details of the Ecological Justice – Circularity indicator framework development for Low-carbon | High air quality NbS, are given in section 4.

To the best of the authors' knowledge this is the first NbS evaluation Framework to combine the 3 principles.

4 DEVELOPMENT OF THE ECOLOGICAL JUSTICE – CIRCULARITY INDICATOR FRAMEWORK

4.1 State of the art indicators for Low-carbon | High air quality NbS functions and services

The point of departure for developing the indicator framework for Low-carbon | High air quality NbS functions and services was the handbook "Evaluating the Impact of Nature-based Solutions: A Handbook for Practitioners". The handbook is considered to be an authoritative source of state-of-the-art NbS indicators, resulting from the combined experience of several previous H2020 funded projects relating to NbS (European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2021).

While creating the list of indicators used in the present project, two additional requirements were considered:

- i. The 6 areas of justice and baskets of indicators that resulted from Task 2.1 and described in the JUSTNature Deliverable 2.1 (Gantioler et al., 2023)
- ii. The expected impact and added impacts of the project and the associated indicators to these impacts, as described in the Grant Agreement (GA).

The handbook categorizes the indicators according to 12 societal challenges. This taxonomy was differentiated to meet the objectives of JUSTNature, recognizing that the NbS activation must be performed in direct relation to ecological justice. Therefore, 6 areas of injustice were identified, which are described in detail in D2.1. The indicators of the handbook were assigned to the JUSTNature thematic areas of injustices: air-quality, thermal, carbon, spatial, flora-fauna-habitat, temporal.

In compiling the list, a judgement selection¹ was made whereby the recommended indicators from the handbook were prioritized and distributed across the thematic areas. Thereafter, indicators that were designated by the handbook as 'additional' were selected and distributed. The indicators from the handbook that do not relate to the 6 thematic areas and the project's focus on Low-carbon | High air quality were left out. As part of D2.1, a basket (list) of indicators had also been identified for each thematic area. The baskets from D2.1 were compared with the indicators' lists derived by the handbook so that the final selection contains all indicators associated to each injustice area, both by the handbook and D2.1.

Next, considering the JUSTNature expected and added impacts that are described in the GA, it was ensured that the indicators to measure/evaluate those impacts are included in

¹"Judgement selection": this is based on TUC team's experience from VARCITIES project.

the lists of the 6 thematic areas or otherwise added. Through this process, the indicators from the GA that did not match any of the 6 thematic areas were allocated to two additional groups: the Social Justice & Cohesion group and the Economy & Employment group. The participatory planning and governance indicators are all left out because these are part of Task 7.1.2 where a separate list of indicators for co-governance evaluation is created.

The indicators are organized in a spreadsheet database (Appendix II). The database is divided into sections corresponding to the 8 groups of indicators (6 areas of injustices + Social Justice & Cohesion and Economy & Employment groups of indicators). The database is an expansion of the work performed in D2.1. It includes information regarding in which stage of the NbS implementation the indicators are applicable, the scale applicability, details about the calculation methodologies, tools and required data, and pros and cons for their use. As a result, a complete picture of the possible ways that an indicator can be used for measuring the potential functions and services of Low carbon | High air quality NbS is clearly and easily depicted. In addition, for each CiPeL, the indicators that have been pre-selected in the GA are marked, and when a specific target has been set in the GA, this value is inserted.

The matrices in the spreadsheet that form the indicators' database are presented in Table 1, along with a filled example in Table 2.

This spreadsheet was used as the basis for further developing the indicator framework as follows:

1. The CiPeL partners used these lists in two consecutive steps for selecting the indicators relevant to the CiPeL challenges and the planned interventions, thus creating the CiPeL tailored indicator framework (details in section 5.1).
2. A set of criteria was determined for assessing the created frameworks regarding their applicability, relevance to CUM, connection to Ecological Justice (EJ) and alignment to specific SDGs (details in section 4.2.20).
3. A set of criteria was determined for evaluating (scoring) the indicators. The criteria for scoring the indicators link to the framework criteria (details in section 4.2.1).

Table 1: Matrix template for creating the database of indicators for Low carbon | High air quality NbS.

No	Indicator	Units	SOURCE	JUSTICE INDICATOR	JUSTICE TYPE	Synergies with other indicators/challenges	EVALUATION STAGE		SCALE APPLICABILITY						INDICATOR PROS & CONS		proposed method of indicator measurement/calculation	source and type of data	sensor based (yes/no/partially)	data collection frequency	data protection	CiPeL						
							pre-NbS	post-NbS	SPATIAL SCALE			TEMPORAL SCALE			PROS	CONS						Bolz	Mer	Ch	Gz	Leuv	Mun	Szom
									site	district	city	short	medium	long														
x.x	NbS indicator	Unit of measurement	Source of indicator, the majority come from the NbS evaluation Handbook, clarification whether it is recommended, or additional indicator is given	Adjustments to the NbS indicator into an ecological justice indicator	distributional /recognition /process	Dependence from other indicators, Contribution to other indicators	indicator can be measured for pre-NbS evaluation	indicator can be measured for post-NbS evaluation	building/street/NbS	neighborhood/residential area	city	measurement and results in a few days to few months	measurement and results 1-2 years		Pros of using this indicator, or method for indicator measurement (as given in the NbS evaluation Handbook from the experience of previous H2020 NbS projects)	Cons of using this indicator, or method for indicator measurement (as given in the NbS evaluation Handbook from the experience of previous H2020 NbS projects)	proposed method from experience of previous projects or literature, not binding to be followed, this column is indented for information (e.g. in later stages of the project when ApPs and CiPels are planning for the indicator measurement/calculation)	resulting from methods and tools as well as evaluation purposes, intended for information (e.g. in later stages of the project when ApPs and CiPels are planning for the indicator measurement/calculation)	indicators that can be measured by monitoring equipment, except for remote sensors i.e. satellite, aerial (links to T3.2)	might determine temporal scale of indicator	information needed for ethics planning	Checking which CiPeLs have selected the indicator from the GA stage (by inserting the target set in the GA or marking with x when no specific target has been set yet)						

Legend:
 Yellow background Indicator also identified in 2.1, or in agreement with D2.1
 Green Font Indicator set in the GA
 Pink background Groups indicators that are same or similar; numbering for these is x.x.x

Table 2: Filled example – part of the indicator database.

No	Indicator	Units	SOURCE	JUSTICE INDICATOR	JUSTICE TYPE	Synergies with other indicators	EVALUATION STAGE		SCALE APPLICABILITY						INDICATOR PROS & CONS		proposed method of indicator measurement/calculation	source and type of data	sensor based (yes/no/partially)	data collection frequency	data protection	CiPeL						
							pre-NbS	post-NbS	SPATIAL SCALE			TEMPORAL SCALE			PROS	CONS						Bolz	Mer	Ch	Gz	Leuv	Mun	Szomb
									site	district	city	short	medium	long														
1.4.1	Removal of atmospheric pollutants by vegetation (leaves, stems and roots) [In GA: Reduced pollution fluxes per area & share of emissions captured (by vegetation/area/socio-economic unit)]	kg/ha/day	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for air quality	demographic data: population groups around NbS	distributional										This method does not require field work.	Modelled method and specific software are required	Calculation formulas given in: https://op.europa.eu/s/o9b8	Atmospheric pollutant concentration data from monitoring stations and tree cover data from (municipal) maps and models.	no	annually	n/a	x	x		reduction of more than 10% in pedestrian zones thanks to green barriers			

4.2 Selection of criteria for the framework development

The development of the Ecological Justice – Circularity indicator framework was based on a set of criteria that characterize it in relation to its potential to measure progress towards CUM, EJ and the sustainable development goals. The combination of the three principles – sustainability, circularity, justice – in forming the framework constitutes the originality of this work and thus these criteria were considered indispensable to its characterization. Stemming from the concept definition of the framework, the criteria for the three principles are thereby mentioned as “concept criteria”.

Moreover, certain criteria need to apply to the indicators when defining the framework as a system of indicators (Papageorgiou et al., 2021). Two sets of criteria have consequently been defined, one for scoring the indicators and another for the framework evaluation.

4.2.1 Criteria for indicators

A list of technical criteria is essential for the indicators’ assessment to provide a complete picture of their functionality. The technical criteria characterize the indicators regarding their computation methodology, data requirements, and ease of use. In addition, given the framework definition, the concept criteria apply to the indicators that compose the framework, therefore the indicators should be also assessed for their potential to measure progress towards CUM, EJ and the sustainable development goals.

The selection of criteria for the indicators was based on:

- the so-called RACER criteria (Relevant, Acceptable, Credible, Easy, Robust), as technical criteria,
- a literature review on properties that indicators that measure circularity should have, especially regarding their ability to measure fundamental CUM principles.
- the JUSTNature scope, for the ecological justice criterion,
- the alignment with specific SDGs related to JUSTNature objectives.

Established by the European Commission, the RACER criteria have been widely adopted for assessing indicators that measure progress towards the circular economy (European Commission, 2023). Similarly in literature, the RACER criteria have been adopted for constructing a framework of resource efficiency indicators linked with socio-economic and ecosystem functions (Eisenmenger *et al.*, 2016). The Horizon2020 project NATURE4CITIES has also implemented a RACER evaluation for developing a framework of urban performance indicators (Green4Cities, 2017).

The literature also frequently references the SMART criteria, which stand for specific, measurable, agreed, realistic, and time dependent. These are most often used for defining a project’s objectives (Martinelli, Battisti, & Matzarakis, 2015) but have been also

used in developing the indicators that are included in the NbS evaluation Handbook (European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2021).

The studies by Papageorgiou *et al.* (2021) and Kennedy, Pincetl, & Bunje (2011) were also considered for establishing the indicators' criteria. Papageorgiou *et al.* (2021), assessing the potential of indicator frameworks to measure progress toward circular economy at the city level, used 8 criteria, that reflect attributes of the indicators as follows: 1. Transparency, 2. (developed through) Stakeholder engagement, 3. Effective communication of information, 4. Ability to track temporal changes, 5. Applicability, 6. Alignment with CE principles 7. Valid for the evaluation objective 8. Relevance to sustainable development.

Kennedy, Pincetl, & Bunje (2011) discussed applications of UM in urban planning and design. Since the analysis of urban metabolism complements the assessment of urban sustainability, they proposed that similarly to good sustainability indicators, the indicators that measure urban metabolism are expected to be 1. Scientifically valid, 2. Representative, 3. Responsive, 4. Relevant to urban planners and dwellers, 5. Based on data that is comparable over time, 6. Understandable, 7. Unambiguous (C. Kennedy et al., 2011),

The criteria proposed by Papageorgiou *et al.* (2021) and Kennedy, Pincetl, & Bunje (2011), present commonalities with the RACER criteria. Therefore, the final list of technical criteria has resulted by combining the criteria proposed by Papageorgiou *et al.* (2021) and Kennedy, Pincetl, & Bunje (2011), also using the approaches of Eisenmenger *et al.*, (2016) and NATURE4CITIES (Green4Cities, 2017) in sub-dividing the RACER criteria. Consequently, the technical criteria have been organized in a set of 4 basic criteria and 9 sub-criteria (Table 3).

Table 3: List of technical criteria applied for scoring the indicators.

Criterion	Sub-criteria	Description
Relevance	-	How/if the indicator is related to measuring progress/impacts of the intervention. The aim is to keep the selection relevant to the objectives and interventions as well as consider the resources (time/ knowledge/ budget) of each CiPeL. Looking into which data is already available and what data needs to be collected linked to the indicator's relevance.
Credibility	Transparency	The indicator has a clear methodology; the methods, tools, standards to be used and the data needed are well defined.
	Unambiguous results	The indicator is not open to interpretation (i.e., cannot be interpreted in more than one way)
Ease	Availability of data to calculate the indicator	The methodology requires inputs of data that are easily accessible through open databases. Data can be easily obtained if surveys/questionnaires are part of the methodology. Data can be collected through a developed (existing) sensors' network.
	Technical feasibility	The indicator can be calculated using standard software. No special programs, equipment and/or expertise is required.

	Reproducibility	It is possible to apply the indicator in other cases (or easily repeat it in the same case), serving comparability among cases (or in the same case through time).
	Cost effective	Evaluation of the cost implications of using the indicator: The data can be collected, and the indicator applied at a reasonable cost.
	Understandable	The indicator is meaningful to the non-experts and the public. The results are easily understood by non-experts and the public.
Ability to track temporal changes	Ability to track temporal changes	The indicator can track temporal changes based on data that is comparable over time. Data for calculating the indicator is expected to be available in the future.
	Temporal Sensitivity	The indicator can track and quickly respond to rapid changes over time.

Regarding the potential of indicators to measure progress towards CUM, the criterion of validity, as described by Papageorgiou *et al.* (2021), was adapted to this work's purposes. Intended for evaluation of a CE framework, the validity criterion was linked to 12 validity requirements and the analysis measured the extent to which these were covered by the inclusion of relevant indicators (Papageorgiou *et al.*, 2021). In the present work, the same approach for scoring the NbS indicators was applied. The criterion **relevance to circular urban metabolism** has been defined, distinguishing **6 CUM requirements relevant to the Low-carbon | High air quality NbS implementation** (Table 4). For each indicator, it was examined whether it can directly or indirectly link to the 6 CUM requirements.

Table 4: List of criteria applied for scoring the indicators on their relevance to CUM

RELEVANCE TO CIRCULAR URBAN METABOLISM					
Link to emission levels (pollutants and GHG emissions)	Link to utility and durability of public and open spaces	Link to investing on green economy	Link to creation and distribution of added value and other outcomes of economic performance	Link to social wellbeing and health	Link to raising awareness on Biodiversity and FFH

Pursuant to JUSTNature's focus, the **relevance to ecological justice criterion** is a prerequisite and is defined as the **potential of the indicator to capture and reveal socio-ecological injustices by measuring spatial and/or socio-economic distribution or the results**. Finally, the **relevance of indicators to the SDGs** was defined as the **potential of the indicator to be linked to progress of specific SDGs**. Suggestions for such links are highlighted in the handbook for Evaluating the Impact of Nature-based Solutions (European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2021), and have been used as references during the scoring process.

The scoring of the indicators resulted from a collaborative process and reflects the interdisciplinary background of the JUSTNature partners. Particularly for the relevance

criterion, this is assessed from the CiPeL side, and it supports the indicator selection relevant to the intervention and the CiPeL's objectives.

For each of the indicator criteria the scores were given as follows:

- Technical criteria: 0=no; 1=partially/difficult; 2=yes
- Concept criteria:
 - CUM relevance: 0=no; 1 yes, indirectly; 2=yes, directly
 - Ecological justice criterion: 0=no; 1=has the potential; 2=yes
 - SDG relevance: this is an on/off criterion, 0=no; 2=yes

4.2.2 Framework Criteria

The transition from the indicator criteria to the framework criteria is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Linking the indicator criteria to the framework criteria.

Transitioning from the indicator criteria to the framework criteria, two groups of criteria were finally formed for characterizing the framework (Table 5); in addition to the concept criteria, which are inherent to the framework definition, a group of technical criteria for the framework were derived from the indicators' technical criteria.

Each of the framework criteria expresses qualities of the framework. These also receive a score, resulting from the scores of the indicators that comprise the framework. Effectively, the framework's score for each of the criteria/qualities, results from inclusion of relevant indicators, as explained in Table 5.

Table 5: List of Framework criteria

Framework criteria		Explanation
TECHNICAL	Credibility	The framework is composed of credible indicators with transparent methodology and unambiguous interpretation
	Applicability	The application of the framework is based on applicable indicators. The required data are easily accessible at no/low cost.
	Ability to track temporal changes	The framework is composed of indicators that track changes and determine the degree to which goals are achieved over time.
CONCEPT	CUM Validity	The Framework includes indicators relevant to CUM aspects
	Relevance to sustainable development	The Framework includes indicators relevant to specific SDGs
	Ecological Justice	The Framework includes indicators that can measure ecological justice

4.3 Creating the framework

4.3.1 Creation of the indicator framework

The creation of the indicator framework entails an iterative step-by-step approach that is summarized in Figure 3.

In step 1, the project team identifies the challenges to be addressed and defines the project's objectives for overcoming these challenges. Concluding the 1st step, indicators suited to measure progress towards the objectives are selected, thus forming the first version of the indicator framework.

The second step entails refinement of the indicator selection in accordance with the refinement of the pilot's challenges and objectives through a series of participatory workshops with local stakeholders. The participatory workshops (organized in WP4) serve to clarify the objectives as well as the NbS interventions. The results of the workshops assist in further refining the indicator selection based on concrete objectives and planned interventions. In the end of the second step, the tailored indicator framework has been formed.

Figure 3: Stepwise approach for the creation of the indicator framework

Further revision steps can take place, if needed. These can serve to update the composition of the framework, for example by adding indicators especially with the aim of strengthening the score of the framework in relation to certain criteria. Other revision steps can take place periodically, especially linked to revision of the project's objectives.

The detailed description of the steps' implementation for creating the tailored indicator framework of the JUSTNature CiPeLs, is given in section 5.1.

4.3.2 Scoring the qualities of the indicator framework

Following the aforementioned stepwise approach, the framework is created by selecting indicators relevant to the project/intervention (i.e., criterion relevance). The indicators that comprise the framework bring their attributes into the framework and ultimately, the framework is characterized by the set of indicators that comprise it. The attributes of the indicators are essentially expressed through the scores that the indicators have received for each of the indicator criteria. The scores are used as inputs for calculating the qualities of the framework. Therefore, different compositions of indicators form frameworks with different qualities.

According to the criteria that have been defined for the framework (section 4.2.2), it is expected that the framework will have the following qualities: credibility, applicability, ability to track temporal changes, CUM validity, relevance to sustainable development, ecological justice. The score for each of these qualities is calculated as follows (Equation 1 to Equation 5).

Equation 1:

$$\text{Framework credibility} = \mu \left(\sum_{i=1}^n ti + \sum_{i=1}^n ui \right) \div n$$

Where:

t= indicator transparency score, $0 \leq t \leq 2$

u= indicator unambiguous score, $0 \leq u \leq 2$

n = the number of indicators

The credibility of the framework can thus take on values that range from 0 and 2. A value closer to 2 indicates that the framework is composed of credible indicators with transparent methodology and unambiguous interpretation.

Equation 2:

$$\text{Framework applicability} = \mu \left(\sum_{i=1}^n ai + \sum_{i=1}^n fi + \sum_{i=1}^n ci + \sum_{i=1}^n ri + \sum_{i=1}^n udi \right) \div n$$

Where:

a= indicator availability of data score, $0 \leq a \leq 2$

f= indicator technical feasibility score, $0 \leq f \leq 2$

c= indicator cost effectiveness score, $0 \leq c \leq 2$

r= indicator reproducibility score, $0 \leq r \leq 2$

ud= indicator understandable score, $0 \leq ud \leq 2$

n = the number of indicators

As with the framework credibility, the framework applicability can take on values from 0 and 2. A value closer to 2 indicates that the framework is composed of applicable indicators that can be easily reproduced and understood.

Equation 3:

$$\text{Framework ability to track temporal changes} = \mu \left(\sum_{i=1}^n tci + \sum_{i=1}^n tsi \right) \div n$$

Where:

tc= indicator ability to track temporal changes score, $0 \leq tc \leq 2$

ts= indicator temporal sensitivity score, $0 \leq ts \leq 2$

n = the number of indicators

The framework's ability to track temporal changes also takes on values in the range from 0 to 2.

Equation 4:

$$\text{Framework validity for CUM} = \mu \left(\sum_{i=1}^{nc1} CUMc1i/nc1 + \dots + \sum_{i=1}^{nc6} CUMc6i /nc6 \right)$$

Where:

CUM_{c1} = CUM criterion 1

nc_1 = the number of indicators with value "1" or "2" for the criterion 1

Similarly, the value of each CUM criterion is calculated for the 6 CUM criteria.

The average value is the framework CUM validity result. The framework CUM validity will range from 0 to 2, where a value closer to 2 indicates a framework composed of indicators that can holistically approach and evaluate CUM.

Equation 5:

$$\text{Framework potential to measure ecological justice} = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n ji \right) \div n$$

Where:

j = indicator ecological justice score, $0 \leq j \leq 2$

n = the number of indicators

Finally, for evaluating the relevance to sustainable development, a qualitative approach has been followed. Having defined an on/off score for the indicators' relevance to the SDGs, the number of indicators that link to each of the SDGs is calculated.

4.4 Tool for indicator selection

4.4.1 Graphical tool for visualization of indicator score

As many indicators have been selected to be part of the framework, with extensive data per indicator, the development of a user-friendly tool was investigated for visualizing the information. The tool was particularly envisioned to support concise overview and visualization of the indicator criteria scores, and thereby assist in indicator selection.

The tool is built using streamlit python framework and it is published on the following url: <https://h2020justnature.tuc.gr/>. Emphasis was given during the development of the tool in providing ease of use along with valuable information to the user.

The tool interface has two sections (Figure 4). The left section includes all the user interaction elements in drop down menus where the user can select the challenge (injustice) area, the indicators associated with this challenge, and the criteria to be visualized for this indicator. When the selection process is finished, the requested data appear on the right side.

Figure 4: Tool interface

4.4.2 Example of using the tool

Here an example of using the tool is provided.

First, the user selects the challenge, which for this example is the air quality injustice (Figure 5). Next, the user selects an indicator of interest to measure relevant to the air quality injustice (Figure 6). The drop-down menu includes all the indicators associated with the air quality injustices according to the steps described in section 4.1. For this example, the selected indicator is "European Air Quality Index [in GA: Reduced exposure to air pollution (by area/socio-economic unit)]".

Figure 5: User selection of challenges

Figure 6: User selection of indicator

Finally, the user selects the criteria to be visualized from the options of a) Technical criteria, and b) CUM criteria (Figure 7). The scores of the criteria are plotted in a barpolar graph (Figure 8, Figure 9). Along with the visualization of the scores for the criteria, the proposed method of indicator measurement/calculation, the associated SDGs, and the potential to capture ecological justice are displayed (Figure 8).

Figure 7: User selection of criteria to be plotted.

Indicator information

ID: 1.3 European Air Quality Index [in GA: Reduced exposure to air pollution (by area/socio-economic unit)]

Proposed method of indicator measurement/calculation

The Index uses 'up-to-date' air quality data officially reported every hour by EEA member countries, complemented where necessary by modelled air quality data from the European Union's Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS). Additionally, can be complemented with local air quality data from equipments installed in NBS locations. Concentrations values for up to five key pollutants determine the index level that reflects air quality at each monitoring station. The index corresponds to the poorest level for any of five pollutants... More details for the calculation methodology in: <https://op.europa.eu/en/yXbk>

Associated SGDS:

SDG3: good health and wellbeing
 SDG11: sustainable cities and communities
 SDG15: life on land

Potential to capture ecological justice:

Potentially, needs additional data: EAQI per neighborhood, demographic data (population groups residing in each neighborhood)

Figure 8: "European Air Quality Index", plotting technical criteria scores.

Figure 9: “European Air Quality Index”, plotting CUM criteria scores.

The user can use the plot control menu to view the plot in full screen (Figure 10). Finally, the score of each of the criteria can be viewed when the user hovers their mouse over the icon (Figure 11).

Figure 10: Plot control

Figure 11: Explanation of the score when the user hovers over it.

5 FORMATION OF TAILORED INDICATOR FRAMEWORKS

This section begins by presenting the steps for selecting the indicators for the NbS interventions' assessment and the creation of the tailored indicator framework per CiPeL. Next, the assessment of the tailored indicator framework that has resulted for each CiPeL is presented. The assessment includes the scores of each framework that have been calculated according to the methodology presented in section. This is not intended to evaluate the quality of the framework as “good” or “poor”, but rather provide an insight on what the framework can offer in its current composition. The section closes with a reflection on the resulting frameworks and their differences vis-à-vis the CiPeLs different objectives.

5.1 Selecting indicators for the CiPeLs

The NbS monitoring and evaluation framework is directly linked to the challenges that the NbS interventions are expected to address. A stepwise process has been followed for developing the evaluation objectives, leading to a tailored evaluation framework for each CiPeL.

Step 1: The first step was the identification of the challenges that each CiPeL needs to address. These were first identified by the CiPeL representatives and confirmed after the 1st Local stakeholder workshop (in step 2).

The rationale was that the challenges indicate the needs for improvement and the steps needed to achieve this through suitable NbS interventions. To measure and evaluate the results of the interventions, a set of indicators has been selected per CiPeL that serves as the tailored indicator framework per CiPeL.

The first step took place between August – October 2023, when all CiPeL representatives, with the support of the Attendant Project Partners (ApPs), performed the initial selection of indicators. The criterion for selection of indicators was the relevance of the indicator to the CiPeL's objectives and planned interventions at the time. This initial selection was also intended to support T3.2 in getting feedback for the sensor-based monitoring.

Step 2: The next selection step was the review and refinement of the indicator framework per CiPeL, which took place between June – July 2023, after the 1st and 2nd LSW had been completed for the majority of the CiPeLs. Following completion of the LSW1, the challenges were clarified and confirmed with the stakeholder's input. At this step the questions asked for updating the indicator selection were:

1. *At this stage, having completed the 1st Local Stakeholder Workshop, needs, challenges, and areas of in-justices in your CipeL have been confirmed. Check your selections and see if there are challenges that are important to evaluate but for which you currently have no relevant indicator selected. Maybe you would like to consider selecting a relevant progress indicator.*

2. *At this stage, having completed the 2nd Local Stakeholder Workshop, your planned interventions have become clearer or finalized. Think about whether the indicators that you have already selected are suitable for evaluating the impact of the interventions, or whether you need to remove some indicators and include others.*
3. *Check the indicators relevant/needed for pre-monitoring/ measuring the baseline (existing situation).*

The information provided for each indicator e.g., temporal scale, spatial scale, pros & cons, methodology, further assisted the selection process.

As a result, frameworks tailored to evaluating each CiPeL's objectives and interventions were formed. The different combinations of indicators and indicator scores result in frameworks with different characteristics. The resulting framework per CiPeL and the evaluation according to the framework criteria are presented in the following sub-sections.

Step 3: Owing to interdependence with other project activities, especially those related to planning of workshops in WP4, the 3rd step will take place during the CiPeLs' collaborative workshop in October 2023, after submission of the present deliverable. In a dedicated session, the tailored frameworks that have been formed will be discussed with the CiPeL representatives and will be juxtaposed with each CiPeL's respective objectives. A full description of the session and its outcomes will be provided in relevant reports.

Subsequent steps: In line with the scope of JUSTNature, the framework aims to evaluate for each CiPeL the environmental benefits of the NbS interventions but also holistically demonstrate the preservation of ecological space, the inclusion of circularity in urban processes, and the progress towards specific SDGs correlated with the interventions. The framework is by nature dynamic and can be altered by adding or removing indicators to adjust to the specific needs at each period of the NbS life.

5.2 Resulting indicator frameworks

Frameworks with varying indicator compositions and results in their qualities have been created. The created frameworks per CiPeL are not directly comparable since they were designed to evaluate different NbS, derived from different needs and their primary purpose is to assist the CiPeLs in aligning with the specific objectives of the proposed interventions. Each framework, being tailored to the CiPeL that will use it, can only be juxtaposed to the challenges and objectives of the respective CiPeL.

Table 6 shows the diversity among CiPeLs as each CiPeL prioritizes different challenges to tackle with the selected NbS interventions. The number of indicators selected stems from the challenges that are more important to each CiPeL. These have been highlighted through the discussions with the local stakeholders and reported in the relevant workshop reports (prepared by the CiPeL representatives and curated by PI in WP4). Common characteristics

are that almost no indicators are chosen at this stage for the Temporal injustices and that all CiPeLs have at least 3 indicators for the Thermal and Spatial injustices.

Table 6: Number of indicators selected per challenge for all CiPeLs

Cipel	Air quality	Thermal	Carbon	Spatial	FFH	Temporal	Social Justice & Cohesion	Economy & Employment	Total
Bolzano	1	3	2	3	1	0	1	0	11
Merano	0	5	0	3	5	0	1	0	14
Chania	6	9	5	6	4	2	1	5	38
Gzira	9	4	0	3	0	0	0	2	18
Leuven	1	4	0	4	4	0	7	1	21
Szombathely	5	12	2	8	6	0	7	4	44
Munich	0	2	0	6	4	0	2	2	16

The frameworks with the highest numbers of indicators are those of Szombathely (44 indicators) and Chania (38 indicators). Whereas Bolzano has selected 11 indicators and Merano 14. In any case, through the stepwise approach for selecting indicators, all cities have ensured to select at least the necessary indicators in their respective areas of interest to measure progress and the impacts of the selected NbS.

As explained, the scores of the selected indicators result in the framework evaluation and demonstrate its performance. Figure 12 depicts the resulting indicator frameworks and the scores that they got for the criteria credibility, applicability, ability to track temporal changes, CUM validity, and potential to measure ecological justice. The relevance to sustainable development, resulting from an on/off criterion, is not placed in the diagram and is qualitatively assessed in this discussion.

The frameworks have high scores in **credibility** (i.e., the framework is composed of credible indicators with transparent methodology and unambiguous interpretation) and **applicability** (i.e., the application of the framework is based on applicable indicators and the required data are easily accessible at no/low cost). This is reasonable since the basis for forming these frameworks came from state-of-the-art indicators for NbS, already implemented in previous NbS projects.

On the other hand, the ability to track temporal changes has received a low score. This results from the fact that two indicator scores are included in the calculation of the framework score: the ability to track temporal changes and temporal sensitivity. Although many indicators can track temporal changes, this is not always sensitive to rapid changes. Nevertheless, many of the outcomes of the NbS interventions require relatively long periods to become visible or do not show significant differences in short periods.

Looking at the results of the concept criteria, the CUM validity scores range from 0.93 to 1.53, while for ecological justice all frameworks got score close to 1, ranging from 0.73 to

1.09. A further analysis of the results for CUM validity and ecological justice helps to better interpret these results.

Figure 12: Results of the criteria credibility, applicability, ability to track temporal changes, CUM validity, and potential to measure ecological justice for the indicator framework of each CiPeL.

All frameworks have the potential to evaluate ecological justice (Figure 13). The ecological justice criterion for the framework considers that: **the framework includes indicators that can measure ecological justice** and it is calculated by averaging the ecological justice scores of the indicators that compose the framework. The indicator scores for potential to measure ecological justice get values of 0=no; 1=has the potential; 2=yes. It is inferred that the frameworks are mostly composed of indicators that got score 1, meaning that they have the potential to capture and reveal socio-ecological injustices. This potential can be realised if the indicator result is disaggregated considering spatial and/or socio-economic distribution. For example, the indicator of Total particulate matter removed by NBS vegetation, measured in kg/ha/day, can reveal socio-ecological injustices, if demographic data of population groups living around NbS are available and considered for the impact evaluation.

Figure 13: Composition of frameworks regarding the indicators' potential to measure ecological justice.

The frameworks are mainly composed of indicators that have the potential to measure ecological justice. This is the reason why, although the frameworks contain adequate indicators to assess ecological justice, all the frameworks got values close to 1 for the ecological justice criterion. In Merano 70% of the indicators have the potential to measure ecological justice, but none directly, therefore the value for ecological justice for the indicator framework of Merano is 0.79. In the framework of Bolzano, 18% of indicators can directly evaluate ecological justice and this results in the highest score for ecological justice among the frameworks (1.09). Eventually, the cities will need to assess whether they want to strengthen the measurement of ecological justice or how they want to utilize this potential.

The CUM validity criterion is further investigated through the charts in Figure 14 through Figure 20 that depict the number of indicators that link to the 6 aspects of CUM. There are indicators in all frameworks that can directly or indirectly link to the evaluation of all aspects of CUM, except for the frameworks of Bolzano and Merano. Bolzano's framework does not include indicators that can measure the aspects of "creation and distribution of added value and other outcomes of economic performance" nor "investing on green economy". Merano's framework does not include indicators that can measure "creation and distribution of added value and other outcomes of economic performance".

The results show that different aspects of CUM are associated to the planned NbS interventions and different indicators are needed to measure the progress towards CUM through NbS performance evaluation.

Figure 14: Bolzano's framework; number of indicators that link to CUM validity criteria.

Figure 15: Merano's framework; number of indicators that link to CUM validity criteria.

Figure 16: Chania's framework; number of indicators that link to CUM validity criteria.

Figure 17: Gzira's framework; number of indicators that link to CUM validity criteria.

Figure 18: Leuven's framework; Number of indicators that link to CUM validity criteria.

Figure 19: Szombathely's framework; Number of indicators that link to CUM validity criteria.

Figure 20: Munich's framework; Number of indicators that link to CUM validity criteria.

Regarding the relevance to the SDGs and sustainable development overall, all frameworks are composed of indicators that can link to progress in multiple SDGs. The relevance of each framework to sustainable development and the potential to measure progress towards specific SDGs is depicted in Figure 21, with the number of indicators that link to SDGs. The most prominent links are found with SDG11 and SDG3, explained by the focus on the transition to sustainable urban areas in parallel to the population's good health and wellbeing. SDGs 13 and 15 are also addressed with indicators in all frameworks, indicating the efforts to mitigate the effects of climate change and the aim to preserve and protect natural ecosystems.

	1. NO POVERTY	2. ZERO HUNGER	3. GOOD HEALTH AND WELLBEING	5. GENDER EQUALITY	6. CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION	8. DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH	9. INDUSTRY INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE	10. REDUCED INEQUALITIES	11. SUSTAINABLE CITIES AND COMMUNITIES	12. RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION	13. CLIMATE ACTION	15. LIFE ON LAND	16. PEACE JUSTICE AND STRONG INSTITUTIONS
Bolzano			6	2				3	9		5	2	1
Merano		1	9	1			1	4	14	3	7	8	3
Chania	1		18	2		4	3	7	29	1	12	12	3
Gzira		1	13	1	1	1	2	4	15		5	9	1
Leuven		0	12	7				9	20	1	5	7	8
Szombathely		1	25	11	1	1	2	14	37	3	14	17	11
Munich			9	3		1	3	6	13	2	4	3	4

Figure 21: Number of indicators that link to SDGs.

Finally, it is interesting to see the distribution of the indicators in the three pillars of sustainable development (Figure 22). All frameworks include indicators that are connected

to the environmental and societal pillars. For Bolzano and Merano there are no indicators for the economic pillar. This again can be justified by the challenges of the cities and the objectives of the planned NbS. Overall, the CiPeLs have prioritized confronting the environmental and societal challenges.

Figure 22: Distribution of indicators in the pillars of sustainable development

Within JUSTNature, a stepwise methodology has been followed for developing ecological justice – circularity indicator frameworks, tailored to each city’s challenges and objectives of NbS interventions. The resulting frameworks can be used as basis for the cities to build upon and adapt to their future NbS interventions. Consequently, the frameworks can be reviewed and revised throughout the project’s lifetime, especially in relation to evolving objectives.

Within, as well as beyond JUSTNature, the cities can use the evaluation of the framework for checking alignment with their objectives and targets and ensuring that they have in hand a credible and applicable indicator framework that can measure and provide insights on critical areas of ecological injustices, transition to circularity and sustainable urban development. In that sense, the developed ecological justice – circularity indicator frameworks are not static, but rather flexible and their qualities will change by adding or removing indicators with changing plans and objectives.

6 BENCHMARK NBS INDICATORS FROM COMPARABLE CITIES

6.1 Introduction

Underpinning the logic of NbS is the promise of a double dividend. One part of this dividend is the cost-saving secured by harnessing ecosystem services to meet needs that would otherwise require an engineered solution, as when tree-cover substitutes for air-conditioning in cooling homes in a neighborhood. The other part comprises the myriad co-benefits that the ecosystem provides. In the case of tree-cover, these benefits include aesthetic beauty, water filtration, carbon sequestration, as well as physical and health benefits.

Notwithstanding this promise, the implementation of NbS necessarily requires a change in the status quo, which brings its own attendant costs. In urban landscapes, where space is a premium and priorities diverge, the implementation of NbS can therefore become a complex balancing act. Stakeholders may see the same project through different lenses, each valuing different outcomes. For instance, a property developer might focus on potential increases in real estate value from greener surroundings, while local residents might prioritize recreational spaces and cleaner air. Residents may also be concerned that integrating nature into urban areas could elevate property prices, thus displacing low-income households. Another challenge is maintenance. While ecosystems can be self-sustaining once mature, they may need care, protection, and monitoring, especially in their nascent stages. This can imply high upfront costs that may dissuade action. Moreover, the unpredictability of nature, coupled with urban stressors, makes the success of these interventions uncertain at times.

Nevertheless, much can be learned from past experiences, which is why monitoring and evaluation of NbS interventions is crucial. *Impact evaluations*, which attempt to infer a causal relationship between an intervention and a (set of) outcome indicator(s), are especially important because they move beyond monitoring changes at the site of an NbS – as insightful as this may be – to ascribe those changes to the NbS itself. A credible causal attribution is a necessary condition for informed discussions among stakeholders about which NbS to prioritize. It is therefore up to urban planners to undertake impact assessments, with an eye toward tallying changes in different outcome indicators and providing an evidence base for the design of cost-effective future interventions.

In many cases, such evaluations may require the assessment of multiple bottom-lines that span the biological, economic, and social realms, with appropriate indicators to measure each one. This clearly adds complexity, but it can also serve to highlight trade-offs between progress in one area and progress in others. In a study of trade-offs amongst social, economic and conservation outcomes, Halpern *et al.*, 2013 found that, “[social] equity tends to trade off nonlinearly with the potential to achieve conservation objectives, such that similar conservation outcomes can be possible with greater equity, to a point.” The authors point out, however, that a variety of trade-off typologies exist, depending upon how such

terms as “social equity” are defined. A study by Brooks, Waylen, & Mulder (2012), used a meta-analysis to identify trade-offs between ecological, economic, and social outcomes of community-based conservation projects. Incidentally, the highest trade-offs appear to occur between economic and social outcomes. In whatever case, the key lesson is that the NbS measures will have to define their priorities to ultimately enable decision-making, especially when there are trade-offs within NbS objectives. A causal impact assessment can serve to highlight such trade-offs, but to date examples of such assessments remain rare.

The aims of the following chapter are multifold. The first is to cover key conceptual considerations that underpin impact assessments of NbS when the aim is to ascribe causal effects to the intervention. The focus here is on quantifying changes in individual indicators, recognizing that a holistic assessment almost certainly requires consideration of multiple indicators using a mix of methodological approaches. The second aim is to briefly cover a selection of such approaches, including ones that are appropriate for the data sparse environments that often characterize NbS interventions. A common feature of each approach is the identification of control site(s) that serve as a comparison with the site of the NbS. This feature is often required for inferring causality, but it raises the question of how to ensure that such sites are sufficiently “comparable.” The discussion includes coverage of benchmarking and methodological adjustments by justice area. The third aim is to sketch a methodology for assessing comparability and identifying control sites, illustrating its application with data from the CiPeLs. The chapter closes with a review of existing databases and a discussion of data-driven approaches to impact assessment.

6.2 Conceptualizing Causality

Effective urban planning relies on monitoring and evaluating changes in outcome indicators to identify whether an intervention is having its intended consequences. A typical approach to monitoring involves a before-after comparison, wherein data are collected before and after the intervention to measure the direction and magnitude of changes. While such information is well-suited to track whether conditions in the target region are improving, it typically does not capture the causal effect of the intervention itself, and hence, is unlikely to be useful in ascertaining the success of the intervention.

Impact evaluation moves beyond measurement to explanation, with the aim of estimating the causal effect of an intervention. From an empirical perspective, the causal effect can be conceived as the difference between the value of an outcome indicator when an NbS-intervention – or treatment² – is undertaken, and the value of the same indicator in the intervention’s absence, with other things held fixed. More concretely, we wish to compare

² The words “treatment” and “intervention” as well as the words “control” and “comparison” are used interchangeably in this discussion.

the state of the world in a region treated by an intervention with the hypothetical state of the world in the same region had there been no intervention, with the difference between states being the intervention's causal impact. Being based on an unseen outcome, this difference is, of course, impossible to calculate, a circumstance referred to as the *evaluation problem*.

In essence, the problem is one of missing data: the potential state of a result indicator in the absence of an intervention is unknown. At first blush, the problem can be solved by collecting data on one or more sites both before and after the intervention is implemented, with the "before"-data serving to proxy the indicator's value without the intervention. The analyst can then proceed to calculate the change in the indicator over the two points in time. Whether this calculation captures the causal effect, however, is questionable. It requires, at a minimum, ruling out the influence of other variables that may vary over the two points in time and that influence the indicator. As the example below illustrates, this assumption is often dubious.

Various empirical techniques can be used to circumvent the difficulty, all of which involve simulating a credible counterfactual scenario to address the missing data problem. One such technique is a randomized control trial (RCT), which randomly allocates the treatment across study subjects and then derives the causal effect by comparing treated with non-treated subjects. Because the randomization renders the two subject pools comparable across all attributes that affect the outcome, the non-treated group serves as the counterfactual to measure how the treated group would hypothetically fare in the absence of the treatment, thereby solving the missing data problem. The simple difference in mean outcomes across the treated and untreated groups yields an unbiased estimate of the intervention's causal effect. While considered a gold standard of impact evaluation, RCTs have limited practical applicability to questions of conservation interest. Aside from the difficulty of randomizing a treatment when (nature-based) infrastructure is involved, questions of ethical and political feasibility may also arise.

An alternative approach is the difference-in-differences (DiD) estimator. The basic premise of DiD is to create a counterfactual scenario by collecting data not only in treatment sites but also in comparable control sites both before and after the intervention. Comparability, which is measured with respect to the set of predictors that determine the outcome in both sites, is key: in the ideal case, the control sites can be regarded as a proxy for the treatment sites. By measuring how conditions changed in the control sites, where there has been no intervention, the aim is to simulate how conditions would have changed at the treatment site if there had been no intervention. Subtracting the changes in an outcome indicator observed in a control site from the changes observed in a treatment site – the difference in the difference – tackles the evaluation problem, yielding a causal estimate of the intervention's impact.

A simple example serves to illustrate the approach. Assume that an intervention is initiated in 2022 and completed in 2023 that aims to restore water quality in an urban lake, where a key outcome indicator is the fish stock. Baseline data on fish counts are collected prior to the initiation of the intervention from the treated lake and from a lake in a neighboring city that is of close proximity and similar size, which serves as the control. A follow-up survey of fish counts is conducted a year later in 2024 in both sites, giving the stocks a year to evolve following the intervention. The diagrams below (Figure 23) indicate the fish stocks recorded in the baseline and follow-up surveys for the two sites.

Figure 23: Illustration of difference-in-differences

Consider, for the purpose of this example that 2023 is shaping up to be the Earth's warmest on record, with the temperature of water bodies breaking records across the globe, a development that could have adverse impacts on fish reproduction. Turning first to the treatment site, the fish stock decreases from 24 to 21 between the baseline and the follow-up surveys, for a negative difference of 3 fish. A before-after comparison would thus indicate a decline of 12.5% percent in the fish stock. Whether this decline can be ascribed to the NbS depends on the extent to which other factors, such as warmer water, affected fish stocks over the recorded time interval. The measurement in the control site is intended to capture the influence of these other factors, predicated on the idea that the control captures the hypothetical state of the intervention site had there been no intervention. Here the fish stock decreased even more dramatically between the baseline survey and follow-up, yielding a negative difference of 4 fish. The difference in the difference between the two sites gives the estimated causal impact of the intervention: $-3 - (-4) = 1$. Thus, notwithstanding the negative change in the fish count captured by the before-after comparison in the treatment site, the DiD estimate suggests that the intervention had a

positive impact. Put in the words of causal attribution: the fish stock declined in the treatment site in the year following the intervention, but it would have declined even more in the absence of any intervention.

6.3 Methodological obstacles

Establishing comparability across benchmark sites and running impact analyses using DiD is still not a straightforward task. There are several assumptions and complications which vary from performance area to performance area and across intervention sites. We will cover these in the following subchapter:

- Parallel trends assumption
- Onset of the impact
- Spillover effects
- Effective dosage and scalability
- Context dependency

The most important assumption underpinning the difference-in-difference estimator is the parallel trends assumption, according to which the outcome in treatment and control group would both follow the same time trend in the absence of the treatment. This assumption is depicted in Figure 24, where the solid red and green lines indicate the trends in fish stocks in the treatment and control sites. The dashed portion of the red line indicates the hypothetical development of the fish stocks in the absence of any treatment. The assumption of parallel trends would be violated if other influences unique to one of the sites were to impact the outcome after the treatment. An example would be a surge in agricultural run-off that adversely affects fish stocks in the control site, which would negatively alter the trajectory of the fish count and (in this case positively) bias the estimated causal effect.

Figure 24: Parallel trends assumption

Even when the parallel trends assumption of the difference-in-difference estimator is met, the above example abstracts from several complications that may arise in practice.

One crucial consideration is the timing, specifically the length of time that should separate the baseline survey and the post-treatment survey. This will, of course, depend on the indicator in question. Indeed, the timing between the baseline and post-treatment surveys is a critical consideration in the DiD estimator. The ideal time gap depends on the nature of the treatment, the indicator being measured, and the speed at which changes are expected to occur. When it comes to ecological indicators like fish stocks or vegetation growth, it may take a long time to show noticeable effects from an intervention, requiring a long interval between surveys to fully capture the impact of a policy (presumably longer than the year-interval used in the example). In contrast, a social indicator, like public visitation to a natural amenity, might show more immediate changes following an intervention, making a shorter time gap between surveys more appropriate. Another consideration is when the treatment is administered. If the treatment is a one-time event, like a policy change, the appropriate timing for the post-treatment survey would be different compared to an ongoing treatment, such as a continuous training program. In the case of ongoing treatments, it might be necessary to conduct multiple post-treatment surveys to measure the effects at different points in time.

Impact assessments of NbS should also recognize the possibility of spillovers, which can complicate impact attribution. Spillover effects refer to the unintended consequences of an intervention that manifest outside the immediate area of implementation. One source of spillovers is ecosystem connectivity. An intervention in one part of an ecosystem can cascade to influence other parts. For instance, restoring a wetland in one area could improve water quality downstream, benefiting communities and ecosystems that were not the primary targets of the intervention. In this instance, neglecting such positive downstream impacts could lead to an underestimation of the causal effect of the intervention. Another source of spillovers is social connectivity, as when afforestation in one region boosts ecotourism while simultaneously diverting tourism from neighboring areas. Neglecting the spillover in this case could lead to an overestimation of the causal impact, to the extent that revenue losses from decreased tourism at the site of the spillover are unaccounted for.

Caution is additionally required to ensure that the control site itself is not affected by spillovers. Following Tobler's first law of geography – that near things are more related than distant things – geographic proximity of the treatment and control sites is one way to provide some assurance of comparability. But proximity can also be a vice, as it increases the likelihood that the site will be contaminated by spillovers from the intervention. In the case of nature-based solutions, an example of spillovers could be the migration of wildlife from the treated site to the control site. For instance, if the intervention involves planting trees or creating wetlands to attract certain species of birds, these birds may subsequently migrate to the control site, thereby affecting its ecosystem and the outcomes measured there. Similarly, the physical changes in the treatment site, such as altered water flow or soil

conditions, could also impact the control site through hydrological or geological connections. Navigating the trade-off between comparability and the threat from contamination of the control site through spillovers is crucial to obtain an unbiased estimate of the causal effect of the intervention.

Furthermore, one must consider a common weakness of pilot projects: Due to budgetary limitations, and a focus on process rather than outcome, the interventions may be too limited in scope to provide a signal to capture a significant impact. Nonetheless, this does not mean that the treatment is ineffective, but rather the dosage is insufficient to produce an effect that is measurable. For example, an urban forestation project could be planned for a 10-ha area, but the initial intervention is only 0.5 ha, which would then be heavily monitored to make assumptions about the larger project. For several areas of performance, this would work: airborne pollutant removal, carbon storage, and evapotranspiration could be measured. However, this intervention cannot realistically be the basis for measuring impact on noise abatement since noticeable noise reduction from streets requires at least 10-20-metre-wide dense vegetation (Pathak, Tripathi, & Mishra, 2008). Similarly, other variables that do produce a signal at a smaller scale may not scale linearly. For example, filtering particulate matter has diminishing returns, while biodiversity may accelerate if the area designated for rewilding increases. It is therefore necessary to consider for each treatment and each indicator what the minimum scale of effective dosage is, and what the scalability of the impact is.

Finally, and connected to the problem of scale, there is the problem of context-dependency. NbS does not function in isolation, but always as a part of a larger green infrastructural system. The same exact intervention in different parts of the city will yield different impacts. Such heterogeneity can severely compromise the external validity of even a well-executed causal impact assessment, rendering the extrapolation of findings from one study site to an untested site imprudent. What makes this more complicated, is that the same NbS have different roles in different systems, and the relevant context to determine comparability changes based on these roles. For example, an urban park can serve a hydrological role. In this case, what is relevant, is the water cycle of the city, what is the receiving channel, or destination right after the park, what is the catchment of this destination, what is the degree of imperviousness of the catchment, what are other hydrological losses (vegetation, rainwater harvesting, etc.), what are the limits for intensity and volume of the destination, what are the soil conditions below the park, what pollutants the runoff water might pick up. On the other hand, from a spatial justice perspective, what is important is the population density in the vicinity of the park, the presence or absence of competing public spaces with similar facilities, the pedestrian and bicycle infrastructure, public transportation, and the social composition of the neighborhood. This experiment can and should be iterated to all justice areas, since we may find a similarly sized park in the neighboring city as a control site, but if, for example, the treatment includes contributions to a 15-minute city concept,

then the control site should no longer even be another park in another city, but a neighborhood with similar density of parks.

6.4 Recommendations for benchmarking

The management of the risks arising from the methodological obstacles shall be achieved through the collection of background information which will help selecting appropriate comparison sites and give guidelines on the applicability and limitations of the impact assessments. The most important recommendation is to follow the principles of complex system theory, namely, avoid reducing the problem, and rely on heterogeneous sources of knowledge. Many of the obstacles refer to blind spots, which can be alleviated by relying on local expertise and fostering collaboration of different disciplines. Therefore, it is recommended **(R1) to mobilize and consult a local team of experts, whose fields reflect the key performances co-selected by the project owners and local stakeholders**. The role of this local team is to share tacit and formal knowledge of the intervention site and prospective control sites, and to synthesize their experience in accurate system models.

To support the work of the local expert team, it is necessary for the project team to **(R2) specify all treatments in the context of the impact they are expected to elicit, through specific mechanisms, responding to specific problems – i.e., specify the NbS**. This is necessary since the obstacles refer to variability in pairs of treatments and influenced performances. Articulating these treatments is a necessary step since urban greening projects are often described in terms of landscape architectural projects or in terms of facilities and amenities developed for the public. Neither of these are appropriate for impact assessment, as the impacts are tied to the NbS, not to the greening project in general. For example, a landscape architect might describe a project as 1.5 hectares of urban woodland, with an inventory of trees, shrubs, and other plants, pathways, lighting, informational boards, and amenities. From an impact assessment perspective, what is important is the NbS. As stated in D2.1 and by the IUCN, NbS address human needs with the deliberated utilization and safeguarding of the mechanisms and resources of nature (IUCN, 2016). It is restoring, creating, and improving ecosystems with an intent that includes but also goes beyond conservation to reliably solve engineering and social problems. The core elements of this definition include resolving a human problem, intentionality, and reliance on nature. The problem is the simplest to articulate. Intentionality means that there is a specific treatment designed to resolve the stated problem, therefore the treatment must be known. Reliance on nature needs to be explained through the mechanism the designers rely on when designing the treatment. Finally, the way the treatment solves the problem is articulated by stating the performance. Thus, with these four elements, problem, treatment, mechanism, and performance, the NbS components of a greening project can be articulated, which provides enough background information to consider spillover, onset, dosage, and scalability. For example, such specification could be: roadside airborne pollution (problem), reduced by biofiltration (mechanism), through a multilayered vegetated strip 3-metre wide (treatment), that is expected to reduce pollutant concentration in the area off-

road (performance). Through this information, it becomes clear that spillover only occurs if the control site is polluted by the same road, behind the intervention site (spillover effect); the mechanism allows us to compute dosage by matching traffic density on the road to leaf, stem, and root surface area (dosage); the treatment becomes effective as the plants grow (onset); and that the project scales linearly parallel to the road, and with diminishing returns perpendicular to it (scalability).

The project teams must also consider **(R3) the various systems in which the NbS participate in, alongside its specific role**, to ensure that the assumption of parallel trends holds true, and to understand which aspects of the NbS context are relevant. This is where the difference between NbS and green infrastructure has practical relevance. Despite the multiscale perspective that proponents attribute to NbS, in practice, NbS projects often lack a systemic approach, designing interventions as means to manipulate larger networks, systems of interrelated areas (Langemeyer & Baró, 2021). One possible explanation is that the concept itself, and the wording of the NbS definitions generalize to an extent that the multiscale systems perspective is latent. Its focus on actions further emphasizes that NbS primarily consist of individual projects that, though not entirely indifferent to the context, are characterized by objectives primarily tailored to a specific scale. Green (and blue) infrastructure on the other hand emphasizes multiscale dynamics of various natural and semi-natural elements and argues that the ecosystem services delivered are not a result of single, goal-oriented actions, but of a nested network where the pieces fulfil some role in a larger system (Kroll, Müller, Haase, & Fohrer, 2012). A useful approach to relate the two is to consider NbS as nodes in green infrastructures (Langemeyer & Baró, 2021). In practice, this means not only describing projects as a list of NbS, but also considering the NbS as a node, while gaining an understanding of the relationships and connections within that network in which they are located. NbS as a node means it has a role in a system, whereas the network is a connected set of elements performing the system. If the role is identified for the treatment and control sites, parallel trends can be established with higher confidence and relevant contextual parameters become clear. For example, the vegetated strip mentioned above can be characterized as a node in three different networks: an air purification network, a hydrological network, and an ecological network. For the first, the network is designed according to point and linear pollution sources and ventilation systems. For the second, the strip is the first line of treatment for runoff water from the street that should not pass on any excess water to the land beyond. For the third, the strip is characterized by the ecological patches it connects and the kind of species whose mobility is enabled. If the control site has – or potentially could have – the same three roles, it becomes clear that precipitation, road traffic density, and ecological fragmentation are critical variables to assess comparability.

Finally, the role of the local expert team is to validate R2 and R3, and to use this information to **(R4) specify the variables by which comparability can be assessed, select appropriate control sites, select further data to be monitored, and to create a risk assessment and**

expected limitations if any of their prescriptions are not met. The result of this exercise would be an actionable guideline not only to impact assessment, but also to the interpretation of the results; this guideline should provide the necessary context and confidence in the results to preserve the democratic legitimacy of policy decisions based on them.

The table below (Table 7) summarizes the methodological obstacles and prescriptions for impact assessors on how to overcome them.

Table 7: Methodological challenges and recommendations for impacts assessors.

Obstacle	Risk	Recommendations
Parallel trends	Confounding factors may influence the impact on either the treatment or the control site.	Known confounders of key performances to be mapped and used as comparability metrics when selecting control sites. During monitoring, alternative explanations for specific performance are to be brainstormed and debated with local group of experts.
Onset	Different impacts may occur in different timeframes.	For each treatment-performance pair, onset of impact is to be specified and taken as an input for scheduling monitoring.
Spillover	The impact of the treatment site might elicit changes in the control site.	For each treatment-performance pair, area of effect is to be estimated, and excluded from control selection.
Dosage	The impact may only occur at a larger scale than the intervention.	Theoretical upscaling interventions to be defined, for performances not realistically achievable with smaller intervention, expected impacts to be simulated based on existing knowledgebase.
Scaling	The impact of the intervention may not be usable to predict the impact of a larger intervention.	Linear and non-linear scaling to be specified for each treatment-performance pair.
Context	Different impacts also depend on system dynamics depending on different contextual factors.	System models to be specified for each NbS role, contextual variables to be specified with local group of experts and used as comparability metrics when selecting control sites.

6.5 Methodological adjustments by justice area

Of the components of the prescribed NbS specification, performance and treatment are the key to overcome obstacles for impact assessment. While treatments, problems, mechanisms, and systemic roles are unique (to various extents) to each site, performances are largely standardized. The purpose of the following subchapter is to critically review the most pertinent areas of performance and offer guidance on the different impact assessment obstacles. The following paragraphs dissect each justice area, describe the associated indicator pools in the Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response (DPSIR)

framework, and discuss them from the perspective of parallel trends, onset, spillover, dosage, scaling, and context.

In the area of **air quality justice**, indicators mostly cover the state of air quality (e.g., European air quality index, number of days during which pollutant concentration exceeds a threshold), response indicators focusing on biofiltration (e.g., particulate matter removed, leaf area index), co-impacts in terms of health and cost of health (e.g., morbidity due to poor air quality, avoided costs for pollution control). On the driving force and pressure side of the causal chain, there are no indicators other than the incidence of street canyons and distance from pollution sources. More significant pressures are traffic densities, the age of vehicles, and the proximity of industrial production sites. When monitoring concentrations at both sites, changes in land-use, traffic density, and traffic regulations may be confounding effects for the state indicators, invalidating parallel trends.

When it comes to onset, since biofiltration is the key mechanism NbS treatments are expected to rely on, it will depend on plant growth rate, which directly influences the leaf- and the root zone surface areas. This also means that the effect is not steady, as there is an immediate increase in biofiltration areas after planting, followed by a decelerating growth over the course of 10-20 years, considering tree growth. Specific designs and planting techniques could drastically change the onset however – for example, Miyawaki technique, or bamboo forests. It is also important to consider weather and microclimatic effects for comparability. Cross-ventilation and precipitation are crucial to replenish biofiltration capacities. Due to this effect, climate change plays a role in the onset as well.

Spillover effects depend on the distance between the NbS and the pollution source and the wind patterns. As a rule of thumb, the most critical zone from a health perspective is the first 500 meters from a road with heavy traffic on the downwind side (HEI Panel on the HHealth Effects of Traffic-Related Air Pollution, 2010; Zhu, Kuhn, Mayo, & Hinds, 2006), whereas industrial sites vary from size, production technology, and on-site measures. Abecasis *et al.* (2022), concluded that steelworks sites may distribute heavy metals in significant concentrations in the first 1-2 kilometers; Garcia-Gonzales, Shamasunder, & Jerrett, (2019), concluded that volatile organic compounds reach background level near oil facilities after 130-195 meters. However, street canyons may contain most of the pollutants, with shielded areas receiving as little as 50-60% of the concentration compared to the concentration on the road (Kaski, Mäkelä, & Niemi, 2020). There is also variability among pollutants, with one meta-analysis identified distance-decay gradients of 100-400, 100-300, and 200-500 meters respectively for elemental carbon, ultrafine particles, and nitrogen-dioxide (Zhou & Levy, 2007).

In terms of dosage, even small interventions can yield significant impacts, as one study demonstrates how a temporary line of about 20 young trees in mobile planters could reduce concentrations of PM10 by more than 50% (Maher, Ahmed, Davison, Karloukovski, & Clarke, 2013).

In terms of scalability and identification of the parent system of the NbS, the key consideration is the spatial distribution of pollution sources and wind patterns. Roadside vegetation strips are linearly scalable alongside the road, provided the wind direction and velocity stays the same. Perpendicular to roads, PM10 concentrations can further decrease in urban forests, depending on wind speed and temperature, with one study showing around $5 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ decrease in concentration after every 50 meters in (Cavanagh, Zawar-Reza, & Wilson, 2009), but diminishing returns can be expected.

Table 8 summarizes the methodological obstacles that are relevant to measuring and evaluating air quality justice indicators.

Table 8: Notes on benchmark site selection for air quality justice indicators

Obstacle	Relevance for air quality justice
Parallel trends	Land use, traffic density, and traffic regulations may be confounders if they change.
Onset	Acute effect for grasses, shrubs, bushes, delayed onset for trees, depending on growth rate.
Spillover	No spillovers upwind, spillover up to 500 meters downwind from the source of pollution.
Dosage	No minimum dosage is set.
Scaling	Scaling is dependent on wind speed, wind direction, and distance from pollution source.
Context	Larger system is defined by urban-scale wind patterns and spatial layout of pollution sources.

In the case of **thermal justice**, the indicator pool comprises of metrics around the urban heat island effect, its causes, and effects. State indicators are variations of temperature (e.g., peak daily temperature, monthly mean of daily maximum temperature), there is one impact indicator on human thermal comfort (UTCI), and several driving force and pressure impacts related to urban design (e.g., albedo, soil sealing, surface temperature, land cover, shading). Treatments on thermal justice include evapotranspiration from vegetation, shading from trees, evaporation from water surfaces, decreasing soil sealing, and increasing surface reflectance. Indirectly, incentivization to reduce reliance on cars, and removing particulate matter from the air also reduces urban heat island effect. The size, shape of the NbS, and surrounding urban density, alongside the wind patterns created by street canyons may influence how well the cooling effect is transferred from the site to the surrounding neighborhood. If these conditions are unchanged, parallel trends can be assumed for UTCI.

In case of onset, all effects are acute, except for shading. For shading, the onset depends on the species of trees or crawlers planted. Minor changes in wind patterns may also be exhibited if large volumes of dense vegetation are grown, such as Miyawaki forests. To account for the effect, computational fluid dynamics simulations must be taken.

Spillover effects depend on the type of intervention. The most studied interventions are waterbodies and green areas. In case of green areas, the size, shape, and vegetation of the NbS influence the area of the cooling effect (Chang, Li, & Chang, 2007). What could be taken as a rule of thumb could be extracted from modelling studies, which provide a larger evidence pool accounting for variability. One such study suggests that after 100 meters of an urban cooling island, an increase of 1 C°, and after 200 meters, an increase of 2 C° is common, irrespective of shape (Ghosh & Das, 2018). Another study on modelled temperature gradients found the area of effect to be 300 meters for 100-metre-wide green area, and 400 meters for a 400-metre-wide one (Honjo & Takakura, 1990). Smaller, pocket parks in Israel were modelled for 100-metre-wide area of effect (Shashua-Bar & Hoffman, 2000). Given how most empirical evidence attribute no more than 2 C° cooling effect to green areas, these numbers could be taken as a rule-of-thumb boundary for spillover effects (Bowler, Buyung-Ali, Knight, & Pullin, 2010). In case of waterbodies, the number of studies is scarcer (Ghosh & Das, 2018), with one study in Beijing using empirical data identifying 5 C°/km temperature gradients in downtown areas, corresponding to 400 meters of range for a 2 C° drop (Sun, Chen, Chen, & Lü, 2012). However, all the above numbers may vary significantly depending on the wind patterns around the NbS – larger parks and reservoirs can generate a cooling effect several kilometers downwind (Theeuwes, Solcerová, & Steeneveld, 2013).

The dosage varies considerably for the purpose of the cooling effect. It can be stated that green roof and green wall interventions rarely carry over to urban scale heat island mitigation and should be studied for their impacts on building energy demands and comfort on users of the rooftop (Santamouris, 2014). One study found that for a dense urban core, one-third of the roofs should be vegetated, with multiple layers of vegetation to have a street-level cooling effect of 1 C° (Ng, Chen, Wang, & Yuan, 2012). When it comes to impact on buildings, even the most frugal extensive green roofs provide a better energy balance than cool roofs, but when the comfort of roof-users are in question, the presence of trees for shading is a necessity (K. J. Doick, Peace, & Hutchings, 2014). In terms of urban green spaces, size, shape, and vegetation matters. Parks and gardens smaller than 0,05 km² have negligible cooling impacts beyond their boundaries (K. Doick & Hutchings, 2013). and small green spaces in the range of 0,2-0,3 km² work efficiently only if they are clustered into a network, with distances less than 300 meters between them (Vidrih & Medved, 2013). Larger green areas have a sizeable effect on their surroundings. Furthermore, this cooling effect on the urban scale is largely attributed to increasing surface roughness rather than evapotranspiration, meaning multi-layered vegetation and forestation is preferable to planar interventions, such as grasslands (Zhao, Lee, Smith, & Oleson, 2014). In the case of waterbodies, size or clustering can be considered equally important for static waterbodies as for green spaces (Sun & Chen, 2012). However, exact size thresholds are not known. In the case of rivers, width of 30–40 meters appears to be a cutoff for significant impact on urban climate (Gunawardena, Wells, & Kershaw, 2017).

Scalability and identification of the larger system depends on the wind patterns defined mainly by the urban morphology, and to a lesser extent cross-shading produced by buildings. Urban cooling is highly scalable, but a network of smaller interventions, distributed according to wind patterns are more efficient than fewer, larger ones (Sun & Chen, 2012).

Table 9 summarizes the methodological obstacles that are relevant to measuring and evaluating thermal justice indicators.

Table 9: Notes on benchmark site selection for thermal justice indicators

Obstacle	Relevance for thermal justice
Parallel trends	Vegetation type, density, amount, size and shape of the area, and surface reflectance are typical variables NbS interventions change that also interact with land surface and air temperatures. If neither of these are included in the intervention, the others may be confounders, if they change. Furthermore, air quality, urban density, and urban morphology may be confounders, if they change.
Onset	Acute effect for grasses, shrubs, bushes, delayed onset for trees, depending on growth rate.
Spillover	For green areas of 100 meters width, 200 meters spillover. For green areas of 400 meters width, 400 meters spillover. For permanent waterbodies, 400 meters spillover. All spillovers to be multiplied downwind, with factors depending on local conditions.
Dosage	For urban-scale cooling, green walls and roofs produce effect at 33% coverage, parks, and gardens less than 0,05 km ² are negligible, parks less than 0.3 km ² must be clustered,
Scaling	Cooling interventions are scalable. Multiple smaller interventions in close proximity of less than 300 meters, designed according to wind patterns are desirable.
Context	The larger system is defined by the urban morphology and density, and wind patterns. Introducing surface roughness (green spaces) and enabling turbulent wind flow in dense inner cities have a higher impact. The effects of several smaller green and blue spaces in proximity (<300 meters) can be aggregated, thus infilling interventions are more impactful.

Spatial justice indicators are concerned with the spatial distribution of amenities and disamenities and their coincidence with the social composition of the area. The set of indicators can be grouped according to a diagnostic chain starting from the high-level objective of providing high-quality, attractive, green spaces for all:

1. Are there enough green spaces per population?
2. Are green spaces equally accessible, regardless of where someone lives?
3. Are green spaces equally accessible, regardless of someone's abilities?
4. Are green spaces used frequently?
5. Do the green spaces offer adequate amenities for all?
6. Do people perceive that green spaces offer adequate amenities for all?

This diagnostic chain is supplemented by indicators describing the mobile network, measuring sustainable modes of transport and their support by the infrastructure, as well as a few indicators on housing costs and building stock renewal, linked to green gentrification. The treatments to improve on these areas include the strategic placement of green spaces in areas where they are lacking, improving the quality and accessibility of existing ones, widening the range of amenities provided, and the co-development of pedestrian and bicycle infrastructures with urban greening. Important contextual variables are socioeconomic descriptors of the population in the catchment area of the intervention or benchmark site. Both the people living in the neighborhood, and those engaging with the NbS can be described by economic status, income, wealth, age, gender, marital and family status, place of origin, ethnicity, whether they belong to any known or latent vulnerable groups. Since these are unmeasured by indicators, they should remain stable throughout monitoring. Similarly, changes in the urban fabric, mobile infrastructural developments, and property developments in the catchment area may corrupt the results. Other latent factors influencing modal choice and choice of recreation, such as perceived and measured safety, outdoor comfort, cultural and normative drivers of behavior should be stable.

The onset of interventions is technically acute, since after construction, all amenities offered by the NbS are available for use. However, a small allowance can be attributed to the rate of people finding out about the new development, turning out to use the amenities for the first time, and for a new routine to settle. Although there isn't a specific rule-of-thumb period for habit formation, it's often the case that several months encompass the time required for most individuals who had no prior engagement with that habit (Buyalskaya et al., 2023). We recommend a 6-month allowance, not considering the impact of weather, in which case, 1 year is more appropriate. Since most of the indicators are spatially explicit, that is, they prescribe appropriate distances from the intervention for the performance to be counted, spillover is not relevant to be discussed here. In general, the catchment of the intervention can be considered as the area of spillover effects, which is determined by thresholds in acceptable, walkable distances to the intervention (National Affordable Homes Agency, 2007). For public parks in general, this is 1000 meters, but for playgrounds, 500 meters (Salom & Tamm, 2020). Such spillover effects cannot be attributed to NbS that are not open to the public, such as private green roofs.

In terms of dosage, there are no prescriptions, since acupunctural treatments – such as pocket parks – can elicit a response – such as increase in visitor count or social interactions (J. Dong, Guo, Guo, Guo, & Zhang, 2023)

Scaling of the projects can be understood in two ways. First, by increasing the size of the NbS, the population covered in its catchment area increases, linearly based on the perimeter. However, this also depends on what constitutes the NbS that responds to spatial injustices. A park alone may scale linearly if the proximity of green spaces in general is the target performance, but for proximity to amenities or services, only increasing their number could be counted, and drawing the catchments would be point-based rather than polygon-

based. Second, increasing the size of the NbS allows stocking it with more space-extensive, better sheltered, better-equipped, or simply more amenities and services which could respond to the needs of a larger section of the population. As such, scalability should be defined case-by-case, depending on the specific socio-spatial needs the NbS treats.

This also applies to the identification of the larger system the NbS belongs to. For example, NbS that encourage sustainable modes of transport, should be viewed as a more spatially explicit mobile network. NbS that create opportunities for expression of cultural identity, should be considered as part of the local cultural heritage, languages, symbols, habits, and their manifestations in symbols in-situ. These might be difficult to outline, requiring urban anthropological methods such as urban songlines that map out how discourses relate to movements across space (Marling, 2012). For social cohesion, the larger system is more linked to routines and habits of different social groups, as their social interactions increase social capital, eventually leading to a shared understanding of values and cooperation (Peters, Elands, & Buijs, 2010). For better access to health benefits, linked to spending more time outdoors can only be considered in the context of other social determinants of cardiovascular health, including structural determinants, such as status, access to healthcare, education, income; social risks, such as food security, housing; social context, such as the social environment; and lived experiences, such as depression, perceptions of the environment.

Table 10 summarizes the methodological obstacles that are relevant to measuring and evaluating spatial justice indicators.

Table 10: Notes on benchmark site selection for spatial justice indicators

Obstacle	Relevance for spatial justice
Parallel trends	Changes in socioeconomic composition in the catchment area, changes in the urban fabric, mobile and social infrastructural developments, and trends in the local housing market are variables to be considered for parallel trends.
Onset	Interventions are immediate, but delayed onset of one year is recommended to account for routine change.
Spillover	Spillover tied to the catchment of the intervention. For parks, 1000 meters, for child recreation, 500 meters can be used as a simplification.
Dosage	No minimum dosage.
Scaling	Scalability depends on the social needs treated by the NbS.
Context	The larger system is defined by the social needs treated by the NbS.

The non-human side and foundational services of NbS are treated under the aegis of **FFH justice**. This area is centered around fitness and composition of species, measured by a set of impact indicators, some of which count species directly (e.g., number of native species, number of invasive species), others referring to biodiversity (e.g., Shannon index of species). State indicators focus on habitat size, proportions to the urbanized area and habitat connectivity, both structural and functional. Pressures are not represented, as they stem

from human activities degrading ecosystems, which are not in the scope of monitoring single NbS. Pro-environmental identity, attitudes, and citizen awareness could be considered driving force indicators. Finally, responses include biodiversity conversation, policies informed by the NbS beyond, but linked to the NbS, and non-human representation, FFH-inclusive design, and knowledge provision linked to the creation of the NbS itself.

The larger system and thus the parallel trends assumption is pegged to variables influencing the ecological health of the city. From a land-use perspective, this is well described by the state indicators. Green areas, protected areas, changes in land-use are good proxies to measure how constrained various species are in terms of resources, space, environmental conditions, human disturbance. However, it is crucial not only to examine land-use changes in the vicinity of the treatment and benchmark sites, but also considering the larger networks that either (1) provide mobility for species to reach shelters or acquire resources (such as a grassland leading to a pond, which could be cut by a road), (2) transmit and distribute resources (such as rivers), (3) transmit and distribute environmental stressors (such as new industrial production upwind from the site). Especially connectivity to natural environments should be inspected, as the ecological benefits of NbS in urban green infrastructure will always be secondary to that of conservation of nature (Braaker, Ghazoul, Obrist, & Moretti, 2014) – meaning a change in the connection to a natural area will overshadow the impact of the NbS. What makes matters more complicated is that urban green infrastructure has targeted benefits to different species, with more varied interactions of the urban environment and the species, especially in the case of invertebrates. As a minimum, area, height, and pH are important variables to establish parallel trends, given their limiting role in taxa most associated with urban NbS (Filazzola, Shrestha, & MacIvor, 2019).

Regarding onset, it is important to know that low-maintenance, semi-wild habitats go through a series of succession periods, and different ecosystems have different times needed to mature. This study followed changes in the rooftop vegetation for 4 years before it could hypothetically provide suitable environment for ground-nesting birds (Baumann & Kasten, 2010). Another one focused on increasing plant diversity using nucleation techniques and recorded a hike in the number of genera around 240–250 days (Castelli, Silva, & Dunning, 2021). On the other hand, authors of a meta-analysis on the impacts of green infrastructure on biodiversity noted that projects younger than 10 years are not mature enough to deliver their full potential (Filazzola et al., 2019).

Scalability and spillover effects are two aspects of FFH impacts where it is beyond the scope of this document to provide blanket recommendations. This is due to biocomplexity, that is the “nonlinear or chaotic dynamics, unpredictable behavior and interactions that span multiple levels of biological organization or spatiotemporal scales” (Cottingham, 2002), which contributes to the specificity of FFH spreading and the reliance on a scale of data simply not available for most cities. There is an interaction among social, physical, biological processes shaping ecological structures and functions (Michener et al., 2001) and thus the

way acupunctural interventions spill over or scale up. Each project site would need to describe processes within the ecological patch, interactions between patches, boundary regulation, crosspatch regulation, and functional patch dynamics, as well as historic influences to make assumptions on how FFH impacts are transmitted or how they scale (Cadenasso, Pickett, & Grove, 2006). Once these dynamics are cleared, species-specific dispersal studies can be relied on to specify spillover effects and scalability. One study provided evidence for spillover of plant species decaying up to 50 meters from grassland ecosystems (Sperry et al., 2019). Another study found spillover at 30% of the diameter of the patch, however, only when the patches were connected (Brudvig, Damschen, Tewksbury, Haddad, & Levey, 2009). In the case of animals, dispersal varies by animal mobility. Marine dispersal is typically high, in the several hundreds of meters for macroalgae and around 100 km for fish (Kinlan & Gaines, 2003). Ground arthropods in this study on the other hand, may only disperse up to 20 meters (Schneider, Krauss, Boetzi, Fritze, & Steffan-Dewenter, 2016). Most studies have been done on birds, for example this study, where the spillover effect could reach as far as 500 meters, depending on the built-up density (Andersson, Haase, Scheuer, & Wellmann, 2020). However, bird dispersals also have a time dimension as populations need to grow, making its impact negligible in the first decade, and steadily increasing afterwards (Cocco, Kervinio, & Mouysset, 2023). Furthermore, in an urban context, the significance of barriers, such as roads, impervious surfaces, and buildings are more severe to less mobile species, therefore any hope for dispersal, thus upscaling is bound to patch connectivity.

Dosage in case of FFH also cannot be standardized. Although disputed (Guderyahn, Smithers, & Mims, 2016), one study suggests that a forest patch of 200 ha is required for northern red-legged frogs (Mathias, 2008), which does not exist in most cities. On the other end of the spectrum, a meta-analysis found that small pollinator gardens around 500 m² could be effective in restoring pollinator species (Donkersley, Witchalls, Bloom, & Crowder, 2023). Dosage also depends on what we consider to be our target, that is, whether we are baselining (comparing to an unchanged current state) with our intervention or benchmarking (comparing to an unchanged desired state). Multiple studies have advocated for using a “natural template”, that is to find a proxy natural habitat that resembles what the NbS could be, rather than what a similar urban control site is (Lundholm, 2006; Tonietto, Fant, Ascher, Ellis, & Larkin, 2011).

Table 11 summarizes the methodological obstacles that are relevant to measuring and evaluating FFH justice indicators.

Table 11: Notes on benchmark site selection for FFH justice indicators

Obstacle	Relevance for FFH justice
Parallel trends	Land-use and land-use changes in the larger ecological network the site belongs to, patch area, soil, and groundwater pH, and building heights should be considered when establishing parallel trends.

Onset	Depends on targeted taxa, plant diversity can be measured 1 year after the intervention, more complex biodiversity and ecological functions should be assessed after 5 and 10 years.
Spillover	Local social, physical, biological dynamics of ecological patch networks should be described before assessing spillover. Subsequently, estimations can rely on dispersal studies in the taxa of interest.
Dosage	Depends on targeted taxa and local conditions.
Scaling	Local social, physical, biological dynamics of ecological patch networks should be described before assessing scalability. Subsequently, estimations can rely on dispersal studies in the taxa of interest.
Context	The larger system is defined by the ecological patch network, especially the nearest wild or semi-wild patch, in different ways for different taxa.

The general area of **carbon justice** covers a retributive component, focusing on responsibility sharing proportional to the willful contributions to GHG emissions, and a distributive component, focusing on protecting those bearing the brunt of the negative impacts of climate change. GHG emissions associated with urban living are the key state indicators, one for building energy, another for transportation related emissions. Related pressure indicators can also serve as response indicators, as urban planning and development has an influence over these, such as walkability, bicycle infrastructure, population density, and bicycle infrastructural coverage. Other response indicators focus on the ways NbS directly and indirectly mitigate climate change, (1) by sequestering carbon, (2) by reducing building thermic energy demands, (3) by incentivizing bicycle use. A final group of indicators are ancillary metrics to assert willful contributions, such as land ownership, building age, household income. The cities in this project tend to put larger emphasis on response, and pressure–response indicators.

Parallel trends can be assumed from the get-go in case of carbon sequestration, since the carbon storage is derived from above and below-ground biomass, which is part of the treatment. In the case of building energy-related interactions, the picture is more complex, as other interventions influence energy demand (Grubler et al., 2018). Boundary conditions, such as microclimate can be influenced by hyperlocal wind patterns due to built-up density and urban shape, or outdoor developments changing soil sealing, apart from the NbS interventions. Building envelope interventions can reduce energy transmissions between inside and outside. Indoor interventions, including changes in the secondary systems, occupant presence and actions can significantly alter the energy use profile of the building. This in turn makes socioeconomic variables also relevant, such as age, income, level of education (Mata et al., 2021). Assuming parallel trends is even more complicated for incentivizing bicycle usage. According to a review of reviews, transport mode choice includes social factors (e.g., subjective norms, peer preferences), habits, individual factors (e.g., demographic trends, beliefs, attitudes), price and time elasticities (i.e., comparative costs and time costs), and infrastructural factors (e.g., walkability, street design, network coverage) (Javaid, Creutzig, & Bamberg, 2020). To assume parallel trends is to assume all other factors are either measured, or unchanging.

Onset in the case of building energy impacts should not be a factor, as a life-cycle approach is recommended for carbon accounting, making the final metric, global warming potential, time independent (adopting a 100-year horizon) (Brandão et al., 2013). As for carbon sequestration, the time profile of carbon stored varies by species, but typically follows a function with diminishing returns, characterized by a steady growth period, followed by a plateau (Newell & Stavins, 2000). In case of sequestration, metrics are also time independent, but there is a difference between ton-year approaches and dynamic life-cycle assessments, which account for an uneven temporal profile and different scenarios for what happens to the carbon sink beyond the assessment period (Levasseur, Lesage, Margni, Brandão, & Samson, 2012). In the case of transport mode choice, the habit change time described for spatial justice can be adopted. One additional consideration must be given to tree growth – that is the impact of climate change. The higher concentration of atmospheric carbon increased average temperature, and incidence of climate hazards change tree growth rates, habitable zones for specific species, and increases the risk of their mortality due to an environmental hazard (Vacek, Vacek, & Cukor, 2023). When assessing carbon sequestration over time, climate risks must be considered.

Spillover effects are not relevant for carbon sequestration, nor for transport mode choice (granted the larger mobile network is considered). For building energy impacts, the cooling effects may influence boundary conditions for other buildings in the close vicinity of the intervention, resulting in lower cooling energy demands. To account for this spillover effect, the reader is referred to the thermal justice section of this chapter.

Because of the lack or simplicity of spillover effects, scaling is also a linear function. For sequestration, the number and species of trees can be related directly to the carbon stored. For transport mode change, the catchment of the intervention needs to be identified, and an increasing scale would yield a larger catchment, which, depending on population density, increases the rate of people switching mode. In case of building energy, scalability is linear horizontally, following the spillover pattern of the cooling effect of the NbS.

Similarly, the larger system depends on the intervention type. The mobility network assemblage, especially the pedestrian and bicycle networks are relevant for transport mode change interventions. An NbS filling an important network gap, connecting large potential cyclist stocks will yield a higher impact than the same design in a peripheral neighborhood. In the case of carbon sequestration, the system of interest is a spatiotemporal one. Here we are concerned with land-use and land-use changes. On the one hand, carbon sequestration can only be counted, if the carbon sinks are newly introduced, i.e., a carbon-consuming land-use changes to a carbon sink land-use. On the other hand, it is also important what happens to the carbon sink after it was introduced. If the sink is allowed to decompose, or a wildfire, or any other event destroys it, the stored carbon releases back into the atmosphere, meaning the storage was only temporary.

Table 12 summarizes the methodological obstacles that are relevant to measuring and evaluating carbon justice indicators.

Table 12: Notes on benchmark site selection for carbon justice indicators

Obstacle	Relevance for carbon justice
Parallel trends	Determinants of transport mode choice and building energy consumption need to be unchanged or measured to assume parallel trends, except for carbon sequestration.
Onset	A lifecycle approach of monitoring is recommended, except for transport mode change, where a delayed onset of one year is recommended to allow time for habit development.
Spillover	Only spillover is considered for the cooling effects of NbS on the microclimate, reducing cooling energy demand of buildings – see thermal justice spillover recommendations.
Dosage	No minimum dosage prescribed.
Scaling	Scalability follows biomass, catchment of mobility-related intervention, and spillover area of effect of cooling NbS, respectively.
Context	The larger system is defined by the mobile network, the temporal pattern of land-use changes and biomass-relevant events, and urban morphology and wind patterns, respectively.

Temporal justice is not treated separately, as the “onset” section of the other justice areas covers the specific methodological adjustments relevant for this justice area.

6.6 Assessing comparability

Having discussed the conceptual and empirical considerations underpinning causal evaluation of NbS strategies in Chapter 6.2, this section addresses a key methodological prerequisite for their implementation, namely, the identification of control (comparison) sites to link with the site of the implementation (the treatment). The term “site” refers to the areal unit over which comparability is sought. It may encompass a whole city or a particular site within a city. The following discussion refers to whole cities, but it is noted that the methodology can be readily scaled up or down.

Perfect comparability is, of course, not feasible in the real-world, but it can usually be approximated to a degree that is sufficient for credibly supporting causal methodologies such as DiD technique. The present aim is to demonstrate a matching methodology for generating a candidate list of control sites, from which one or several are selected for inclusion into an impact evaluation. The flowchart in Figure 25 illustrates the decisions, processes, and inputs/outputs that comprise the procedure. The decisions require some degree of expert discretion, while the processes are generally left to data-driven algorithms that are beyond the reach of users’ input. Code in Python and R has been written to implement the processes involved in site selection, including data extraction and the matching algorithm, with exemplary output presented below.

6.6.1 Data Preparation

Figure 25: Selection of control sites

Two decisions start the procedure, the first one pertaining to the initial list of cities to be considered as control sites. There are no strict criteria for which cities are included in this list, though prudence might suggest some limitations such as cities of a certain size and geographic proximity to the treatment site. The second decision pertains to the set of variables used to assess the degree of similarity between these cities and the treatment site. While the variables selected will vary depending on the outcome in question, a suite of core variables is posited that cover socioeconomic features and infrastructure, which, by virtue of their correlation with environmental outcomes, are assumed to be of general relevance to NbS interventions. These variables are presented in Table 13. The list may be extended (or abridged) according to the particularities of the evaluation.

Table 13: Description of constructed measures of comparability

Measure	Description
Population size	Absolute number of people per city
City size	Absolute city size measured in square kilometer
Relative local GDP	Local GDP per capita on the city-level adjusted by the average real GDP per capita of the European Union (EU-28 in 2015) ³
Relative number of education opportunities	Number of education buildings (e.g., schools, universities) relative to the absolute number of people
Relative number of tourist attractions	Number of tourist attractions (e.g., galleries) relative to the absolute number of people
Relative number of access points to public transport	Number of access points to the public transport network (e.g., subway entrances, bus stops) relative to the absolute number of people
Relative length of the street network	Length of the street network (measured in kilometer) relative to the city size
Relative length of the railroad network	Length of the railroad network (measured in kilometer) relative to the city size
Relative area covered by water bodies	Area covered by water bodies (e.g., rivers, lakes) relative to the city size
Relative area covered by green space	Area covered by green space (e.g., parks, gardens) relative to the city size

Most of these measures are constructed in relative terms (e.g., relative to the city's population or size) to make the variables comparable across space. Without this adjustment, it is likely to be impossible to find a comparison group outside one's own city. For example, almost all large cities have a more extensive road network than smaller cities, which would make it difficult to compare a large city with a small one.

The following briefly describes data sources used to assemble the variables. Note that not all cities necessarily have all the characteristics described below. For example, for public transport, not all cities have a subway network. Also, all data presented are based on 2020 information, except for population data, which is based on 2018 information, and GDP, which is based on 2015 data.

Administrative boundaries

For the purpose of this discussion, all considerations are made at the city level. Therefore, well-defined city boundaries are central to the matching strategy. Open Street Map (OSM) data are used to extract the boundaries of all considered cities using the "admin level" tag.

³ The number of real GDP of the European Union (EU-28) in 2015 is provided by Eurostat (2023).

One exception is Paris, where the OSM data is incomplete. Here, information on administrative boundaries from the European Environmental Agency (EEA) fills the gap (EEA, 2017).

Population data

The population data are given as a grid dataset (as 1x1 km grid cells) for 2018 by Eurostat, (2021). The information is aggregated to the total population of the city.

GDP data

Similar to the population data, the GDP data are given as a grid data set by (Kummu, Taka, & Guillaume, 2018). Originally given at a resolution of 30 arc seconds, which is already close to a 1x1 km size, the GDP data are transformed to the INSPIRE grid definition of 1x1 km. The same definition is used for the population data.

Education opportunities

To calculate the relative number of educational opportunities, the following information is extracted from OSM: the locations of colleges, universities, kindergartens, schools, and libraries. All these locations are point data of buildings, not institutions. This means, for example, that multiple universities are listed, even though a city may have only one university. Note that this measure does not represent local educational attainment (such as literacy rates or the proportion with at least a high school education). It represents the opportunity to access education, assuming that more accessible places relative to population size lead to higher levels of education.

Tourist attractions

The tourist attractions capture the appeal of a city. Museums, historical sites, and galleries are included among these. As with all the OSM information used here, this list may not be complete, but it should reflect the most important categories. Furthermore, similar to the education data, this information is in the form of point data, signifying that it pertains to individual buildings rather than institutions.

Public transportation network

Another key indicator for the matching process is the availability of public transport access points. These access points are defined as bus stops, tram stops, subway station entrances, and train stations in general. The point locations of these stops are related to the total population at the city level during the matching strategy.

Street network

In addition to the public transport network, we also capture individual traffic using information from the local road network. We extract the following five attributes from OSM:

freeway, arterial, primary, secondary, and tertiary roads. This list represents the most important routes within the city and represents the connectivity within the city.

Railroad network

In addition to public transit and roads, railways are an important component of urban information. Therefore, the OSM tags light rail, railroad, subway, and tram tracks are downloaded. Note that these railroads are limited to passenger transportation. Freight railways are not included.

Water bodies

Unlike the previously used information, the information on water bodies is given as polygons. These polygons are transformed into a measure of the area covered by water bodies relative to the size of the city. The focus is on the features lakes, oxbows, rivers, streams, and canals to capture urban water sources.

Green space

Similar to water bodies, green areas are extracted as polygons. Parks, gardens, and nature reserves are defined as such locations.

6.6.2 Matching algorithm

The above variables are assembled in a database that records their values for each city. This database is then inputted into a matching procedure that loops through comparisons of the treated city with the control cities for each of the variables. Users' input is required at this juncture regarding the threshold at which a match is found. For example, a matching threshold of 20% means that if the treated city's measure falls within $\pm 20\%$ of the control city's measure, then both cities are matched for that particular variable. Different thresholds can be assigned to different variables. While a lower threshold ensures a higher degree of similarity, it limits the number of cities that meet the criterion. Conversely, a higher threshold results in a lower similarity, but increases the number that meets the criterion. This trade-off can be calibrated based on the methodological requirements of the impact evaluation in data analysis phase. In addition to the matching threshold, decisions on constraints may be required, one being to exclude the scenario of self-matching. Thus, a city cannot be matched to itself as a comparison group.

This process results in a preliminary subset of cities that fulfil the individual matching criteria. This subset could potentially be inputted directly into the impact evaluation. Alternatively, a process of further filtering may be deemed necessary. For the application of DiD, this may involve selecting a single control site based on the highest number of characteristics that meet the matching threshold. For the application of methods that require several control sites, such as the synthetic control method discussed in Chapter 6.8 below, it may involve the selection of multiple sites based on some decision rule. For example, under the maximum rule, the highest number of matches that result from the

matching algorithm is determined, and all comparisons reaching that number are included as control sites. Table 14 presents the output from applying the rule assuming Bolzano to be the treatment site and with 50 candidate control sites. In this instance, the maximum number of matching variables for Bolzano is determined to be 4, which three cities satisfy. Specifically, Bolzano is similar in size (population and area) to Leuven. It has a similar local GDP as Genoa and Antwerp in relation to the European GDP level. While only Antwerp has an almost identical number of access points to the public transport network, all three cities match in terms of tourist attractions and road network. Finally, Genoa and Bolzano have the same relative length of railways.

Table 14: Matching results for Bolzano

	Bolzano	Genova	Leuven	Antwerp
Population size	113,406	598,579	118,012	570,983
City size	52.3	240.8	57.6	204.6
Relative local GDP	77.1	89.3	118.9	87.3
Relative number of education opportunities	1.1	0.8	3.1	0.4
Relative number of access points to public transport	2.9	5.5	3.5	2.8
Relative number of tourist attractions	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.2
Relative length of the street network	2.2	2.1	2.5	2.5
Relative length of the railroad network	1.1	1.3	2.5	5.8
Relative area covered by water bodies	0.1	1.9	0.5	25.0
Relative area covered by green space	0.5	82.4	3.5	11.0

The match between Bolzano and, for example, Genoa in terms of the relative length of the road network (relative to the size of the city) can be illustrated on a map. Figure 26 shows the road network in both cities (Panel A for Bolzano and Panel B for Genoa) using data from OSM.

Figure 26: Matched street network in Bolzano and Genova.

Figure 27 shows another example of a matching characteristic - relative local GDP calculated from data in (Kummu et al., 2018). On this measure, Bolzano matches the city of Antwerp, with Bolzano having a local GDP measure of 77% relative to the European GDP and Antwerp having a value of 87% relative to the European value. Figure 27 shows the raw grid data that is used to construct the relative GDP measure. Note that the GDP is shown grouped into deciles for a better spatial comparison in the map. White spots indicate missing information that arises from unpopulated grids or missing data.

Figure 27: Matched local GDP in Bolzano and Antwerp

Ultimately, the filtered list of control sites – in this example three – is inputted into the impact evaluation. At this stage, the list may be subject to further processing. Depending on the methodological approach of the evaluation, this could involve calculating an average value

over the sites, or, as in the synthetic control approach, assigning weights to each site based on a data-drive algorithm.

6.7 Existing databases

Several databases and platforms are available that focus on NbS and related environmental topics, allowing users to share knowledge and experiences and combine and use data and information (Liu et al., 2021). For example, the ThinkNature platform, Oppla–EU Repository of NbS, NbS initiative, and Urban Nature Atlas are platforms on diverse environmental challenges directly addressed by NbS, while the European Environmental Agency (EEA), Data and Maps, EEA Climate-ADAPT, EU Joint Research Centre (JRC) Data Catalogue, Copernicus–Europe’s Eye on Earth, EU Biodiversity Information System, EU water information system, and EU forest information system are databases and platforms which have systematically collected different data, including data on specific natural hazards, that may not be directly related to NbS, but can be useful when designing and implementing NbS, for example, certain types of hazards can be mitigated or resolved by NbS.

Similar to NBS Databases, Databases on Ecosystem Services share rich data entries, which can operationalize NBS to its successful implementation. Several scholars link NBS to ecosystem services (ES) and natural capital (NC) concepts (Babí Almenar et al., 2021; Cohen-Shacham et al., 2016; European Commission & Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2015). Ecosystem Services are widely regarded as a wide array of benefits ecosystems and biodiversity provide to humanity (Turner et al., 2016). They are considered outputs (flows) derived from natural capital stocks (Dominati, Patterson, & Mackay, 2010). Almenar *et al.* (2021) cite experts, IUCN and European Commission, as well as other authors (Albert et al., 2019; Bush & Doyon, 2019) that claim NBS contain natural capital stocks or enhance the flow of ES. In terms of as part of urban planning strategies and interventions addressing different UC, NBS can help operationalize natural capital and ES (Potschin et al., 2015). Hence, in this section, databases tackling Ecosystem Services were included in the discussion of NBS databases.

In a study of decision support tools by Grêt-Regamey, Sirén, Brunner, & Weibel, (2017), to operationalize the ecosystem services concept, they found that many of the tools included in the review are scenario-based tools that allow a better understanding of the effects of different management practices on ES, such as thinning (forestry tools) or land-use change (spatial planning tools). Multi criteria decision analysis (MCDA) tools like Sim4Tree, HEUREKA, LANDIS, and MONSU are often used to assess different outcomes based on ES trade-offs. In some cases, tools provide information, such as web-platforms for querying ES maps and presenting ES case studies (EnviroAtlas, ESP-VT, ESLab, GecoServ, Interdisciplinary Decision Support Dashboard, and Our Ecosystem webmapping tool). There are also economic tools (Ecological-economic simulation model, CBA-typology, Benefit Transfer Toolkit, and Marxan) that focus on economics. It is also possible to describe some tools as

"model suites" (ARIES, InVEST, MIMES, Wetland Ecosystem Services Model Prototype) that provide multiple approaches to the problem to choose the best option.

In 2017, the NATURVATION project (NATure-based URban innoVATION, a Horizon 2020 research project) developed the [Urban Nature Atlas](#) (Figure 28). The Atlas was developed by the Central European University (CEU) in collaboration with the Ecologic Institute, and with further support provided by Durham University. The Atlas collected evidence on nature-based solutions to assist in the analysis of socioeconomics and innovation patterns associated with the implementation of urban nature-based solutions in Europe. Moreover, it aimed to provide an interactive online platform for showcasing and accessing inspiring nature-based solutions. Initial data collection for the Atlas was conducted from June to August 2017 and comprised a systematic survey of nature-based solutions in 100 European cities. After initial data collection, the content of the database was regularly maintained, and all previously existing entries were reviewed and updated as of July - November 2020.

The Urban Nature Atlas now presents nature-based solutions around the world as part of its global expansion. More than 1000 nature-based solution case studies are included in the database, including non-European case studies from cities featured in the NATURVATION project, as well as case studies from 70 other countries across all the different continents. The platform showcases multiple filters that range from key challenges, nature-based solutions, collection phrase, etc. A visual map will be available that includes hundreds of nature-based solutions, which are possible to analyze their project. In each project, it will be divided into consistent sections, namely overview, governance, financing, monitoring and assessment, and references.

Figure 28: Urban Nature Platform illustration. Ecologic Institute 2018: Urban Nature Atlas – NATURVATION. URL: <https://naturvation.eu/atlas>

According to Brander, Schägner, & De Groot (2022), the [Ecosystem Services Valuation Database](#) (ESVD) is the most important collection and synthesis of economics literature on ecosystem services. ESVD is a follow-up database to "The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity" (TEEB), which included over 1,300 data points from 267 case studies valuing ecosystem services across all biomes (Kumar, 2011). EEB has not been updated since 2010, so many gaps exist across biomes, ecosystems, and services. ESVD has become the successor of this database, and has been significantly expanded in recent years with funding from a variety of partners, including the UK's Department of Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (Defra), the Dutch Ministry of Agriculture, Nature, and Food Quality (LNV), and the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO). The ESVD was developed and hosted by the Foundation for Sustainable Development (FSD) and Brander Environmental

Economics (BEE) with support from the Ecosystem Services Partnership (ESP). Every place on Earth can easily access reliable and easily accessible information about the monetary value of ecosystem services. Stakeholders will be able to better integrate the 'full value' of ecosystem services into their planning, management, and decision-making processes with the help of this information. Further information on the ESVD can be found at <https://www.esvd.net>.

Figure 29: Ecosystem Services Valuation Database (ESVD) Validation Website. The filters on the side allow the user to specify the different valuations, based on multiple factors. The valuation can be toggled from map view or table view.

The goal of the ESVD is to gather information on economic welfare values related to ecosystem services measured in monetary terms. They provide recognizable information

that can be used to internalize Nature's importance in decision making by communicating in monetary units. Currently, the website contains 9500 value records from over 1100 studies distributed across all biomes, ecosystem services and geographical regions. Their repository of valuation studies contains over 2000 studies and the number is growing continuously so the number of value records in the ESVD will increase over time (Figure 29).

The valuations from the search query can be toggled between a table and a map format. There are several relevant variables provided in the table, including ecosystem type, ecosystem services, standardized values, beneficiaries, valuation methods, location information, and bibliographic information. Additionally, it indicates whether an external reviewer has reviewed a valuation. According to the coordinates of their point locations, the map depicts the valuations. The map shows basic information when hovering over a valuation pointer. The pointers open windows with more information on the valuation(s) of interest and ecosystem services. It should be noted that a map pointer may contain valuations from multiple studies and that it may reflect a small or large study area. A pointer can also refer to valuations on a local, national, multi-country, or global scale.

ESVD's monetary valuation is based on academic publications and reports. Therefore, the valuation information in these academic publications and reports is also included in the ESVD. Ecosystem types (biomes, ecozones, ecosystems) and ecosystem services are included in some valuations while others include multiple types. Multiple types and/or services underlying a monetary value **should always be reported together and should not be disaggregated** since it is not possible to attribute a specific part of the value to either one ecosystem type or ecosystem service.

6.8 Data-driven approaches

One of the main challenges is establishing a systematic way in the selection of comparison sites for causal impact evaluations that ensures sufficient similarity to the site of the intervention (the treatment). In the absence of this similarity, any difference in outcomes between the comparison and control sites may merely reflect differences in their characteristics, yielding a biased estimate of the treatment effect (Abadie, Diamond, & Hainmueller, 2015; Geddes, 2003; George & Bennett, 2005). Chapter 6.6 outlined a matching methodology for ensuring similarity along different dimensions by referencing a suite of socioeconomic and infrastructure variables that are potential predictors of the outcome. The data assembled in WP2, including the satellite imagery of land cover, the measurements of land surface temperature, and economic and demographic variables from the CiPeLs, provides a rich trove of information for the construction of these variables.

While the matching methodology serves to filter a set of candidate sites to use in a comparison, further narrowing may be needed that determines which of these candidates are ultimately selected for the analysis. In DiD setting, one possibility would be to select the single "best" site, perhaps based on the highest similarity between it and the treatment across the majority of the predictors. An alternative would be to construct an average value

across a subset of the sites to link with the treatment. But, aside from being potentially time-consuming and ad hoc, either of these approaches could suffer from a lack of transparency and formality. Moreover, they are subject to the possibility that the comparison sites selected are the ones that deliver the desired results. Even ruling out this threat, the final choice may be suboptimal because not all possible combinations of comparisons were considered.

The synthetic control method is an extension of the DiD framework that addresses these shortcomings (Abadie, Diamond, & Hainmueller, 2012; Abadie & Gardeazabal, 2003; Arkhangelsky, Athey, Hirshberg, Imbens, & Wager, 2021). Estimation proceeds by employing a data-driven algorithm that systematically chooses comparison sites using a weighting scheme. Implementation requires a time series of measurements on the outcome variable that straddles the date of the intervention from both the treated site and a set of control sites, resulting in a balanced panel of data. The algorithm selects a weighted average of all the potential comparison sites to create a synthetic control that closely matches the treatment site over the pre-treatment period. The synthetic control is then projected onto the post-treatment period, providing a counterfactual for the treated site that is used to estimate the causal effect of the intervention. The method has several advantages over DiD, one being that it does not require the parallel trends assumption. Moreover, it provides transparency by making explicit the relative contribution of each comparison site to the counterfactual synthetic control via the weights.

To further the intuition, let's consider a hypothetical city that undertakes a city-wide program to expand coverage of green roofs and green walls, following scientific evidence of improved urban air quality through PM_{2.5}-capture (Viecco et al., 2021). In 2022 the city undertakes a comparative study of the program's impact, assumed to have been completed in 2009. High-resolution data on PM_{2.5} are retrieved over a 30-year time interval from 25 other European cities that are deemed to be reasonably comparable based on the matching methodology of section 6.6. Figure 30 shows a plot of the temporal development PM_{2.5} concentrations from the cities before and after the intervention in 2009 using simulated data.⁴ Concentrations across most of the cities decreased over time. A shift in the rate of the decrease is vaguely discernible in the treated city as of 2009. The question is how to measure the magnitude of the shift. While any individual city or some combination of cities could potentially serve as a comparison case using DiD, which of these to select is not immediately evident. The synthetic control algorithm determines this selection by assigning weights to each comparison that vary between 0 and 1, resulting in a weighted synthetic counterpart. Figure 31 displays the trajectory of PM_{2.5} for this counterpart as well as for that of the treated city. The counterpart reasonably reproduces PM_{2.5} for the treated

⁴ While simulated data is used in this example, Van Donkelaar *et al.* (2021), have produced a panel data set on PM_{2.5} that is descriptively analyzed in D2.3.

city during the entire pre-treatment period from 1990 until 2009, as evidenced by the tight overlap of the trajectories. The estimate of the effect of the intervention is given by the difference between the treated city and its synthetic version following 2009, indicating a moderate reduction in PM2.5 concentrations.

Figure 30: Trajectories of PM2.5 in the treatment and comparison sites

Figure 31: Outcome of the synthetic control method

The synthetic control method is subjected to some limitations. One is that it is particularly suited to estimate the effects of aggregate interventions, that is, interventions that are implemented at an aggregate level affecting a small number of units (such as a countries, regions, cities, or sub-divisions therein). In principle, this could also include small-scale, localized interventions. Nevertheless, the method may not always be appropriate to the analysis of NbS, especially when it is difficult to find a suitable set of control sites that shares the particularities of the treatment site, even with the aid of a data driven algorithm. Relative to DiD, another limitation is the method's more stringent data requirements. At a minimum,

two control sites, but ideally more, are needed. A long pre-treatment observation period is also desirable for model training.

Returning to the conceptual simplicity of a before-after comparison, but undergirded by the rigor of machine-learning, Bayesian structural time series models provide an alternative data-driven method that may ameliorate some of these challenges (e.g., (Brodersen, Gallusser, Koehler, Remy, & Scott, 2015)). From a data perspective, a key advantage of this approach is that it only requires a time series of data taken from the treatment site. These models leverage Bayesian inference to incorporate prior knowledge and update the likelihood of different outcomes over time. They thereby serve to predict the counterfactual response that would have occurred had no intervention taken place. One of the advantages over DiD is to flexibly accommodate multiple sources of variation, including local trends, seasonality, and the time-varying influence of contemporaneous covariates. This allows researchers to better isolate the effects of the intervention from other factors that may influence the outcome. However, the effectiveness of Bayesian structural time series models depends on the quality and length of the available time series data, as well as the accuracy of the prior information used in the analysis. Incorrect prior information or short time series can lead to biased estimates of the causal effect.

7 CONCLUSIONS

Deliverable 3.1 describes the creation and application of tailored, indicator-based frameworks for measuring the performance of the NbS interventions while simultaneously addressing several socio-economic challenges with respect to preserving ecological space. The novelty of the framework is that, to the best of the authors' knowledge, it is the first attempt to combine the principles of sustainability, circularity, and ecological justice into a holistic tool that can assess and evaluate the progress in achieving specific goals and objectives toward sustainable and resilient cities through NbS.

The framework for each CiPeL in its present form has been created in consecutive steps with the active participation of city partners. An evaluation process for the framework has been developed and implemented using "concept criteria" (relevance to CUM, relevance to SDGs, and potential to measure EJ) as well as technical criteria (credibility, applicability, ability to track temporal changes). The frameworks are designed to be dynamic and adjusted to the CiPeLs' needs at each phase of the NbS life. The application of the frameworks can be expanded to plan and design future NbS interventions on the city/neighbourhood scale in a way that circularity is enhanced and, simultaneously, ecological justice is preserved. Furthermore, the frameworks can assist in the effective monitoring and evaluation of the NbS performance throughout their whole lifetime.

Lastly, it is important to consider that NbS monitoring is more than doing performance measurements before and after the intervention on the site itself. Ascertaining NbS performance is a form of causal analysis, which means the goal of monitoring is not to measure what is happening, but also to explain how it happened. To get a picture of the specific impact of an NbS, one or preferably more control (sites with similar baseline) and benchmark (sites with similar target) sites also need to be monitored. If suitable sites are also monitored, performance assessment can take the form of a difference-in-difference analysis. To select suitable sites, the monitoring team needs to ensure for all areas of performance that (1) all sites follow parallel trends, (2) timing of data collection takes into account the impact onset, (3) sites are distant enough to avoid spillover effects, but close enough to maximize latent similarity, (4) effective dosage and how it scales is considered when comparing sites of different sizes, (5) and the role of the sites in larger relevant systems are similar. To support this process, the document offers a process and the key variables to assess comparability, an algorithm to quantitatively synthesize these variables in a single comparability metric, using publicly available data, an overview of existing NbS databases to find benchmark sites, and a machine-learning method to generate synthetic control sites in the absence of a real control.

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APPENDIX I - RESULTING INDICATOR FRAMEWORKS

Bolzano CiPeL tailored framework

The indicators that have been selected for Bolzano are listed in Table 15.

Table 15: List of indicators for Bolzano.

ID	Indicator label
1.13	Citizen perception on air quality & predominant view
2.6.1	Hospital admissions due to high temperature during extreme heat events [In GA: reduced impact of heatwaves on human health]
2.8.1	Land Cover - Total vegetation cover
2.11	Surface reflectance - Albedo
3.1	Total carbon stored in vegetation [In GA: Tons of carbon removed (by vegetation type/area/socio-economic unit)]
3.9	Carbon emissions due to building cooling/heating
4.1.1	Green space accessibility (Proportion of the population living within a 300 m maximum linear distance to the boundary of urban green spaces of at least 0.5 ha in size.) [In GA: Generally improved GI accessibility, according to population density and walking distance & Improved access to greenery for physical and psychological well-being]
4.8	(Number of and) reason for visits an NBS area
4.1	Visual access to green space [In GA: Improved access to greenery for physical and psychological well-being]
5.15	Extent of habitat for native pollinator species [In GA: Increased number of native species such as pollinating insects]
7.1.3	Linking social capital [In GA: Improved social cohesion, increased interaction density in neighborhood community and limited gentrification]

The indicator framework for Bolzano CiPeL is composed of 11 indicators. The distribution of indicators per challenge is shown in Table 16.

Table 16: Number of indicators selected per challenge for Bolzano CipeL.

Air quality	Thermal	Carbon	Spatial	FFH	Temporal	Social Justice & Cohesion	Economy & Employment
1	3	2	3	1	0	1	0

The selected indicators result in a framework with the following qualities (Figure 32):

Figure 32: Results of the criteria for the indicator framework of Bolzano

The framework has the potential to evaluate ecological justice, composed mostly of indicators that score 1, meaning that they have the potential to capture and reveal socio-ecological injustices if the indicator result is disaggregated considering spatial and/or socio-economic distribution (Figure 33).

Figure 33: Composition of framework regarding the indicators' potential to measure ecological justice.

Investigating further the CUM validity, there are indicators in the framework that can directly or indirectly link to the evaluation of four out of six aspects of CUM. The framework will not measure the aspects of "creation and distribution of added value and other outcomes of economic performance" nor "investing on green economy" (Figure 34).

Figure 34: Number of indicators that link to CUM validity criteria.

Regarding the relevance to the SDGs and sustainable development overall, the framework is composed of indicators that can link to progress in multiple SDGs, with the most prominent link to SDG 11 (Figure 35). The composition of the framework includes indicators that equally cover the two pillars of sustainable development, excluding indicators that link to the economy pillar (Figure 36).

Figure 35: Number of indicators that link to SDGs.

Figure 36: Distribution of indicators in the pillars of sustainable development.

Merano Cipe1 tailored framework

The indicators that have been selected for Bolzano are listed in Table 17.

Table 17: List of indicators for Merano

ID	Indicator label
2.1	Monthly mean value of daily maximum temperature (TXx)
2.2	Monthly mean value of daily minimum temperature (TNn)
2.3.1	Mean or Peak local daytime temperature (direct measurement) [In GA: Decrease in mean/peak local temperature (by vegetation type/area/socio-economic unit)]
2.4.1	Urban Heat Island (incidence)
2.12	Tree canopy cover index
4.4	Community garden area
4.12.2	New pedestrian and cycling paths [In GA: Increase in walking and cycling linked to interventions]
4.2	Level of outdoor physical activity (self reported) [In GA: Increased outdoor physical activity]
5.5	Number of native species [In GA: Increased number of native species such as pollinating insects]
5.13	Number of veteran trees per unit area [In GA: Habitat & species preservation such as historic trees]
5.19	Social learning (Policy learning) regarding ecosystems and their functions [In GA: Number of local/regional policies influenced through the project actions]
5.21	Citizens' awareness regarding urban nature and ecosystem services [Increased knowledge & awareness of citizens and decision-makers regarding climate-related benefits of green space, carbon storage & multifunctional NbS]
5.23	Positive environmental attitudes motivated by contact with NBS [Increased knowledge & awareness of citizens and decision-makers regarding climate-related benefits of green space, carbon storage & multifunctional NbS]
7.1.2	Bonding – quality of interactions within and between social groups [In GA: Improved social cohesion, increased interaction density in neighborhood community and limited gentrification]

The indicator framework for Merano CiPeL is composed of 14 indicators. The distribution of indicators per challenge is shown in Table 18.

Table 18: Number of indicators selected per challenge for Merano CiPeL.

Air quality	Thermal	Carbon	Spatial	FFH	Temporal	Social Justice & Cohesion	Economy & Employment
0	5	0	3	5	0	1	0

The selected indicators result in a framework with the following qualities (Figure 37):

Figure 37: Results of the criteria for the indicator framework of Merano

The framework has the potential to evaluate ecological justice, composed mostly of indicators that score 1, meaning that they have the potential to capture and reveal socio-ecological injustices if the indicator result is disaggregated considering spatial and/or socio-economic distribution (Figure 38).

Figure 38: Composition of framework regarding the indicators' potential to measure ecological justice.

Investigating further the CUM validity, there are indicators in the framework that can directly or indirectly link to the evaluation of most CUM criteria. The exception is the “creation and distribution of added value and other outcomes of economic performance”, which is not measured by the framework (Figure 39).

Figure 39: Number of indicators that link to CUM validity criteria.

Regarding the relevance to SDGs and sustainable development overall, the framework is composed of indicators that can link to progress in multiple SDGs, with the most prominent link to SDG 11 (Figure 40). The composition of the framework includes indicators that equally cover the two pillars of sustainable development, excluding indicators that link to the economy pillar (Figure 41).

Figure 40: Number of indicators that link to SDGs.

Figure 41: Distribution of indicators in the pillars of sustainable development.

Chania CiPeL tailored framework

The indicators that have been selected for Chania are listed in Table 19.

Table 19: List of indicators for Chania

ID	Indicator label
1.1	Number of days during which ambient air pollution concentrations in the proximity of the NBS (PM2.5, PM10, O3, NO2, SO2, CO and/or PAHs expressed as concentration of benzo[a]pyrene) exceeded threshold values during the preceeding 12 months [in GA: Reduced exposure to air pollution (by area/socio-economic unit)]
1.2	Proportion of population exposed to ambient air pollution (PM2.5, PM10, O3, NO2, SO2, CO and/or PAHs expressed as concentration of benzo[a]pyrene) in excess of threshold values during the preceding 12 months [in GA: Reduced exposure to air pollution (by area/socio-economic unit)]
1.3	European Air Quality Index [in GA: Reduced exposure to air pollution (by area/socio-economic unit)]
1.5.1	Concentration of particulate matter (PM10 and PM2.5), NO2, and O3 in ambient air
1.10	Leaf Area Index
1.13	Citizen perception on air quality & predominant view
2.1	Monthly mean value of daily maximum temperature (TXx)
2.2	Monthly mean value of daily minimum temperature (TNn)
2.3.1	Mean or Peak local daytime temperature (direct measurement) [In GA: Decrease in mean/peak local temperature (by vegetation type/area/socio-economic unit)]
2.4.1	Urban Heat Island (incidence)
2.5.1	Human comfort: Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) [In GA: Increased outdoor thermal comfort (by area/socio-economic unit)]
2.7	Land surface temperature
2.9.2	Soil sealing (share of impervious surfaces)

2.10	Daily temperature range
2.11	Surface reflectance - Albedo
3.1	Total carbon stored in vegetation [In GA: Tons of carbon removed (by vegetation type/area/socio-economic unit)]
3.10	Household size
3.11	Household income
3.13	Building age/construction year
3.14	Population density
4.1.1	Green space accessibility (Proportion of the population living within a 300 m maximum linear distance to the boundary of urban green spaces of at least 0.5 ha in size.) [In GA: Generally improved GI accessibility, according to population density and walking distance & Improved access to greenery for physical and psychological well-being]
4.1.2	Area easily accessible for people with disabilities [Improved access to greenery for physical and psychological well-being]
4.2.1	Share of green urban areas (proportion of all vegetated areas within the city boundaries in relation to the total area of the city)
4.8	(Number of and) reason for visits an NBS area
4.10	Visual access to green space [In GA: Improved access to greenery for physical and psychological well-being]
4.11.1	Satisfaction with green and blue spaces
5.1	Non human representation
5.2	Provision of a solid foundation of knowledge on ecosystems, biological processes, nonhuman species
5.3	FFH-inclusive design (Target species or habitats are selected at the earliest project stages)
5.21	Citizens' awareness regarding urban nature and ecosystem services [Increased knowledge & awareness of citizens and decision-makers regarding climate-related benefits of green space, carbon storage & multifunctional NbS]
6.1	Land use and land use change [in NbS Handbook: Land use change and green space configuration]
6.6	Neighbourhood age (usually determined by average building age and land use change)
7.4	Quantity and quality of social interaction [In GA: Improved social cohesion, increased interaction density in neighborhood community and limited gentrification]
8.2.1	Number of new jobs created
8.2.2	Number of new jobs in green sector
8.5	Initial costs of NbS implementation (Project's initial costs are those occurring during the design and construction phases)
8.6	Maintenance costs of NbS
8.14	Investments in NbS triggered by the project

The indicator framework for Chania CiPeL is composed of 38 indicators. The distribution of indicators per challenge is shown in Table 20.

Table 20: Number of indicators selected per challenge for Chania CipeL.

Air quality	Thermal	Carbon	Spatial	FFH	Temporal	Social Justice & Cohesion	Economy & Employment
6	9	5	6	4	2	1	5

The selected indicators result in a framework with the following qualities (Figure 42):

Figure 42: Results of the criteria for the indicator framework of Chania

The framework has the potential to evaluate ecological justice, composed mostly of indicators that score 1, meaning that they have the potential to capture and reveal socio-ecological injustices if the indicator result is disaggregated considering spatial and/or socio-economic distribution (Figure 43).

Figure 43: Composition of framework regarding the indicators' potential to measure ecological justice.

Investigating further the CUM validity, there are indicators in the framework that can directly or indirectly link to the evaluation of all aspects of CUM (Figure 44).

Figure 44: Number of indicators that link to CUM validity criteria.

Regarding the relevance to the SDGs and the sustainable development overall, the framework is composed of indicators that can link to progress in multiple SDGs, with the most prominent link to SDG 11 (Figure 45). The composition of the framework includes indicators from all three pillars of sustainable development, mainly focusing on societal and environmental indicators (Figure 46).

Figure 45: Number of indicators that link to SDGs.

Figure 46: Distribution of indicators in the pillars of sustainable development.

Gzira CiPeL tailored framework

The indicators that have been selected for Gzira are listed in Table 21.

Table 21: List of indicators for Gzira

ID	Indicator label
1.4.1	Removal of atmospheric pollutants by vegetation (leaves, stems and roots) [In GA: Reduced pollution fluxes per area & share of emissions captured (by vegetation/ area/socio-economic unit)]
1.4.2	Total particulate matter removed by NBS vegetation [In GA: Reduced pollution fluxes per area & share of emissions captured (by vegetation/ area/socio-economic unit)]
1.4.3	Modelled O3, SO2, NO2 and CO capture/ removal by vegetation [In GA: Reduced pollution fluxes per area & share of emissions captured (by vegetation/ area/socio-economic unit)]
1.5.1	Concentration of particulate matter (PM10 and PM2.5), NO2, and O3 in ambient air
1.5.2	Mean level of exposure to ambient air pollution [in GA: Reduced exposure to air pollution (by area/socio-economic unit)]
1.6	Concentration of particulate matter (PM2.5 and PM10) at respiration height (1.5m) along roadways and streets [in GA: Reduced exposure to air pollution (by area/socio-economic unit)]
1.10	Leaf Area Index
1.11	Distance from air pollution sources
1.13	Citizen perception on air quality & predominant view
2.3.1	Mean or Peak local daytime temperature (direct measurement) [In GA: Decrease in mean/peak local temperature (by vegetation type/area/socio-economic unit)]
2.3.2	Mean or Peak local daytime temperature (modelling) [In GA: Decrease in mean/peak local temperature (by vegetation type/area/socio-economic unit)]
2.4.1	Urban Heat Island (incidence)

2.7	Land surface temperature
4.10	Visual access to green space [In GA: Improved access to greenery for physical and psychological well-being]
4.11.1	Satisfaction with green and blue spaces
4.11.2	Perceived quality of urban blue-green spaces (accessibility, amenities, natural features, incivilities, and recreational facilities)
8.5	Initial costs of NbS implementation (Project's initial costs are those occurring during the design and construction phases)
8.6	Maintenance costs of NbS

The indicator framework for Czira CiPeL is composed of 18 indicators. The distribution of indicators per challenge is shown in Table 22.

Table 22: Number of indicators selected per challenge for Czira CipeL.

Air quality	Thermal	Carbon	Spatial	FFH	Temporal	Social Justice & Cohesion	Economy & Employment
9	4	0	3	0	0	0	2

The selected indicators result in a framework with the following qualities (Figure 47):

Figure 47: Results of the criteria for the indicator framework of Czira

The framework has the potential to evaluate ecological justice, composed mostly of indicators that score 1, meaning that they have the potential to capture and reveal socio-ecological injustices if the indicator result is disaggregated considering spatial and/or socio-economic distribution (Figure 48).

Figure 48: Composition of framework regarding the indicators' potential to measure ecological justice.

Investigating further the CUM validity, there are indicators in the framework that can directly or indirectly link to the evaluation of all aspects of CUM (Figure 49).

Figure 49: Number of indicators that link to CUM validity criteria.

Regarding the relevance to the SDGs and the sustainable development overall, the framework is composed of indicators that can link to progress in multiple SDGs, with the most prominent link to SDG 11 and SDG 3 (Figure 50). The composition of the framework includes indicators from all three pillars of sustainable development, mainly focusing on environmental indicators (Figure 51).

Figure 50: Number of indicators that link to SDGs.

Figure 51: Distribution of indicators in the pillars of sustainable development.

Leuven CiPeL tailored framework

The indicators that have been selected for Leuven are listed in Table 23

Table 23: List of indicators for Leuven.

ID	Indicator label
1.6	Concentration of particulate matter (PM2.5 and PM10) at respiration height (1.5m) along roadways and streets [in GA: Reduced exposure to air pollution (by area/socio-economic unit)]
2.3.1	Mean or Peak local daytime temperature (direct measurement) [In GA: Decrease in mean/peak local temperature (by vegetation type/area/socio-economic unit)]
2.5.3	THOM'S DISCOMFORT INDEX
2.8.1	Land Cover - Total vegetation cover

2.9.2	Soil sealing (share of impervious surfaces)
3.19	Percentage of motorised/bicycle/pedestrian traffic
4.10	Visual access to green space [In GA: Improved access to greenery for physical and psychological well-being]
4.11.1	Satisfaction with green and blue spaces
4.21	Measured infiltration rate and capacity [In GA: Enhanced water infiltration and decreased flood risk & Enhanced water regulation to combat drought]
4.22	Volume of rainwater removed from sewage system
4.23	% of space taken up by parked cars in the public domain
5.5	Number of native species [In GA: Increased number of native species such as pollinating insects]
5.6	Number of non-native species introduced
5.7	Number of invasive alien species
5.22	Green intelligence awareness [In GA: Increased knowledge and awareness of sustainable actions by citizens & businesses to move towards shared values]
7.1.1	Bridging – quality of interactions within and between social groups [In GA: Improved social cohesion, increased interaction density in neighbourhood community and limited gentrification]
7.1.2	Bonding – quality of interactions within and between social groups [In GA: Improved social cohesion, increased interaction density in neighbourhood community and limited gentrification]
7.1.3	Linking social capital [In GA: Improved social cohesion, increased interaction density in neighbourhood community and limited gentrification]
7.2.1	Trust within the community [In GA: Improved social cohesion, increased interaction density in neighbourhood community and limited gentrification]
7.2.3	Tolerance and respect
7.3	Perceived social interactions [In GA: Improved social cohesion, increased interaction density in neighborhood community and limited gentrification]
7.4	Quantity and quality of social interaction [In GA: Improved social cohesion, increased interaction density in neighbourhood community and limited gentrification]
8.10	Subsidies applied for private NBS measures

The indicator framework for Leuven CiPeL is composed of 21 indicators. The distribution of indicators per challenge is shown in Table 24.

Table 24: Number of indicators selected per challenge for Leuven CipeL.

Air quality	Thermal	Carbon	Spatial	FFH	Temporal	Social Justice & Cohesion	Economy & Employment
1	4	0	4	4	0	7	1

The selected indicators result in a framework with the following qualities (Figure 52):

Figure 52: Results of the criteria for the indicator framework of Leuven

The framework has the potential to evaluate ecological justice, composed mostly of indicators that score 1, meaning that they have the potential to capture and reveal socio-ecological injustices if the indicator result is disaggregated considering spatial and/or socio-economic distribution (Figure 53).

Figure 53: Composition of framework regarding the indicators' potential to measure ecological justice.

Investigating further the CUM validity, there are indicators in the framework that can directly or indirectly link to the evaluation of all aspects of CUM (Figure 54).

Figure 54: Number of indicators that link to CUM validity criteria.

Regarding the relevance to the SDGs and sustainable development overall, the framework is composed of indicators that can link to progress in multiple SDGs, with the most prominent link to SDG 11 (Figure 55). The composition of the framework includes indicators from all three pillars of sustainable development, mainly focusing on societal and environmental indicators (Figure 56).

Figure 55: Number of indicators that link to SDGs.

Figure 56: Distribution of indicators in the pillars of sustainable development.

Szombathely CipeL tailored framework

The indicators that have been selected for Szombathely are listed in Table 25.

Table 25: List of indicators for Szombathely

ID	Indicator label
1.1	Number of days during which ambient air pollution concentrations in the proximity of the NBS (PM2.5, PM10, O3, NO2, SO2, CO and/or PAHs expressed as concentration of benzo[a]pyrene) exceeded threshold values during the preceeding 12 months [in GA: Reduced exposure to air pollution (by area/socio-economic unit)]
1.3	European Air Quality Index [in GA: Reduced exposure to air pollution (by area/socio-economic unit)]
1.4.1	Removal of atmospheric pollutants by vegetation (leaves, stems and roots) [In GA: Reduced pollution fluxes per area & share of emissions captured (by vegetation/ area/socio-economic unit)]
1.7.1	Morbidity/Mortality due to poor air quality [Reduced impact of air pollution on human health]
1.10	Leaf Area Index
2.1	Monthly mean value of daily maximum temperature (TXx)
2.2	Monthly mean value of daily minimum temperature (TNn)
2.3.1	Mean or Peak local daytime temperature (direct measurement) [In GA: Decrease in mean/peak local temperature (by vegetation type/area/socio-economic unit)]
2.4.1	Urban Heat Island (incidence)
2.5.1	Human comfort: Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) [In GA: Increased outdoor thermal comfort (by area/socio-economic unit)]
2.7	Land surface temperature
2.8.2	Land Cover - Woody vegetation cover
2.8.3	Tree shade for local heat reduction
2.8.4	NDVI (normalized difference vegetation index)
2.9.2	Soil sealing (share of impervious surfaces)

2.10	Daily temperature range
2.11	Surface reflectance - Albedo
3.1	Total carbon stored in vegetation [In GA: Tons of carbon removed (by vegetation type/area/socio-economic unit)]
3.6	Urban tree inventory (age, species, stem size) This is not an indicator, Urban Tree Inventory will give data to calculate indicators
4.1.1	Green space accessibility (Proportion of the population living within a 300 m maximum linear distance to the boundary of urban green spaces of at least 0.5 ha in size.) [In GA: Generally improved GI accessibility, according to population density and walking distance & Improved access to greenery for physical and psychological well-being]
4.1.2	Area easily accessible for people with disabilities [Improved access to greenery for physical and psychological well-being]
4.6	Activities allowed in recreational areas
4.7	Number of visitors to recreational areas (recreational value)
4.8	(Number of and) reason for visits an NBS area
4.9	Frequency of use of green and blue spaces
4.11.1	Satisfaction with green and blue spaces
4.11.2	Perceived quality of urban blue-green spaces (accessibility, amenities, natural features, incivilities, and recreational facilities)
5.13	Number of veteran trees per unit area [In GA: Habitat & species preservation such as historic trees]
5.14	Area of habitats restored
5.19	Social learning (Policy learning) regarding ecosystems and their functions [In GA: Number of local/regional policies influenced through the project actions]
5.21	Citizens' awareness regarding urban nature and ecosystem services [Increased knowledge & awareness of citizens and decision-makers regarding climate-related benefits of green space, carbon storage & multifunctional NbS]
5.22	Green intelligence awareness [In GA: Increased knowledge and awareness of sustainable actions by citizens & businesses to move towards shared values]
5.23	Positive environmental attitudes motivated by contact with NBS [Increased knowledge & awareness of citizens and decision-makers regarding climate-related benefits of green space, carbon storage & multifunctional NbS]
7.1.1	Bridging - quality of interactions within and between social groups [In GA: Improved social cohesion, increased interaction density in neighborhood community and limited gentrification]
7.1.2	Bonding - quality of interactions within and between social groups [In GA: Improved social cohesion, increased interaction density in neighborhood community and limited gentrification]
7.1.3	Linking social capital [In GA: Improved social cohesion, increased interaction density in neighborhood community and limited gentrification]
7.2.1	Trust within the community [In GA: Improved social cohesion, increased interaction density in neighborhood community and limited gentrification]
7.2.3	Tolerance and respect
7.6	Perceived safety of neighborhood
8.5	Initial costs of NbS implementation (Project's initial costs are those occurring during the design and construction phases)
8.6	Maintenance costs of NbS
8.7	Avoided costs due to NbS implementation
8.8	Payback period for NbS

The indicator framework for Szombathely CiPeL is composed of 44 indicators. The distribution of indicators per challenge is shown in Table 26.

Table 26: Number of indicators selected per challenge for Szombathely CipeL.

Air quality	Thermal	Carbon	Spatial	FFH	Temporal	Social Justice & Cohesion	Economy & Employment
5	12	2	8	6	0	7	4

The selected indicators result in a framework with the following qualities (Figure 57):

Figure 57: Results of the criteria for the indicator framework of Szombathely

The framework has the potential to evaluate ecological justice, composed mostly of indicators that score 1, meaning that they have the potential to capture and reveal socio-ecological injustices if the indicator result is disaggregated considering spatial and/or socio-economic distribution (Figure 58).

Figure 58: Composition of framework regarding the indicators' potential to measure ecological justice.

Investigating further the CUM validity, there are indicators in the framework that can directly or indirectly link to the evaluation of all aspects of CUM (Figure 59).

Figure 59: Number of indicators that link to CUM validity criteria.

Regarding the relevance to the SDGs and sustainable development overall, the framework is composed of indicators that can link to progress in multiple SDGs, with the most prominent link to SDG 11 (Figure 60). The composition of the framework includes indicators from all three pillars of sustainable development, mainly focusing on societal and environmental indicators (Figure 61).

Figure 60: Number of indicators that link to SDGs.

Figure 61: Distribution of indicators in the pillars of sustainable development.

Munich CipeL tailored framework

The indicators that have been selected for Munich are listed in Table 27.

Table 27: List of indicators for Munich

ID	Indicator label
2.3.2	Mean or Peak local daytime temperature (modelling) [In GA: Decrease in mean/peak local temperature (by vegetation type/area/socio-economic unit)]
2.5.2	Human comfort: Physiological Equivalent Temperature (PET) [In GA: Increased outdoor thermal comfort (by area/socio-economic unit)]
4.1.1	Green space accessibility (Proportion of the population living within a 300 m maximum linear distance to the boundary of urban green spaces of at least 0.5 ha in size.) [In GA: Generally improved GI accessibility, according to population density and walking distance & Improved access to greenery for physical and psychological well-being]
4.1.2	Area easily accessible for people with disabilities [Improved access to greenery for physical and psychological well-being]
4.8	(Number of and) reason for visits an NBS area
4.11.1	Satisfaction with green and blue spaces
4.13	Sustainable transportation modes allowed [In GA: Improved sustainable mobility behaviour and reduced noise pollution]
4.14	Walkability [In GA: Generally improved GI accessibility, according to population density and walking distance & Increased connectivity in the city center]
5.3	FFH-inclusive design (Target species or habitats are selected at the earliest project stages)
5.16	Pollinator species presence [In GA: Increased number of native species such as pollinating insects]

5.21	Citizens' awareness regarding urban nature and ecosystem services [Increased knowledge & awareness of citizens and decision-makers regarding climate-related benefits of green space, carbon storage & multifunctional NbS]
5.23	Positive environmental attitudes motivated by contact with NBS [Increased knowledge & awareness of citizens and decision-makers regarding climate-related benefits of green space, carbon storage & multifunctional NbS]
7.1.1	Bridging – quality of interactions within and between social groups [In GA: Improved social cohesion, increased interaction density in neighborhood community and limited gentrification]
7.3	Perceived social interactions [In GA: Improved social cohesion, increased interaction density in neighborhood community and limited gentrification]
8.5	Initial costs of NbS implementation (Project's initial costs are those occurring during the design and construction phases)
8.6	Maintenance costs of NbS

The indicator framework for Chania CiPeL is composed of 16 indicators. The distribution of indicators per challenge is shown in Table 28.

Table 28: Number of indicators selected per challenge for Munich CiPeL.

Air quality	Thermal	Carbon	Spatial	FFH	Temporal	Social Justice & Cohesion	Economy & Employment
0	2	0	6	4	0	2	2

The selected indicators result in a framework with the following qualities (Figure 62):

Figure 62: Results of the criteria for the indicator framework of Munich

The framework has the potential to evaluate ecological justice, composed mostly of indicators that score 1, meaning that they have the potential to capture and reveal socio-ecological injustices if the indicator result is disaggregated considering spatial and/or socio-economic distribution (Figure 63).

Figure 63: Composition of framework regarding the indicators' potential to measure ecological justice.

Investigating further the CUM validity, there are indicators in the framework that can directly or indirectly link to the evaluation of all aspects of CUM (Figure 64).

Figure 64: Number of indicators that link to CUM validity criteria.

Regarding the relevance to the SDGs and sustainable development overall, the framework is composed of indicators that can link to progress in multiple SDGs, with the most prominent link to SDG 11 (Figure 65). The composition of the framework includes indicators from all three pillars of sustainable development, mainly focusing on societal indicators (Figure 66).

Figure 65: Number of indicators that link to SDGs.

Figure 66: Distribution of indicators in the pillars of sustainable development.

APPENDIX II – GROUPS OF STATE-OF-THE-ART INDICATORS FOR LOW-CARBON | HIGH AIR QUALITY NBS FUNCTIONS AND SERVICES

Definition: Air quality (in-) justice responds to the higher exposure to average values of air pollutants (e.g. NO2, O3, SO2, CO and PM10 and PM2.5) among different groups of the population and also takes into consideration procedural impacts on the distribution of an Air Quality Monitoring Network and potentially resulting blind spots.

No	Indicator	Units	TYPE (S, P, O)	SOURCE	JUSTICE INDICATOR	JUSTICE TYPE	Synergies with other indicators/challenges	SCALE APPLICABILITY								INDICATOR PROS & CONS		proposed method of indicator measurement/calculation	source and type of data	sensor based (yes/no/partially)	data collection frequency	data protection	CIPet																		
								SPATIAL SCALE				TEMPORAL SCALE				PROS	CONS						Bolzano	Merano	Ortisei	Sils	Siusi	Levico	Munich	Stonbach											
								pre-NBS	post-NBS	site	district	city	short	medium	long																										
1.1	Number of days during which ambient air pollution concentrations in the proximity of the NBS (PM2.5, PM10, O3, NO2, SO2, CO and/or PMHs expressed as concentration of benzo(a)pyrene) exceeded threshold values during the preceding 12 months [In GA: Reduced exposure to air pollution (by area/socio-economic unit)]	No of days	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, recommended indicator for air quality		distributional	Directly related to the European Air Quality Index indicator and the other indicators of the Air Quality group.								Accurate results with automated measurements	Some of the measurement systems can be expensive and require continual management and upkeep	measuring station; air quality monitoring should be conducted in close proximity to the NBS of interest and at an analogous reference site, details in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8	pollutant measurement data from municipalities and regional, national and European authorities	yes	Continuous measurements with hourly, daily, monthly, and yearly averages	n/a	x																			
1.2	Proportion of population exposed to ambient air pollution (PM2.5, PM10, O3, NO2, SO2, CO and/or PMHs expressed as concentration of benzo(a)pyrene) in excess of threshold values during the preceding 12 months [In GA: Reduced exposure to air pollution (by area/socio-economic unit)]	%	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, recommended indicator for air quality	disaggregation of data - population groups mostly affected (% of population groups)	distributional	Number of days during which air quality parameters exceed threshold values, European Air Quality Index and the other indicators of the Air Quality group.								Accurate results with automated measurements. Based on the reported monitoring data by Member States	Some of the measurement systems can be expensive and require continual management and upkeep; Methodological uncertainty, data uncertainty and rationale uncertainty	Information on cities is obtained from the Urban Audit (UA) data. The urban population considered is the total number of people represented by any of the urban monitoring stations in the 'core city' and, from 2016, the 'greater city' of the UA cities taking part in the calculations. Initially, stations in the EEA air-quality database are spatially joined with UA core and, from 2016, greater cities in a geographical information system in order to select those stations that fall within the boundaries of the cities included in the UA collection. The selected stations include station types classified as 'urban traffic', 'suburban traffic', 'urban background' and 'suburban background'. More details for the calculation methodology in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8	Air Quality e-Reporting (AQ e-Reporting) provided by European Commission (https://www.eea.europa.eu/ds_resolveuid/DAT-3-en) AirBase - The European air quality database provided by European Environment Agency (EEA) (https://www.eea.europa.eu/ds_resolveuid/DAT-3-en) Gisco - Urban Audit 2012 provided by Statistical Office of the European Union (Eurostat) (https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/external/gisco-urban-audit) City population provided by City Population (https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/external/city-population)	yes	annually	n/a		x																		
1.3	European Air Quality Index [In GA: Reduced exposure to air pollution (by area/socio-economic unit)]	Good, Fair, Moderate, Poor, Very Poor, Extremely Poor	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, recommended indicator for air quality	EACI per neighborhood, demographic data (population groups, residing in each neighborhood)	distributional	Number of days during which air quality parameters exceed threshold values and the other indicators of the Air Quality group.								Based on the reported monitoring data by Member States. Easy to visualise	Some of the measurement systems can be expensive and require continual management and upkeep	The index uses 'up-to-date' air quality data officially reported every hour by EEA member countries, complemented where necessary by modelled air quality data from the European Union's Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS). Additionally, can be complemented with local air quality data from equipments installed in NBS locations. Concentrations values for up to five key pollutants determine the index level that reflects air quality at each monitoring station. The index corresponds to the poorest level for any of five pollutants... More details for the calculation methodology in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8	pollutant measurement data from municipalities and regional, national and European authorities	yes	Continuous measurements with hourly, daily, monthly, and yearly averages	n/a																				
1.4.1	Removal of atmospheric pollutants by vegetation (leaves, stems and roots) [In GA: Reduced pollution fluxes per area & share of emissions captured (by vegetation)/ area/socio-economic unit]	kg/ha/day	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for air quality	demographic data: population groups around NBS	distributional									This method does not require field work.	Modelled method and specific software are required	Calculation formulas given in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8	Atmospheric pollutant concentration data from monitoring stations and tree cover data from (municipal) maps and models.	no	annually	n/a	x																			
1.4.2	Total particulate matter removed by NBS vegetation [In GA: Reduced pollution fluxes per area & share of emissions captured (by vegetation)/ area/socio-economic unit]	kg/ha/day	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for air quality	demographic data: population groups around NBS	distributional	Reduction of Pollutants								It allows to detect the abatement of PM at different particle size fraction.	The limit is that the survey is discrete and not continuously during the time.	PM deposited on the leaves will be studied by Scanning Electron Microscopy combined with Energy Dispersed X-Ray microanalysis, obtaining a quantitative characterisation of the deposited particles, as a function of their size and elemental composition. More details in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8	Leaf samples	no	Particulate matter abatement will be estimated twice during the project: at the NBS implementation and after 2 years	n/a		x																		
1.4.3	Modelled O3, SO2, NO2 and CO capture/removal by vegetation [In GA: Reduced pollution fluxes per area & share of emissions captured (by vegetation)/ area/socio-economic unit]	kg/ha/day	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for air quality	demographic data: population groups around NBS	distributional	Other indicators of the Air Quality group								Effective method for extensive analyses	Needs expert users and a lot of input data	The chemical transport model WRF-Chem (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration [NOAA], n.d.) or The 'Tree For model (USDA Forest Service, 2019) can also be applied to estimate the air pollutants removed by vegetation. (details in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8)	depending on model, details in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8	no	Before and after the NBS implementation	n/a		x																		
1.5.1	Concentration of particulate matter (PM10 and PM2.5, NO2, and O3 in ambient air)	µg/m3	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for air quality	spatial distribution of concentrations, population groups mostly affected (µg/m3 per area and per group)	distributional	Other indicators in the Air quality indicator group (Same as 1.5.2 when spatial distribution is mapped)								Accurate results with automated measurements	Some of the measurement systems can be expensive and require continual management and upkeep	Air pollution concentrations can be estimated based on measured and/or modelled concentrations in ambient air (O3, NOx, VOC, PM10 and PM2.5) near the NBS intervention area. Data can be retrieved from air quality monitoring stations or from measured values during experimental campaigns. Data can also be estimated by applying air quality models, such as the WRF-Chem model (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration [NOAA], n.d.), which estimates 3D concentration fields with an hourly resolution at the grid, neighbourhood or city scale. More details in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8	Pollutant measurement data	yes	Continuous measurements with hourly, daily, monthly, and yearly averages	n/a																				
1.5.2	Mean level of exposure to ambient air pollution [In GA: Reduced exposure to air pollution (by area/socio-economic unit)]	µg/m3	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for air quality	spatial distribution of concentrations, population groups mostly affected (µg/m3 per area and per group)	distributional	This KPI is useful to assess the level of population exposed to low air quality levels in the city and the importance of this challenge for the city. Further analysis could be developed using public health or hospital admission data to correlate the importance or green infrastructure on air quality levels.								PM monitoring device required.	Calculation of annual and monthly mean levels of NO2, O3, PM10 and PM2.5 at each station location. There are three main types of stations for city domains (excluding industrial sites that are no considered for this KPI): Road traffic, Urban background, Peri-urban background. According to this classification, average values can be obtained for road traffic areas, urban areas and peri-urban areas. Then, using a GIS software, a model of the city can be built that classifies all locations/streets/areas of the city in those categories. More details in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8	Air Quality monitoring stations network in major urban agglomerations. Measurements: Concentrations of NO2, O3 and airborne particulate matter are measured by recording PM mass per cubic meter of air (PM2.5 and PM10).	yes	Continuous monitoring in the selected points hourly.	n/a	x																				
1.6	Concentration of particulate matter (PM2.5 and PM10) at respiration height (1.5m) along roadways and streets [In GA: Reduced exposure to air pollution (by area/socio-economic unit)]	µg/m3	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for air quality	air quality experienced by bicyclists and pedestrians	distributional									This method requires the use of specialised equipment (PM monitoring device); Monitoring campaigns involve manual measurements, requiring personnel.	Measure air concentrations of PM2.5 and PM10 at defined sampling points at a height of 1.5 m above ground level and a range of linear distances from NBS street tree/green wall locations, both pre- and post-intervention. Compare these data to measurements taken at analogous locations on equivalent stretches of road without street-side NBS at similar times of day on the same dates. A portable photometric sampler designed to measure ambient PM2.5 and PM10 concentrations can be used to gather data on a non-continuous basis, i.e. during planned field monitoring campaigns. Data can be collected and stored on the device, then can be downloaded later to a PC. Compare the particulate matter (PM2.5 and PM10) values qualitatively and quantitatively for the periods before and after the interventions in the NBS and reference sections. More details in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8	Atmospheric PM2.5 and PM10 concentration data (in µg/m3) obtained at a height of 1.5 m above ground level using (a) portable monitoring device(s).	yes	each predetermined sampling location at a study site should be repeated sampled every 4 weeks for one year pre-intervention, and for at least two years following intervention.	n/a																					
1.7.1	Morbidity/Mortality due to poor air quality [Reduced impact of air pollution on human health]	No/y	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for air quality	disaggregation of data - population groups mostly affected (No/y per group)	distributional	Other indicators in the Air quality indicator group								The indicator is easy to define	The method needs corresponding air pollutant concentration, demographic and epidemiological input data	The general approach in health impact assessment is to use exposure-response functions, linking the concentration of pollutants to which the population is exposed to the number of health events occurring in that population. Details for calculation methodology in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8	i) involved pollutants and their air concentration levels, ii) health indicators analysed in terms of morbidity and mortality, iii) affected age groups, and iv) exposure time	yes		n/a																				
1.7.2	Years of life lost due to poor air quality [Reduced impact of air pollution on human health]	y	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for air quality	disaggregation of data - population groups mostly affected (y per group)	distributional	Other indicators in the Air quality indicator group								The indicator is easy to define	The method needs corresponding air pollutant concentration, demographic and epidemiological input data	The general approach in health impact assessment is to use exposure-response functions, linking the concentration of pollutants to which the population is exposed to the number of health events occurring in that population. Details for calculation methodology in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8	i) involved pollutants and their air concentration levels, ii) health indicators analysed in terms of morbidity and mortality, iii) affected age groups, and iv) exposure time	yes	Daily, weekly, monthly or annually	n/a																				
1.8	Avoided costs for air pollution control measures	euro	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for air quality	for the city	distributional											https://www.mdpi.com/2073-445X/10/9/788/html		no		n/a																				
1.9	Vegetation contribution to CO2 absorption [In GA: Tons of carbon removed (by vegetation type)/area/socio-economic unit]	kg/ha/y	O	D2.1 literature review	spatial mapping and population groups (kg/ha/y per area and per group)	distributional	Indicator related to carbon in-justices, recommended indicator in NBS evaluation handbook for climate resilience, included in the carbon (in-justices) list of indicators	see carbon injustice indicator 3.1			see carbon injustice indicator 3.1	see carbon injustice indicator 3.1	see carbon injustice indicator 3.1	no	see carbon injustice indicator 3.1	n/a																									
1.10	Leaf Area Index	dimensionless (D 10)	O	D2.1 literature review	spatial mapping (LAI per area)	distributional	Can be linked to Air pollutants removal by vegetation indicators (1.4.1, 1.4.2, 1.4.3)										https://academic.oup.com/jbr/article/54/392/2403/621920R10438141		no		n/a																				
1.11	Distance (of CIPet 7) from air pollution sources	km	O	D2.1 literature review	spatial mapping	distributional	can be linked to air pollution concentration indicators										https://www.mdpi.com/2072-4292/8/5/355/html	Maps	no		n/a																				
1.12	Location of street canyons	unitless	O	D2.1 literature review	spatial mapping	distributional	can be linked to air pollution concentration indicators											Maps	no		n/a																				
1.13	Citizen perception on air quality & predominant view		O	Indicator pre-selected in GA relevant to the expected IMPACT A. Increased evidence and awareness of the benefits of re-naturing cities indicators.	population groups	distributional											surveys	surveys: questionnaires?	no	Before and after NBS implementation	yes																				
1.14	Ambient pollen concentration	No	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for air quality	demographic data: population groups around NBS	distributional	Synergies with Distribution of public green space, Accessibility of urban green spaces, and Proportion of natural area, and Availability and equitable distribution of blue-green space indicators								The results are widely accepted and known to be consistent	The method of identifying and characterising trapped pollen and spores is time-consuming and requires considerable expertise	The volumetric, Hirst-type pollen and spore trap designed in 1952 remains one of the devices most commonly used for pollen and spore monitoring. More details in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8	Hirst-type pollen and spore trap, Pollen measurement data	yes	Continuous collection with a 24 h or a 7-day sampling period	n/a																				

Definition: Thermal justice refers to the reduction of the inequitable distribution of extreme heat conditions and related risks across different areas within the same city and the vulnerable population.

No	Indicator	Units	TYPE (S, P, O)	SOURCE	INDICATOR	JUSTICE TYPE	Synergies with other indicators	EVALUATION STAGE		SCALE APPLICABILITY				INDICATOR PROS/CONS		Proposed method of indicator measurement/calculation	sensor based (yes/no/partially)	data collection frequency	data protection	CPet									
								pre-NBS	post-NBS	site	district	city	short	medium	long					PROS	CONS	Bolzano	Merano	Chiana	Görs	Leuven	Munich	Szombathely	
2.1	Monthly mean value of daily maximum temperature (T _{max})	°C	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, recommended indicator for climate resilience, additional for natural and climate hazards	spatial mapping (depending on available sensor network), housing conditions	distributional	Indicators daily min temperature, and daily temperature range	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	Indicator together with the mean of daily minimum temperature can give an idea of the high temperature effects in urban comfort and human health.	Sensors: measuring instruments (measurement stations or manual instruments e.g., TESTO multi-function); thermography camera (e.g., FLIR). (details in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8)	yes	10min	n/a	x									
2.2	Monthly mean value of daily minimum temperature (T _{min})	°C	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, recommended indicator for climate resilience, additional for natural and climate hazards	spatial mapping (depending on available sensor network), housing conditions	distributional	Indicators daily max temperature, and daily temperature range	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	Indicator together with the mean of daily maximum temperature can give an idea of the high temperature effects in urban comfort and human health.	Sensors: measuring instruments (measurement stations or manual instruments e.g., TESTO multi-function); thermography camera (e.g., FLIR). (details in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8)	yes	10min	n/a	x									
2.3.1	Mean or Peak local daytime temperature (modeling) [In GA: Decrease in mean/peak local temperature (by vegetation type/area/socio-economic unit)]	°C	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for climate resilience	spatial distribution, (peak local of different neighborhoods), housing conditions	distributional	A prerequisite for Heatwave Risk and Urban Heat Island indicators, and a requirement for Depth to groundwater indicator	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	Straightforward assessment of ambient air temperature; Reliable in the long run	Ambient air temperature can be assessed through continuous monitoring of temperature, near the NBS intervention area, and calculation of mean and peak daytime temperature before and after NBS implementation (details in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8)	yes	Annually, at minimum, before and after NBS implementation	n/a	-1°C in adjacent streets							x		
2.3.2	Mean or Peak local daytime temperature (modeling) [In GA: Decrease in mean/peak local temperature (by vegetation type/area/socio-economic unit)]	°C	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for climate resilience	spatial distribution, (peak local of different neighborhoods), housing conditions	distributional	Contributes to Drought vulnerability indicator group and to Climate resilience strategy development indicator	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	Allows the calculation with an hourly resolution at the grid, neighborhood or city scale neighborhood	Difference in temperature can be assessed through application of a meteorological model such as the Weather Research and Forecasting model (WRF) [NCAR & UCAR, n.d.; NOAA, n.d.] (details in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8)	yes	Annually, at minimum, before and after NBS implementation	n/a	-1°C in adjacent streets							x		
2.4.1	Urban Heat Island (incidence)	°C	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for climate resilience & natural and climate hazards	spatial distribution, (UHI incidence per neighborhood-> population groups mostly affected), housing conditions	distributional	Assessed from Mean or peak daytime temperature indicator and connected with Heatwave Risk indicator	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	Fairly easy and straightforward assessment of temperature differences	1. Identify or install one or more meteorological (temperature) measurement stations within the built environment, and one measurement station outside the city that functions as a reference station. Alternatively, models can be used. 2. Compare the hourly average air temperature measurements of the urban measurement station(s) with the station outside the city (the reference station). 3. Look for the largest temperature difference (hourly average) between urban and countryside areas during the summer months. This temperature difference is an absolute measure of the UHI effect.	yes	Annually, at minimum before and after NBS implementation	n/a	x								x	
2.4.2	Urban Heat Risk Index (UHRI)		O	D3.1 literature review (https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/13549839.2018.1474861?scroll=top&needAccess=true)	spatial distribution, (UHRI incidence per neighborhood-> population groups mostly affected)	distributional	Urban land use indexes are used for its calculation	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	calculated from measures of land surface temperature, structural density, and vegetation abundance. Multilevel modelling examine statistical associations between urban heat, minority status, socioeconomic disadvantage, and segregation of racial/ethnic minority groups. (https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/13549839.2018.1474861?scroll=top&needAccess=true)	Remote sensing imagery, Census data (Variables representing socioeconomic status, minorities etc.)	no	before and after NBS implementation	n/a	we are very interested in receiving the outputs from the scientific partners									
2.5.1	Human comfort: Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) [In GA: Increased outdoor thermal comfort (by area/socio-economic unit)]	°C	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for climate resilience & natural and climate hazards	spatial distribution, (UTCI per neighborhood), disaggregation of data per population group (e.g., UTCI for elderly)	distributional	Direct relation to Heatwave incidence and Number of combined tropical nights and hot days indicators Similar to Physiological equivalent temperature (PET)	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	Mathematical expression of a person's thermal comfort in the outdoors. The output is expressed in easily understandable temperature units, e.g., °C	Universal Thermal Climate Index mathematical model (details described in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8)	yes	Frequency as desired	n/a	x							x		
2.5.2	Human comfort: Physiological Equivalent Temperature (PET) [In GA: Increased outdoor thermal comfort (by area/socio-economic unit)]	°C	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for climate resilience & natural and climate hazards	spatial distribution, (UTCI per neighborhood), disaggregation of data per population group (e.g., UTCI for elderly)	distributional	Directly related to incorporation of environmental design in buildings indicator	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	uses °C, which allows the results to be easily interpreted by urban or regional planners	PET calculation equations, High level of expertise required for the calculations (details described in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8)	yes	Annually, and before and after NBS implementation	n/a	x							x		
2.6.1	Hospital admissions due to high temperature during extreme heat events [In GA: reduced impact of heatwaves on human health]	No. per 100 000	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for HWB	disaggregated data per population group	distributional	Synergies with the Temperature indicators, Heatwave indicators and UHI indicators	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	Easy to measure	evaluated using public health data regarding daily emergency room admissions. These data can be used either to evaluate total emergency room admissions, or to assess hospital admissions for specific disease categories such as heat stroke, dehydration and cardiac arrest. Further disaggregation of data may include separation by population demographic.	Public health data regarding either total emergency room admissions or hospital admissions for specific disease categories. Population data.	partially	Before and after NBS implementation	n/a	x						x		
2.6.2	Heat related deaths/ heat related mortality [In GA: reduced impact of heatwaves on human health]	No. per 1 000 000 per year	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for HWB	disaggregated data per population group	distributional	Synergies with the Temperature indicators, Heatwave indicators and UHI indicators	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	robust evidence as to UHI being a strong predictor of death rates, especially for certain health conditions, like cardiovascular disease, respiratory disease, renal disorders, etc.	Heat-related Deaths: the annual rate for deaths classified by medical professionals as "heat-related" in a given country, based on death certificate records. Dividing the annual number of deaths by the country's population in that year, then multiplying by one million, will result in the death rates (per million people). Mortality is the number of deaths due to a disease during a specific time divided by the number of persons in that population at the beginning of the time period.	Quantitative: epidemiological data (Health Data Administration/Cities) Recommended variables: Discomfort Index, DI (i.e., Temperature-humidity index, THI) - combination of temperature and humidity that is a measure of the degree of discomfort experienced by an individual in warm weather (Temperature-humidity index)	partially	Before and after NBS implementation	n/a	x						x		
2.7	Land surface temperature	°C	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for climate resilience	spatial mapping per neighborhood	distributional	Directly related to Albedo, Rate of evaporation, and Occurrence of heat waves indicators	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	Earth observation methods allow for large-scale observations, Direct observation of the changes of the Earth's energy budget	Earth observation methods or Ground-based (in situ) methods (details described in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8)	no	Hourly, daily, weekly	n/a	we are very interested in receiving the outputs from the scientific partners									
2.8.1	Land Cover - Total vegetation cover	%	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for green space management	spatial mapping per neighborhood	distributional		*	*	*	*	*	*	*	Soil covered by assemblage of plant species and the ground, without specific reference to particular taxa, life forms, structure, spatial extent, or any other specific botanical or geographic characteristics: GIS/Project Data	no	n/a	n/a	x										
2.8.2	Land Cover - Woody vegetation cover	%	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for green space management	spatial mapping per neighborhood	distributional		*	*	*	*	*	*	*	Soil covered by trees, bushes and shrubs. GIS/Project Data	no	n/a	n/a	x										
2.8.3	Tree shade for local heat reduction	m2	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for climate resilience	spatial mapping per neighborhood	distributional	Strong synergies with Air temperature reduction and with HWB indicators in relation to heat stress. Reducing temperatures in a specific location could link to social cohesion and accessibility as people may be more likely to use a space. Where weather stations are utilised, there are synergies in relation to capturing additional environmental parameters of relevance for other indicators (e.g., total rain fall for stormwater management indicators).	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	direct measurement in the field can provide greater confidence than microclimate simulations	Robustness of evidence depends upon the level of precision of the equipment, the spatial design of the monitoring and the duration of temperature recording. Can be hard to accurately scale-up direct local measurements to the whole city. To accurately simulate the thermal performance benefits that trees provide, it is necessary to account for growth and phenological changes in tree shade amount and quality and the influence of street canyon geometry.	Various methods, details described in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8	depending on method	partially	depending on method	n/a	x							
2.8.4	NDVI (Normalized difference vegetation index)	range from -1 to 1	O	D2.1 literature review	spatial mapping per neighborhood	distributional		*	*	*	*	*	*	*	remote sensing	https://www.usgs.gov/landsat-missions/landsat-normalized-difference-vegetation-index https://gisgeography.com/ndvi-normalized-difference-vegetation-index/ https://land.copernicus.eu/global/products/ndvi	no	before and after NBS implementation	n/a	we are very interested in receiving the outputs from the scientific partners									
2.9.1	NDBI (Normalized Difference Built-up Index)	range from 0 to 1	O	D2.1 literature review	spatial mapping per neighborhood	distributional		*	*	*	*	*	*	*	remote sensing	https://land.copernicus.eu/global/products/ndvi	no	before and after NBS implementation	n/a	we are very interested in receiving the outputs from the scientific partners									
2.9.2	Soil sealing (share of impervious surfaces)	%	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for green space management	spatial mapping	distributional	Synergies with other indicators related to mapping urban form. The data can be used as an index for other environmental (i.e., UHI, flooding and health/wellbeing indicators that require blue-green space mapping as the foundation for analysis. In relation to carbon injustices: Proxy indicator to determine soil climate mitigation potential	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	CO ₂ -R: If appropriate pixel and/or sub-pixel classification is carried out, a high level of evidence can be generated. Error factors can also be calculated based on sample areas.	Applied methods: Not typically a method for generating solid evidence. Tends to be more of a focus on generating an index to help quantify change.	various methods. Applied and EO/RS details in https://connectingnature.eu/nature-based-solution-evaluation-indicators-environmental-indicators-review	depending on method	before and after NBS implementation	n/a	x								
2.10	Daily temperature range	°C	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for climate resilience	spatial mapping	distributional	Evaluated from T _{max} , Monthly mean value of daily maximum temperature, T _{min} , Monthly mean value of daily minimum temperature, related to Warm spell duration index (WSDI) indicator	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	Straightforward assessment of ambient air temperature, Reliable in the long run	Requires a rather large amount of monitoring stations to be installed to monitor various NBS intervention areas	Ambient air temperature can be assessed through continuous monitoring of temperature, near the NBS intervention area, and calculation of the average minimum and maximum monthly temperature before and after NBS implementation. (details described in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8)	yes	Annually, at minimum, before and after NBS implementation	n/a	we are very interested in receiving the outputs from the scientific partners								
2.11	Surface reflectance - Albedo	unitless	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for climate resilience	spatial mapping	distributional	Direct relation to Rate of evapotranspiration, Land surface temperature and Urban Heat Island incidence indicators	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	Surface reflectance can be measured directly, Directly comparable to other variables such as cooling and greenhouse gases emissions, Albedo values for various known surfaces and land-uses already exist	Requires advanced equipment and judgment	Surface reflectance can be measured in the laboratory, in the field, and via remote sensing. (details in: https://op.europa.eu/s/09b8)	no	Annually	n/a	x								

Definition: Temporal justice refers to the interrelations between past, present and future conditions of injustices and inequalities, considering lock-ins and path dependency processes occurring in cities as well as the consequences of today's actions on future generations.

No	Indicator	Units	TYPE (S, P, O)	SOURCE	JUSTICE INDICATOR	JUSTICE TYPE	Synergies with other indicators	EVALUATION STAGE		SCALE APPLICABILITY						INDICATOR PROS & CONS		proposed method of indicator measurement/calculation	source and type of data	sensor based (yes/no/partially)	data collection frequency	data protection	CIPEL								
								pre-NBS	post-NBS	SPATIAL SCALE			TEMPORAL SCALE			PROS	CONS						Bolzano	Merano	Chania	Gzira	Leuven	Munich	Szombathely		
								site	district	city	short	medium	long																		
6.1	Land use and land use change [in NBS Handbook: Land use change and green space configuration]	various	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for green space management	observation in relation to population data variations on map	distribution	Strong synergies with other mapping indicators and other environmental indicators such as UHI, drainage, air quality, biodiversity as well as health and wellbeing.	•	•			•				Applied methods are used to support and supplement evidence generated through remote sensing metrics. As such, they should strengthen the evidence generated. GIS, historical maps, aerial imagery, and remotely sensed images have proven very effective in studying land change dynamics. These tools have been widely used also on the city level to assess changes over time and to predict future scenarios based on long-term sets of observations.	Remote sensing and GIS details in pg 122-131 : https://connectingnature.eu/nature-based-solution-evaluation-indicators-environmental-indicators-review	To be interpreted accurately, remotely sensed data are often supplemented with other data. Often these ancillary geospatial data can be found or included in a GIS for analysis. Remotely sensed data are a key technology for updating many types of GIS data.	no	tbd	n/a										
6.2	Green space configuration and variations over time [in NBS Handbook: Land use change and green space configuration]	various	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for green space management	observation in relation to population data variations on map	distribution	Strong synergies with other mapping indicators and other environmental indicators such as UHI, drainage, air quality, biodiversity as well as health and wellbeing. Can result from longterm monitoring of indicator 4.4.1 Share of Green Urban Areas and/or 4.2.2 Public Green Space distribution and or	•	•			•				Applied methods are used to support and supplement evidence generated through remote sensing metrics. As such, they should strengthen the evidence generated.	Same as Land use and land use change Also can result from longterm monitoring of indicator 4.4.1 Share of Green Urban Areas and/or 4.2.2 Public Green Space distribution and or	Same as Land use and land use change or Similar to indicator 4.4.1 Share of Green Urban Areas and/or 4.2.2 Public Green Space distribution and or	no	tbd	n/a										
6.3	Location of facilities (waste facilities, incinerators...)	n/a	O	D2.1 literature review	mapping neighborhoods and population groups	distribution		•	•	•	•						Location on map	maps, municipality records	no	tbd	n/a										x
6.4	Proportion of natural areas	% or ha	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for natural and climate hazards and for biodiversity	mapping neighborhoods and population groups	distribution	Land use change impacts on natural heritage (This indicator is also included in the flora-fauna-habitat (in-justices to provide a measure for habitat evaluation)	•	•			•	•			Simple and easy to assess	Estimation from maps and land-use maps. The area can be calculated using mapping tools, including satellite images from Google Maps. Calculate the share of the sum of natural and naturalized areas to the total area to get the indicator value. Natural areas include forests, swamps, streams, lakes, etc., but exclude parks and green infrastructure. Re-naturalized areas can be included.	Geographical and topographical data, Data on zones in natural or naturalized condition in the urban area of interest from, e.g., government agencies, municipalities, nature groups, universities, etc.	no	tbd	n/a										
6.5	Proportion of protected areas	%	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for biodiversity		distribution	Land use change impacts on natural heritage (This indicator is also included in the flora-fauna-habitat (in-justices to provide a measure for habitat evaluation)	•	•			•				A key indicator related to the biodiversity value of spaces. Relatively straightforward.	Propose methodology from CONNECTING Nature does not consider any sites that do not fall under the Natura 2000 directive. This can, therefore, miss many sites of value to nature conservation including designated sites, particularly in urban areas.	Proportion (%) of a designated protected area (e.g., Formal Urban Area) For Natura 2000: % area belonging to Natura 2000 network per grid cell. Typically, using a GIS programme (e.g., ArcGIS, QGIS) a Natura 2000 shapefile is clipped to a target area polygon, with remaining sites dissolved to avoid site overlaps. The proportion of the total area covered by Natura 2000 sites is calculated.	no	tbd	n/a										
6.6	Neighbourhood age (usually determined by average building age and land use change)	years	S	D2.1 literature review	mapping neighborhoods and population groups	distribution & recognition	Correlated to the distribution of green spaces and tree canopy	•				•	•	•				Census/Municipality data	no	tbd	n/a										
6.7	Urban/residential/productive area exposed to risks	ha	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for natural and climate hazards	population groups affected	distribution		•	•			•	•	•	•		Depending on risks: definition of risk (e.g. flood, heat wave) and risk mapping e.g. methodology for Area and population exposed to flooding pg 304-306 in: https://op.europa.eu/s/o9b9		no	tbd	n/a										
6.8	Vulnerable population (e.g. elderly, disable) exposed to risks	% per ha	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for natural and climate hazards	default	distribution	Link to areas exposed to risks	•	•			•	•	•	•			Census/Municipality data	no	tbd	n/a									x	
6.9	Urban/residential/productive area exposed to flood risks	ha	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for natural and climate hazards	mapping neighborhoods and population groups	distribution		•	•			•	•	•			Flood hazard maps cover the geographical areas which could be flooded according different scenarios in terms of the return period. For each scenario studied the following elements shall be taken into account: the flood extent, water depths or water level, flow velocity. Flood risk maps show the potential adverse consequences associated with flood scenarios referred to potential significant flood risks areas and expressed in terms of: number of inhabitants potentially affected; type of economic activity of the area potentially affected; and special installations GIS software or other specific software (i.e., Iber software) is required. pg 305 in: https://op.europa.eu/s/o9b9	Digital land cover maps from CORINE land cover project; demographic data from the studied area; and size and topography from digital elevation models (DEM) of each intervention. Data input type GIS data	no	tbd	n/a										
6.10	Buildings and infrastructures exposed to flood risks	number of buildings per km2	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for natural and climate hazards	mapping neighborhoods and population groups	distribution	Link to areas exposed to risks	•	•			•	•	•	•			Census/Municipality data	no	tbd	n/a										

No	Indicator	Units	TYPE (S, P, O)	SOURCE	JUSTICE INDICATOR	JUSTICE TYPE	Synergies with other indicators	EVALUATION STAGE			SCALE APPLICABILITY			INDICATOR PROS & CONS		proposed method of indicator measurement/calculation	source and type of data	sensor based yes/no/partially	data collection frequency	data protection	GPEL											
								pre-NBS	post-NBS	site	SPATIAL SCALE	TEMPORAL SCALE	PROS	CONS	Bolzano						Merano	Chania	Gzira	Leuven	Munich	Szombathely						
								district	city	Short	medium	long																				
7.1.1	Bridging – quality of interactions within and between social groups [In GA: Improved social cohesion, increased interaction density in neighbourhood community and limited gentrification]	n/a	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, recommended indicator for soc.just.&soc.coh.	disaggregation of data - population groups	distributional	Bonding social capital, Linking social capital, Trust in community, Solidarity between neighbours, Tolerance and respect, Perceived safety, Actual/real safety, Place attachment (Sense of place): Place Identity, Empowerment: Perceived control and influence over NBS decisionmaking, Social desirability, can indicate spatial (in)-justices	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	reliable indicator of resources that encourage reciprocity and collaboration between groups/communities/organisations; mostly inclusive, fosters tolerance and acceptance of different people, values, and beliefs through contact with diverse others; bridging, facilitates swifter recognition of new opportunities, and promotes social change, innovation and consensus among groups/communities/organisations; can improve economic development, growth, and employment	(bridging)may enable collusion, price fixing, or corruption;importance of a balance of bonding and bridging social capital, in that neither is negative per se but can be negative depending on the balance and context. The precise nature of the social identity boundaries, and the political salience of bonding and bridging groups are highly context specific	Questionnaire (survey procedure, paper-and pencil administration, computer-based administration) consisting of 2 items measuring the presence of BrSC type of connections of connections, and respondent's perception of quality of interactions within BrSC type of connections: 1.Thinking about people you interact with ... (e.g., in your community garden, in your local park), are most of them of: mixed occupations, mixed religion, mixed ethnic or linguistic group/race/caste/tribe, mixed educational backgrounds or levels, mixed income levels (Answers coded as [1] yes or [0] no) 2. Thinking about these same people, how would you rate the quality of your interactions with them? 1...2...3...4...5...6...7, extremely dissatisfied (1)... extremely satisfied (7) (details in: https://op.europa.eu/s/o9b8)	Surveys (questionnaires) required data: NBS characteristics for each city/site, more specifically objectives (short-, medium-, and longterm) and challenges	no	Before and after NBS implementation, then aligned with timing of targeted objectives	yes		x			x		x		
7.1.2	Bonding – quality of interactions within and between social groups [In GA: Improved social cohesion, increased interaction density in neighbourhood community and limited gentrification]	n/a	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, recommended indicator for soc.just.&soc.coh.	disaggregation of data - population groups	distributional	Bridging social capital, Linking social capital, Trust in community, Solidarity between neighbours, Tolerance and respect, Perceived safety, Actual/real safety, Place attachment (Sense of place): Place Identity, Empowerment: Perceived control and influence over NBS decisionmaking, Social desirability, can indicate spatial (in)-justices	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	reliable indicator of resources that encourage reciprocity and collaboration within groups/communities/organisations; mostly inclusive, fosters tolerance and acceptance of different people, values, and beliefs through contact with diverse others	(bonding) tightly structured and mostly exclusive networks with excessive levels of bonding tend to breed bias and racism, creating out-groups and exclusion, more impactful as a source of support to people who suffer from socio-economic hardship or poor health, than as a resource for initiatives that challenge the status-quo (e.g., NBS); several studies have found that bonding social capital has either no effect or a negative effect on economic outcomes	Questionnaire (survey procedure, paper-and pencil administration, computer-based administration) consisting of 2 items measuring the presence of BoSC type of connections, and respondent's perception of quality of interactions within BoSC type of connections: 1.Thinking about people you interact with ... (e.g., in your community garden, in your local park), are most of them of: the same family or kin group, the same religion, the same gender, the same age, the same ethnic or linguistic group/race/caste/tribe, the same occupation, the same educational background or level, mostly the same income (Answers coded as [1] yes or [0] no) 2. Thinking about these same people, how would you rate the quality of your interactions with them? 1...2...3...4...5...6...7, extremely dissatisfied (1)... extremely satisfied (7) (details in: https://op.europa.eu/s/o9b8)	Surveys (questionnaires) required data: NBS characteristics for each city/site, more specifically objectives (short-, medium-, and longterm) and challenges	no	Before and after NBS implementation, then aligned with timing of targeted objectives	yes		x			x		x		
7.1.3	Linking social capital [In GA: Improved social cohesion, increased interaction density in neighbourhood community and limited gentrification]	n/a	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for soc.just.&soc.coh.	disaggregation of data - population groups	distributional	Bridging social capital, Bonding social capital, Trust in community, Solidarity between neighbours, Tolerance and respect, Perceived safety, Actual/real safety, Place attachment (Sense of place): Place Identity, Empowerment: Perceived control and influence over NBS decisionmaking, Social desirability.	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	reliable indicator of resources that encourage reciprocity and collaboration among people or institutions at different levels of societal power hierarchy; indicator central to welfare and wellbeing; networks and ties with individuals, groups or corporate actors represented in public agencies, schools, business interests; oriented towards inclusiveness, high potential to further trust within community, to ground tolerance and respect, and to inculcate a community sense of safety	can be put to unhelpful purposes—e.g., nepotism, corruption, and suppression +/- It is important to have an appropriate balance of all types of social capital. Research has found that without linking types of social capital, bonding social capital alone may not be sufficient for community development to occur	Questionnaire (survey procedure, paper-and pencil administration, computer-based administration) consisting of 2 items measuring the presence of LSC type of connections, and respondent's perception of quality of interactions within LSC type of connections: 1.Thinking about people you interact with ... (e.g., meetings to define the open-space strategy, interactions in participatory sessions), are some of them of: higher social status, higher public/political power, higher financial capability (Answers coded as [1] yes or [0] no) 2. Thinking about these same people, how would you rate the quality of your collaborative interactions with them? 1...2...3...4...5...6...7, extremely dissatisfied (1)... extremely satisfied (7) (details in: https://op.europa.eu/s/o9b8)	Surveys (questionnaires) required data: NBS characteristics for each city/site, more specifically objectives (short-, medium-, and longterm) and challenges	no	Before and after NBS implementation, then aligned with timing of targeted objectives	yes					x		x		
7.2.1	Trust within the community [In GA: Improved social cohesion, increased interaction density in neighbourhood community and limited gentrification]	n/a	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, recommended indicator for soc.just.&soc.coh.	disaggregation of data - population groups (%)	distributional	Bridging social capital, Bonding social capital, Linking social capital, Solidarity between neighbours, Tolerance and respect, Perceived safety, Actual/real safety, Place attachment (Sense of place): Place Identity, Empowerment: Perceived control and influence over NBS decisionmaking, Social desirability, can indicate spatial (in)-justices	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	reliable indicator of solid premises for collaboration and reciprocity among members of a community; evolution of perception of trust can be traced back into the history of a community, and events that either decreased or boosted trust can be integrated as "lessons learnt" in the process of design and implementation of NBS; provides consistent information about the values that lay the foundation of both explicit and implicit norms within a community	highly context-dependent, its actual benefits for a local NBS can be foreseen through a good understanding of the values that shore up perceived trust, and the recent history of the community (i.e., through qualitative methods like case studies, focus groups, and/or participatory data collection)	Quantitative method: Questionnaire (survey procedure, paper-and-pencil administration, computer-based administration), perception of trust measured from "Trust and Solidarity" scale of the Integrated Questionnaire for the Measurement of Social Capital (SC-IQ), adapted to purpose of NBS research or Trust Scale in Neighbourhood Social Cohesion measurement tool Qualitative method: case study methodology – structured interviews, focus-groups, case study analysis; participatory data collections methods, such as collaborative participatory data collection, bodies as tools for data collection, photo elicitation (details in: https://op.europa.eu/s/o9b8)	Surveys (questionnaires, interviews) Required data: (Essential)NBS characteristics for each city/site, more specifically objectives (short-, medium-, and longterm) and challenges; (desirable) Data on significant events in the recent history of the community with implications for the evolution of a	no	Before and after NBS implementation, then aligned with timing of targeted objectives	yes		x			x		x		
7.2.2	Solidarity among neighbors	n/a	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, recommended indicator for soc.just.&soc.coh.	disaggregation of data - population groups (%)	distributional	Bridging social capital, Bonding social capital, Linking social capital, Trust within the community, Tolerance and respect, Perceived safety, Actual/real safety, Place attachment (Sense of place): Place Identity, Empowerment: Perceived control and influence over NBS decisionmaking, Social desirability, can indicate spatial (in)-justices	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	reliable indicator of solid premises for partnership around and towards the common good (i.e., awareness of sameness/similarity with fellow community members); evolution of solidarity practices can be traced back into the history of a community, and events that either endangered or inspired solidarity can be integrated as "lessons learnt" in the process of design and implementation of NBS; provides consistent information about the values that lay the foundation of both explicit and implicit norms within a community	highly abstract a concept that requires attention to operationalization so as to distinguish it from empathy, friendship, charity, dignity, reciprocity, altruism, and trust; highly context-dependent, its actual benefits for a local NBS can be foreseen through a good understanding of the existing structures for enactment of a core value like solidarity within a certain community, and of its recent history (i.e., through qualitative methods like case studies, focus groups, and/or participatory data collection)	Quantitative method: Questionnaire (survey procedure, paper-and-pencil administration, computer-based administration), perception of solidarity measured from "Trust and Solidarity" scale of the Integrated Questionnaire for the Measurement of Social Capital (SC-IQ), adapted to purpose of NBS research Qualitative method: case study methodology – structured interviews, focus-groups, case study analysis; participatory data collections methods, such as collaborative participatory data collection, bodies as tools for data collection, photo elicitation (details in: https://op.europa.eu/s/o9b8)	Surveys (questionnaires, interviews) Required data: (Essential)NBS characteristics for each city/site, more specifically objectives (short-, medium-, and longterm) and challenges; (desirable) Data on significant events in the recent history of the community with implications for the evolution of solidarity practices and relevant structures	no	Before and after NBS implementation, then aligned with timing of targeted objectives	yes									
7.2.3	Tolerance and respect	n/a	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, recommended indicator for soc.just.&soc.coh.	disaggregation of data - population groups (%)	distributional	Bridging social capital, Bonding social capital, Linking social capital, Trust in community, Solidarity between neighbours, Perceived safety, Actual/real safety, Place attachment (Sense of place): Place Identity, Empowerment: Perceived control and influence over NBS decisionmaking, Social desirability, can indicate spatial (in)-justices	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	reliable indicator of capacity to overcome differences (i.e., tolerance and respect are important resources in conflict management); evolution of these attitudes can be traced back into the history of a community, and events that challenged tolerance or brought forth deep-seated prejudices can be integrated as "lessons learnt" in the process of design and implementation of NBS; provides consistent information about the values that lay the foundation of both explicit and implicit norms within a community	highly context (culture)-dependent, its actual benefits for a local NBS can be foreseen through a good understanding of the evolution of tolerance and respect within a certain community, and of its recent history (i.e., through qualitative methods like case studies, focus groups, and/or participatory data collection); highly vulnerable to social desirability bias	Quantitative method: Questionnaire (survey procedure, paper-and-pencil administration, computer-based administration), "Tolerance or Respect" scale in Neighbourhood Social Cohesion measurement tool Qualitative method: case study methodology – structured interviews, focus-groups, case study analysis; participatory data collections methods, such as collaborative participatory data collection, bodies as tools for data collection, photo elicitation (details in: https://op.europa.eu/s/o9b8)	Surveys (questionnaires, interviews) Required data: (Essential)NBS characteristics for each city/site, more specifically objectives (short-, medium-, and longterm) and challenges; (desirable) Data on significant events in the recent history of the community with implications for the evolution of tolerance and respect, as well as	no	Before and after NBS implementation, then aligned with timing of targeted objectives	yes									
7.3	Perceived social interactions [In GA: Improved social cohesion, increased interaction density in neighbourhood community and limited gentrification]	Number (0-5) across 4 categories	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for soc.just.&soc.coh.	disaggregation of data - population groups (%)	distributional	Relation to Sociocultural inclusiveness (Connectedness to nature, Perceived social support, cohesion, and interaction...), Pro-environmental identity and behaviour, Sense of empowerment, Place Identity, Population dynamics, Participatory planning and governance, Trust in decision-making procedure, can indicate spatial (in)-justices	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	Direct information from people (perception, valuation...)	Need for rigorous methodology to avoid response bias	Questionnaire, example in https://op.europa.eu/s/o9b8	Surveys (questionnaires)	no	Annually or at minimum, before and after NBS implementation.	yes		x			x		x		
7.4	Quantity and quality of social interaction [In GA: Improved social cohesion, increased interaction density in neighbourhood community and limited gentrification]	Frequency	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for soc.just.&soc.coh.	disaggregation of data - population groups (%)	distributional	Other indicators on socio-cultural inclusiveness and to indicators on mental health, can indicate spatial (in)-justices	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	Easy to assess	Potential biases in self-reported data	Questionnaire (questions about any social activities they might have done in the NBS spot.)	Surveys (questionnaires)	no	min. before and after NBS implementation	yes		x	x		x		x		
7.5	Perception of socially supportive network	Number (0-5) across 5 categories	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for soc.just.&soc.coh.	disaggregation of data - population groups (%)	distributional	Relation to Sociocultural inclusiveness (Connectedness to nature, Perceived social support, cohesion, and interaction...), Pro-environmental identity and behaviour, Sense of empowerment, Place Identity, Population dynamics, Participatory planning and governance, Trust in decision-making procedure, can indicate spatial (in)-justices	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	Direct information from people (perception, valuation...)	Need for rigorous methodology to avoid response bias	Questionnaire, example in https://op.europa.eu/s/o9b8	Surveys (questionnaires)	no	Annually or at minimum, before and after NBS implementation.	yes						x			
7.6	Perceived safety of neighborhood		O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for soc.just.&soc.coh.	disaggregation of data - population groups (%)	distributional	Bridging social capital, Bonding social capital, Linking social capital, Solidarity between neighbours, Tolerance and respect, Actual/real safety, Place attachment (Sense of place): Place Identity, Empowerment: Perceived control and influence over NBS decisionmaking, Social desirability, HWB indicators (morbidity of chronic stress, depression and anxiety, enhanced physical activity, aggressiveness and violence, exploration behavior in children) can indicate spatial (in)-justices	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	reliable indicator of challenges to neighborhood/community resources for a shared sense of trust, and for an individual sense of well-being; perception of safety with respect to green spaces (parks, trees etc.) can inform NBS on best approaches so as to meet community's capacity to manage the demands of environment; consistently adds to the information on a community's shared notion of trust and solidarity	measurement scales usually limit the investigation to physical conditions related to housing (e.g., garbage, insects, and inadequate heat) and neighborhood (e.g., noise, crime, abandoned buildings, dark streets and sidewalks, and low accessibility to shops) hazards play an important role into a shared sense of community safety as well	Quantitative: Questionnaire (survey procedure, paper-and pencil administration, computer-based administration) 8 items Conflict and Violence Scale from "Social Cohesion and Inclusion" module of the Integrated Questionnaire for the Measurement of Social Capital (SC-IQ), adapted to the purposes of NBS research Qualitative: case study methodology – structured interviews, focus-groups, case study analysis; participatory data collections methods, such as collaborative participatory data collection, bodies as tools for data collection, photo elicitation Public participation geographic information system (PPGIS) methods/approaches (details in: https://op.europa.eu/s/o9b8)	Surveys (questionnaires) required data: NBS characteristics for each city/site, more specifically objectives (short-, medium-, and longterm) and challenges	no	Before and after NBS implementation, then aligned with timing of targeted objectives	yes									x
7.7	Realised safety		O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for soc.just.&soc.coh.	disaggregation of data - realised safety per neighborhood-p population groups	distributional	Bridging social capital, Bonding social capital, Linking social capital, Solidarity between neighbours, Tolerance and respect, perceived safety, Place attachment (Sense of place): Place Identity, Empowerment: Perceived control and influence over NBS decisionmaking, Social desirability, HWB indicators (morbidty of chronic stress, depression and anxiety, enhanced physical activity, aggressiveness and violence, exploration behavior in children) can indicate spatial (in)-justices	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	objective indicator of challenges to neighborhood/community resources for a shared sense of trust, and for an individual sense of well-being +safety hazards related to green spaces (parks, trees, etc.) can inform NBS on best approaches so as to meet community's capacity to manage the demands of environment; consistently adds to the information on a community's shared notion of trust and solidarity	measurement scales usually limit the investigation to physical conditions related to housing (e.g., garbage, insects, and inadequate heat) and neighborhood (e.g., noise, crime, abandoned buildings, dark streets and sidewalks, and low accessibility to shops) hazards play an important role into a shared sense of community safety as well	Quantitative: objective measures (e.g., reported crimes in a neighbourhood per capita, crime density, number of crimes per building, or number of emergency calls) Public participation geographic information system (PPGIS) methods/approaches (details in: https://op.europa.eu/s/o9b8)	Data from local authorities (crime data), NBS design (lighting, sidewalks, etc.) required data: NBS characteristics for each city/site, more specifically objectives (short-, medium-, and longterm) and challenges	no	Before and after NBS implementation, then aligned with timing of targeted objectives	n/a									

No	Indicator	Units	TYPE (B, P, O)	SOURCE	JUSTICE INDICATOR	JUSTICE TYPE	Synergies with other indicators	EVALUATION STAGE		SCALE APPLICABILITY						INDICATOR PROS & CONS		Proposed method of indicator measurement/calculation	Sensor based (yes/no/partially)	Source and type of data	Data collection frequency	Data protection	CPet							
								pre-NBS	post-NBS	SPATIAL SCALE	TEMPORAL SCALE	PROS	CONS	Bolzano	Merano	Chania	Gera						Leuven	Munich	Szombathely					
								site	district	city	Short	medium	long																	
8.1.1	Mean land and/or property value in proximity to green space	€	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, recommended indicators of new economic opportunities and green jobs	spatial mapping, possible indicator of gentrification	distributional	Synergies with the Green space accessibility indicator, and the other indicators in the New Economic Opportunities and Green Jobs indicator group	*	*	*	*	*	[pre]	*	*	The indicator is easy to define	A great deal of input data needs to be collected and processed	Hedonic analysis can be used to understand the effect of NBS on property value. This method enables analysis of property sale data, yielding the difference in sale prices as a function of various attributes that are thought to affect the price. (details in: https://op.europa.eu/h/0988)	no	Property sale data from municipalities, cadastre and real estate agencies as well as area and categorisation of green spaces	Before and after NBS implementation	N/A								
8.1.2	Change in mean house prices/rental markets	€	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, recommended indicators of new economic opportunities and green jobs	spatial mapping, possible indicator of gentrification	distributional		*	*	*	*	*	[pre]	*	*			The change in house/rental prices in NBS intervention areas will be measured primarily using secondary analysis of property market data (assessments in Zoopla or similar). (details in: https://op.europa.eu/h/0988)	no	City official data, city platforms, questionnaires, small-medium enterprise account (Related to de NBS investment zone) input data (no business) (€/m2), (no business or no users) (€/year)	Before and after NBS implementation	N/A								
8.1.3	Changes in property incomes	%	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicator for soc.just.Assoc.coh.	spatial mapping, possible indicator of gentrification	distributional		*	*	*	*	*	[pre]	*	*	It could be difficult to get the data necessary to calculate the indicator.		The indicator can be defined as the increase, in terms of percentage, of the profit or income received by virtue of owning property after the implementation of the Origin Scenario. The measurement procedure entails an ex-post indicator evaluation. Calculation methodology in page 976: https://op.europa.eu/h/0988	no	Data provided by national and/or private real estate monitoring agencies, values of rent received from the ownership of land and/or real estate	Before and after NBS implementation	n/a								
8.2.1	Number of new jobs created	€/year	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, recommended indicators of new economic opportunities and green jobs		distributional		*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	Medium or long term assessment; it needs municipality data from different departments; This KPI will require citizens' collaboration, so recovering the data could be difficult.		Essentially a 'before-after' indicator which captures the part of the employment increase that is (a) direct consequence of NBS implementation (workers employed to implement the NBS project should not be directly counted). The positions needs to be filled (vacant posts are not counted) and increase the total number of jobs in the enterprise. Calculation details in: https://op.europa.eu/h/0988	no	City official data, city platforms, questionnaires, small-medium enterprise accounts... (Related to de NBS investment zone) - (No jobs) (€/m2) (No jobs or no users) (€/year)	Before and after NBS implementation	N/A		*						
8.2.2	Number of new jobs in green sector	%	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicators of new economic opportunities and green jobs		distributional	Synergies with the indicator group Economic activity & Green Jobs indicators		*	*	*	*	*	*	*	Easy to measure	Requires extensive processing of input data if not already available	This indicator will be equal to 0 in the baseline scenario (i.e., prior to NBS actions) and will be implemented in a Long Term Scenario, using data made available after NBS have been implemented to determine the number of new jobs created in the green sector. calculation details in: https://op.europa.eu/h/0988	no	Data about the number of green jobs and total number of jobs from business registrations and/or administrative documents; National Statistical Institute; Chamber of Commerce.	Before and after NBS implementation. Recommended annual assessment.	N/A		*						
8.3	Gross value added to local economy from new business creation	%/year	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, recommended indicators of new economic opportunities and green jobs				*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	Medium or long term assessment; it needs municipality data from different departments; This KPI will require citizens' collaboration, so recovering the data could be difficult.		Number of business created (direct value buss related NBS by zone) Direct value on business created by zone NBS affected, before and after implementation, during the established period. Number of business created - n * Z (no business) (€/m2) Where n is referring to the number of business and Z to its increased value (NBS related by zone), during the established period of implementation (directly related to the each particular NBS) Gross value added (GVA) Defined as the difference between the value of goods and services produced and the cost of raw materials and other non-labour inputs, which are used up in production. The research should conclude what is the total contribution of NBS in % of the total GVA to the region/area economy in EUR per year.	no	City official data, city platforms, questionnaires, small-medium enterprise account (Related to de NBS investment zone) input data (no business) (€/m2), (no business or no users) (€/year)	Annually	N/A								
8.4	Value of rates paid by businesses in proximity to NBS	€/year	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicators of new economic opportunities and green jobs			Synergies with the indicator group New Economic Opportunities and Green Jobs indicators and the indicators Distribution of public green space and Accessibility of urban green spaces	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	The indicator is easy to define	A substantial amount of input data needs to be collected	Value of rates paid by businesses established in the area surrounding implemented NBS (within 300 m linear distance of NBS of at least 0.5 ha in size) To accurately determine the impact of NBS implementation on the value of rates paid by nearby businesses, it is necessary to gather data over a period of years to understand trends and business activities before and after NBS implementation. Further details: https://op.europa.eu/h/0988	no	Input data from municipalities, planning departments, and interviews with local businesses as well as area and categorisation of green spaces	Before and after NBS implementation	N/A								
8.5	Initial costs of NBS implementation (Project's initial costs are those occurring during the design and construction phases)	€	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicators of new economic opportunities and green jobs				*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	Top-down synthetic approach could ensure rapid estimation but low accuracy;	Bottom-up analytical approach and parametric approach are very time-consuming.	Different methods can be used to assess initial cost and the choice among them depends on the detail of the available data and of the evaluation itself. Details in: https://op.europa.eu/h/0988	no	Parametric costs; Similar projects	at the beginning of the project	N/A		*						
8.6	Maintenance costs of NBS	€/year	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicators of new economic opportunities and green jobs			Connected to other economic and labour indicators	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*			Data can be collected via an economic and labour questionnaire to be distributed to the entities in charge of long-term maintenance of the planned or implemented NBS. Estimation from project financial assessment.	no	Cost estimates or actual cost reporting from entities administering the NBS and sub-contractors.	At least once after NBS implementation. Potential to estimate maintenance costs during planning stage.	N/A		*						
8.7.0	Avoided costs due to NBS implementation	€	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicators of new economic opportunities and green jobs				*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	It is a frequently used benefit estimation technique, both because it is a common sense approach and because the information needed to assess avoided costs is often readily achievable.	It could be very time consuming since many different models should be implemented to assess the expected damages.	The avoided costs method estimates the cost that the community would incur in the absence of project scenario implementation. Given that NBS could prevent multiple risks, the avoided costs is equal to the sum of costs associated with responding to each risk faced by NBS. Thus, for each hazardous phenomenon regarding the study area, it is essential to assess the expected damages and the cost of actions taken in response to the phenomenon after it occurs.	no	Different type of data (spatial data, models, parametric costs, etc.), depending on the hazardous phenomenon taken into account.	It could be assessed when the project scenario is clear and defined.	N/A								
8.8	Payback period for NBS	years	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicators of new economic opportunities and green jobs			Connected to other economic indicators such as initial cost and maintenance costs.	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	Easy to understand and to calculate. Once the calculation method is defined, it is unambiguous and does not lend itself to misinterpretation.	It does not consider the flows achieved in the periods following the payback period; it does not consider the financial value of time; it does not consider the amount of capital invested; it is an indicator of risk (temporal exposure), not of yield.	The formula to calculate the payback period (PP) of an investment depends on whether the periodic cash inflows from the project are even or uneven. Calculation details in: https://op.europa.eu/h/0988	no	Initial costs and cash flows for the proposed project.	It could be assessed when the project scenario is clear and defined.	N/A		*						
8.9	Social return on investment (SROI)	€/€	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicators of new economic opportunities and green jobs			SROI is highly dependent upon the collection of relevant Social well-being indicators to provide the underlying drivers of valuation. Synergies with Benefit/Cost and Private Finance indicators as data collected for SROI may be useful for these measures and vice versa.	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	The indicator is a meaningful and comparable at multiple levels of aggregation and across different projects; It is a powerful tool for assessing 'value for money' (VfM) of projects with a range of social benefits. It is widely supported by a range of social investment NGOs, think-tanks, impact investors and associations, the EU and the WHO.	It is time-consuming and often quite expensive to conduct an SROI assessment; it requires significant expertise to calculate, to explain and to evaluate its significance; SROI - along with other approaches to social value measurement - has been widely criticised for incorporating estimated attributions of value, 'heroic' assumptions of causality and over-simplifying the unique and heterogeneous	Social Return on Investment (SROI) is generally reported as a ratio between the monetary value of outputs/outcomes and the monetary value of inputs, further details pg 1117-1123: https://op.europa.eu/h/0988	no	Amount (in monetary terms) of investment in the NBS being assessed for SROI, social and well being indicators		N/A		*						
8.10	Subsidies applied for private NBS measures	€/year	O	NBS evaluation Handbook, additional indicators of new economic opportunities and green jobs			Synergies with the indicator group New Economic Opportunities & Green Jobs indicators	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	The indicator is easy to define	Medium or long term assessment. Data are required from multiple different municipal departments.; This KPI may require input from citizens	The subsidies applied for private NBS measures can be expressed either the number of subsidies, or as a monetary value (in EUR). Further details in: https://op.europa.eu/h/0988	no	Local and national governments, as well as the individuals or organisations receiving the aforementioned subsidies, serve as sources of information for this metric. This may include City official data, city platforms, questionnaires, and/or small-medium enterprise accounts (related to the NBS investment zone)	Annually, both before and after NBS implementation	N/A		*						
8.11	Avoided costs regarding heating/cooling consumption in buildings (energy savings)	€/year	O	Indicator pre-selected in GA relevant to the expected IMPACT B. Creation of 'communities of practice'...tested, well-documented, up-scalable and marketable NBS	spatial mapping	distributional	Synergies with 3.3 Avoided greenhouse gas emissions from reduced building energy consumption and Carbon emissions due to building cooling/heating MAYBE IN thermal!!	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*			Energy use conversion to euro, mapping of emissions	no	building energy sources and electrical energy use; municipal sources or from records of building- or district-level energy consumption from the building owner or utility company. Energy conversion factors to energy costs	Before and after NBS implementation	n/a								
8.12	Monetary value of urban forests including air quality, increasing property values and impacts	€	O	Indicator pre-selected in GA relevant to the expected IMPACT B. Creation of 'communities of practice'...tested, well-documented, up-scalable and marketable NBS				*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*			Methodologies in literature: https://gpress.clemson.edu/publication/benefits-of-urban-forests-and-determining-their-value/ https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1389934121001787 https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/10/7/2461	no		Before and after NBS implementation	yes, if surveys are used								
8.13	Trend in Municipal budgets	%	O	Indicator pre-selected in GA relevant to the expected IMPACT D. Enhanced implementation of relevant ... policies and programmes			Related to other NBS value indicators and policy learning	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*			% of municipal budget planned/spent for NBS interventions/relevant activities	no	Municipality budget planning and spending	Before and after NBS implementation	N/A								
8.14	Investments in NBS triggered by the project	No.	O	Indicator pre-selected in GA relevant to the expected The creation of a European reference framework and the establishment of EU leadership in a new global market (supply and demand) for nature-based solutions			Related to other NBS value indicators and social/policy learning	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*				no		after NBS implementation (annually?)	N/A	At least 3 additional investments by defined private actors in further piloting NBS							
8.15	Number of innovative business models launched	No.	O	Indicator pre-selected in GA relevant to the expected The creation of a European reference framework and the establishment of EU leadership in a new global market (supply and demand) for nature-based solutions				*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*				no		after NBS implementation (annually?)	N/A								
8.16	Number of small scale and inclusive business initiatives developed	No.	O	Indicator pre-selected in GA relevant to the expected The creation of a European reference framework and the establishment of EU leadership in a new global market (supply and demand) for nature-based solutions	Population groups that own new businesses	distributional	Synergies with Gross value added to local economy from new business creation	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*				no		after NBS implementation (annually?)	N/A								
8.17	Number of patents filed	No.	O	Indicator pre-selected in GA relevant to the expected The creation of a European reference framework and the establishment of EU leadership in a new global market (supply and demand) for nature-based solutions				*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*				no		after NBS implementation (annually?)	N/A							1 developed	